

GreenDIGIT

Deliverable D4.1 State Of The Art In RI and Digital Infrastructure Sustainability and Technologies Assessment for Energy Efficiency and Impact

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p18-21 (Sec 3.1.1-3.1.3)	Added in-depth analysis of the EC directive (May 2024, 2024/1364, ...) along with the coverage of gap analysis between EED and RIs, reporting methodology and calculation framework.
p23-31 (Sec 3.2)	Described unified monitoring architecture for sustainable digital infrastructures, covering multi-layer telemetry, integration of hardware- and software-based monitoring, and key design aspects including observability, reporting, and federation challenges.
p41-45 (Sec 3.8.1-3.8.5)	Addressed sustainability and monitoring aspects in HPC and HPC-AI Data Centre architectures.
p45 (Sec 3.8.6)	Described integration methods for Kubernetes with traditional schedulers to support flexible, containerised AI and HPC workloads.
p47-60 (Sec 3.9)	Extended sustainability and environment metric coverage to include carbon (CUE, Scope 1–3), water (WUE), energy reuse (ERF), renewable energy (REF), lifecycle impacts (LCA), embodied carbon estimation models, and AI-specific efficiency indicators.
p64-68 (Sec 4.5)	Covered details on GPU scheduling and sharing consolidation for flexible, container-based allocation of accelerators , covering device plugins, MIG integration, and dynamic resource allocation.

p106-113
(Sec 9.4)

Added overview of key industry, policy, and research initiatives addressing sustainable data centres, including European frameworks, global collaborations, hyperscaler strategies, and relevant Horizon Europe projects.

Authors

Author	Partner	Contribution to Section
Gergely Sipos	EGI	1, 2, 3.1
Álvaro López García	CSIC	3.3
Zdenek Sustr	CESNET	3.2, 4
Jiří Sitera	CESNET	3.5, 4
Edouard Guegain	Greenspector	3.6, 5.3
Istvan Pintye	SZTAKI	4.3
Tamas Maray	SZTAKI	4.3
Andrei Tsaregorodtsev	CNRS	4
Kostas Chounos	UTH	5.1
Nicole Simone Martinelli	CNIT	5.2
Alessandro Musumeci	CNIT	5.2
Krzysztof Dombek	PSNC	5.4, 6.3
Shashikant Ilager	UvA	6.1
Gonçalo Teixeira de Pinho Ferreira	UvA	6.2
Sebastian Gallenmüller	TUM	6.3
Kilian Holzinger	TUM	6.3
Roberto Trasarti	CNR	6.1, 6.2, 10
Andrea Passarella	CNR	6.2, 10
Yuri Demchenko	UvA	7, 8, 9
Adnan Tahir	UvA	7.3

Reviewers

Name	Organisation
Yuri Demchenko	UvA
Gergely Sipos	EGI
Shashikant Ilager	UvA

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
PDIT	Installed information technology power demand (kW)
SDC	Data centre total floor area (m ²)
SCR	Data centre computer room floor area (m ²)
EDC	Total energy consumption (kWh)
EIT	Total energy consumption of IT equipment (kWh)
CBtG	Average battery capacity (kW)
WIN	Total water input (cubic metres)
WIN-POT	Total potable water input (cubic metres)
EREUSE	Waste heat reused (kWh)
TWH	Average waste heat temperature
TIN	Average setpoint information technology equipment intake air temperature
CDD	Cooling degree days (°C C-degree days)
ERES-TOT	Total renewable energy consumption (kWh)
ERES-GOO	Total renewable energy consumption from Guarantees of Origin (kWh)
ERES-PPA	Total renewable energy consumption from Power Purchasing Agreements (kWh)
ERES-OS	Total renewable energy consumption from on-site renewables (kWh)
CSERV	ICT capacity for servers
CSTOR	ICT capacity for storage equipment (petabytes)
BIN	Incoming traffic bandwidth (GB/s)
BOUT	Outgoing traffic bandwidth (GB/s)
TIN	Incoming data traffic (exabytes)
TOUT	Outgoing data traffic (exabytes)
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness
WUE	Water Usage Effectiveness
ERF	Energy Reuse Factor
REF	Renewable Energy Factor
LPWAN	Low Power Wide Area Network
IDAF	Infrastructure Data Analytics Function
MDAF	Management Data Analytics Function
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
TSDB	Time-Series Database
PromQL	Prometheus Query Language
API	Application Programming Interface
REST	Representational State Transfer

Executive Summary

The GreenDIGIT project is a European initiative aimed at reducing the environmental footprint of Research Infrastructures (RIs) and digital services by enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability. As digital infrastructures continue to grow in scale and complexity, their energy consumption and carbon emissions have become pressing concerns. This report, Deliverable D4.1, provides a comprehensive State of the Art (SotA) assessment of current technologies, methodologies, and policies that influence the sustainability of RIs, with a particular focus on metrics, optimization strategies, and software solutions for energy-efficient operations.

The presented **State of the Art** (SotA) analysis provides a comprehensive overview of existing technologies, methodologies, and best practices for improving energy efficiency and enhancing the sustainability of scientific computing and digital research infrastructures. It serves as a foundational study for WP4, WP5, and WP6, supporting the design, development, and deployment of GreenDIGIT's sustainability-oriented frameworks and tools addressing such aspects as energy efficiency, carbon-aware computing, sustainable data management, and research reproducibility.

The deliverable assesses technological approaches and best practices across multiple infrastructure layers and data collection and processing continuum, including cloud computing, high-throughput computing (HTC), high performance computing (HPC), 5G networks, and IoT environments, providing insights into how digital RIs can optimize their operations while minimizing energy consumption and carbon emissions.

The document is structured around major technology domains that play a crucial role in reducing the environmental impact of digital infrastructures: sustainability metrics and monitoring, scientific workflow scheduling and optimisation, energy-efficient networks, research data management, experimental research reproducibility, and sustainable software design practices. Across these domains, the report examines not only existing technologies and ongoing research, but also architectural, monitoring, and reporting requirements needed to support next-generation sustainable RIs, including federated observability, heterogeneous computing environments, and AI-enabled infrastructures.

The deliverable provides an extended analysis of existing practices for data centre sustainability metrics collection, monitoring, and reporting. In addition to energy efficiency and carbon-related indicators, the reports expands the coverage of environmental metrics to include Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE), Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE), Renewable Energy Factor (REF), Energy Usage Factor (ERF), Scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions, lifecycle assessment (LCA) perspectives, embodied carbon estimation models, and AI-specific efficiency indicators. The report outlines the European Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) reporting requirements for data centers and examines the need for harmonized monitoring across heterogeneous and federated RIs. Existing monitoring infrastructures like EGI, EOSC, and Prometheus are assessed alongside a unified monitoring architecture for sustainable digital infrastructures, covering multi-layer telemetry, the integration of hardware- and software-based monitoring, and key design aspects related to observability, reporting, and federation challenges.

Although the report considers cooling and thermal management as important elements of the broader sustainability landscape, the direct optimisation of cooling infrastructures is not within the current scope of GreenDIGIT, which is focused primarily on monitoring, metrics, workload optimisation, software practices, and sustainable data management.

A key finding of this study is that research infrastructures often lack the necessary tools and frameworks to effectively measure, monitor, and optimize their environmental impact. While significant advancements have been made in energy-efficient computing, carbon-aware workload scheduling, and optimized data storage, their adoption remains fragmented. This fragmentation is further amplified by the growing heterogeneity of modern digital RIs, including GPU-accelerated HPC systems, AI-native clusters, dense cooling-aware data centre designs, and federated cloud and HTC environments, all of which introduce different sustainability monitoring and assessment requirements. Scientific workflows are often executed without consideration of energy efficiency or carbon intensity, leading to excessive energy consumption and inefficiencies across high-throughput computing (HTC), high-performance computing (HPC), and cloud environments. Similarly, scientific data management strategies are not yet optimized for sustainability, with redundant data storage and inefficient replication practices contributing to unnecessary energy usage.

To address these challenges, GreenDIGIT is working toward the development of federated environmental monitoring infrastructures, enabling RIs to track, report, and optimize their sustainability metrics in real-time across heterogeneous computing environments. This includes the exploration of unified monitoring approaches that combine multi-layer telemetry, infrastructure-level observability, and harmonized sustainability reporting across cloud, HTC, HPC, and AI-enabled platforms. The project is also exploring energy-aware scheduling mechanisms, which will help align computational workloads with low-carbon energy availability. These advancements will significantly improve energy efficiency and carbon footprint management for scientific computing environments.

The overview and analysis of sustainable software design principles and practices will help the project to implement these practices in scientific applications design and efficient use. By enhancing Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and integrating intelligent experiment reproducibility frameworks, the project ensures that research workflows and experimental data collection can be reused and optimized, reducing redundant computations and minimizing energy waste.

Based on the presented State of the Art analysis, the deliverable provides key recommendations for energy efficiency and environmental sustainability of the future research infrastructures:

- Standardized environmental metrics reporting across all European research infrastructures, leveraging federated monitoring platforms.
- Adoption of energy-aware workload scheduling, integrating real-time carbon intensity data for optimized task execution.
- Implementation of sustainable software design practices, including energy-efficient programming, hardware-aware optimization, and carbon-aware software execution.
- Enhancing scientific experiment reproducibility through low-impact digital experiment frameworks, reducing redundant computational efforts and improving efficiency of research data management, in particular compliance with the FAIR data principles.

The report also highlights the growing sustainability implications of Gen-AI and accelerator-intensive scientific computing, particularly in relation to energy demand, monitoring requirements, and AI-specific efficiency assessment.

As the project progresses, GreenDIGIT will develop and validate prototype solutions, helping European research infrastructures transition to greener, more energy-efficient operations. These efforts will contribute to reducing the environmental impact of scientific computing while maintaining high-performance research capabilities.

1 Introduction

Lowering the environmental impact of digital services and technologies has to become a priority for both the operation of existing digital services and the design of future digital infrastructures. Indeed, digital infrastructures are responsible for 5 to 9 % of the world's total electricity use and more than 2% of global emissions. In 2018, data centres accounted for 2.7 % of the electricity demand in the EU-28. Within the Union, data centres accounted for 2.7 % of electricity demand in 2018 and will reach 3.21 % by 2030 if development continues on the current trajectory¹.

The GreenDIGIT project², funded in the Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures (RI) programme runs between 2024-2026 to research, prototype and validate various technical and non-technical approaches and tools that digital service providers within RI communities can adopt to lower their environmental impact.

GreenDIGIT will deliver contributions and will move beyond State of the Art in 3 areas:

1. Policy and Governance: Establishing frameworks for measuring and managing the environmental impact of digital services through the full RI lifecycle.
2. Resource Efficiency: Develop software tools, frameworks and infrastructures that can support digital service providers in measuring and lowering their environmental impact by optimising operation.
3. Skills and Collaboration: Run community building and training programmes for RI provider and user communities to increase their understanding and skills about environmental impact lowering techniques and to foster cooperation among RIs around such topics.

This deliverable is a State of the Art (SotA) study covering the 2nd area from this list. A separate milestone document, titled "MS8.1 Study of existing policies and regulations" provides SotA for area 1, and another deliverable, titled "D10.2 Definition of the competences and skills for sustainability and environmental impact awareness and a set of training modules" already offers solutions for area 3.

The next section 2 of the document details the GreenDIGIT contributions to area 2, by positioning the various software tools/frameworks/infrastructures of the project into a single architecture. This architecture, and the various areas it covers serves as a basis for the chapters of this SotA.

The remainder of the deliverable is structured in the following way. Section 3 provides an extensive overview of the metrics for data centre environmental sustainability. Section 4 is focused on the scheduling approaches for green optimisation of scientific workflows. Section 5 provides existing practices, approaches and used metrics for monitoring the energy efficiency of networks, 5G infrastructure, IoT and mobile environment. Section 6 covers sustainability aspects in research infrastructure for experimental research including sustainability in Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and experiment reproducibility metadata formats. Section 7 provides overview of the sustainable software design practices that are important for scientific software and applications. This section also provides an overview of the best practices recommended by the leading cloud providers AWS and Microsoft Azure. Section 8 analyses data management aspects for both supporting

¹ Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AJOL_2023_231_R_0001&qid=1695186598766

² GreenDIGIT Project: <https://greendigit-project.eu/>

environmental research and ensuring energy efficiency of the data management infrastructure; the latter is important for research and for industry that both face challenges with collecting, storing and processing huge amounts of data. Section 9 touches ongoing research, emerging challenges due to GenAI workloads, initiatives, industry programmes, and relevant community efforts for sustainable digital Infrastructures. The final section provides summary and vision for future implementation of recommendations that come out of the presented State of the Art analysis.

2 GreenDIGIT Software Solutions

In the second half of 2024 GreenDIGIT run a comprehensive landscape analysis³ about digital RI practices and identified needs and gaps in existing practices, approaches, metrics, and tools in addressing environmental sustainability and impact lowering impact. The landscape study revealed a gap in the existence and consistent adoption of software tools within IT centres and user communities to track their environmental footprint and to optimise their operations to lower such impacts.

The GreenDIGIT project aims to fill this gap by providing solutions to energy-related impact minimisation. The focus is on energy, because the landscape analysis showed that digital service providers consider energy consumption as their biggest polluting factor. The below listing details the various technical solutions that GreenDIGIT started working on, and will deliver and validate in 2025-26. These solutions are also presented in Figure 1 in an architecture that positions them towards.

1. Metrics collection infrastructure to support RIs in the collection, aggregation and analysis of environmental impact-related metrics of their digital services. The infrastructure should be capable to work across the spectrum of equipment used within digital RIs (network-edge-IoT-cloud-HTC-HPC). (Lead: EGI, contributions from EGI, SLICES, SoBigData, EBRAINS)
2. Federated data management infrastructure to support RIs in the optimal use of their storage and network equipment by optimising data transfer, data replication and data storage instructions within federated environments. (Lead: CNR)
3. Digital scientific experiment⁴ reproducibility infrastructure to support RIs in the registration, lookup and re-play of previously conducted digital experiments, eliminating/minimising the need of re-executing scientific calculations that have been already performed in the past. (CNR, TUM)
4. Environments and frameworks that provide integrated support for users to the lowering of the environmental footprint of their activities on digital RIs, by building on, and expanding the solutions from the previous 1, 2, 3 points. Particularly: Making informed decisions for resource allocation using data from the metrics infrastructure (area 1); Minimising data transfers and storage with the use of the federated data infrastructure (area 2); Offering scientific reproducibility with minimised computational impact (area 3). The implementations foreseen within this area are:
 - 4.1. An extension to the AI4OS AI platform that can optimise the execution of AI model training and inference tasks on federated cloud-HPC infrastructures. (IFCA-CSIC)
 - 4.2. An extension to the DIRAC middleware that can run massively parallel applications on federated High Throughput Cluster resources. (CNRS)
 - 4.3. A JupyterHub environment that integrates with the rest of the ecosystem and can serve as a front-end towards users and user communities to perform computational analysis on digital RI services, with minimal impact on the environmental. (TUM, UvA)
 - 4.4. A data centre automation service that monitors the use of computers, the trend of incoming user requests and based on these switches HW on/off to lower energy consumption without causing Quality-of-Service failures towards the users. (SZTAKI)
 - 4.5. Workload manager (resource broker) that can choose the most suitable type of HW resources based on job characteristics inside one compute centre or among multiple centres, considering the environmental impact and expected time of completion of compute tasks. (E.g. for compute-heavy, I/O heavy, memory heavy tasks) (CESNET)

³ Deliverable 3.1 RIs Landscape review, best practices analysis and identification of needs within the ESFRI RIs

⁴ The word 'experiment' in this context is used for any type/form of data analysis application that runs on digital infrastructures. Experiments can exist in the form of workflows, VMs, containers, compute jobs, etc.

4.6. Batch scheduler that can delay the execution of jobs to periods when the energy used by the centre is lower in carbon content, making the best compromise between time of completion and environmental impact. (CESNET)

Figure 1: GreenDIGIT software solutions for lower environmental impact (green boxes with orange labels).

The next sections of this document goes into the SotA review of the context of these GreenDIGIT developments.

3 Metrics for data centre environmental sustainability

3.1 European Regulation for Data Center Environmental Sustainability Reporting

In the evolving landscape of data center management, an increasing emphasis is placed on the intersection of sustainability and compliance with government regulations. As the pace of digital transformation continues to accelerate, it fuels an increasing demand for data centers, culminating in heightened energy consumption, carbon emissions, and water usage. However, in the face of these challenges, various government directives around the world have come to the forefront as key regulatory frameworks designed to manage these environmental impacts. The most relevant for GreenDIGIT in this respect is the EU Energy Efficiency Directive (EED)⁵. According to the EED:

- By 15th of May 2024 and annually thereafter, Member States shall require owners and operators of data centres with a non-redundant rated electrical load of at least 500 kW to (1) monitor and report various energy performance metrics. These metrics include energy consumption, power utilization, temperature, heat utilization, and the use of renewable energy AND (2) to implement energy recovery facilities, aiming for up to 20% energy recovery, which can be achieved by connecting to district heating networks.

Figure 2: The EC reporting portal

- Newly constructed data centres are expected to achieve a Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) value of 1.2. Additionally, from 2026, data centres must source all their energy from renewable sources, either physically or virtually. The EC database where the data centres have to report is already available⁶. Some of the countries already have data centres listed, and this includes some academic

⁵ Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (recast) (Text with EEA relevance): https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AJOL_2023_231_R_0001&qid=1695186598766

⁶ European database on data centres: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy-climate-plans-reporting/ePlatform/reportENER/screen/home>

data centres too (e.g. CNRS from France as shown in the screenshot in Figure 2). This reporting requirement will gradually broaden to additional countries and data centres too, and will penetrate more deeply into the academic data centre community (at least to the large centres). Therefore, studying the metrics that the EED demands can serve as a good baseline for SotA metrics.

The EED reporting obligations encompass a total of 24 performance indicators, which can be categorized into three main areas:

1. AREA: Energy and sustainability indicators:

1. Installed information technology power demand (PDIT, kW)
2. Data centre total floor area (SDC, m²)
3. Data centre computer room floor area (SCR, m²)
4. Total energy consumption (EDC, kWh)
5. Total energy consumption of IT equipment (EIT, kWh)
6. Electrical grid functions
7. Average battery capacity ('CBtG', in kW)
8. Total water input ('WIN', in cubic metres)
9. Total potable water input ('WIN-POT', in cubic metres)
10. Waste heat reused ('EREUSE', in kWh)
11. Average waste heat temperature ('TWH', in degree Celsius)
12. Average setpoint information technology equipment intake air temperature ('TIN', in degree Celsius)
13. Types of refrigerants used in the cooling and air conditioning equipment
14. Cooling degree days ('CDD', in degree-days)
15. Total renewable energy consumption ('ERES-TOT', in kWh)
16. Total renewable energy consumption from Guarantees of Origin ('ERES-GOO', in kWh)
17. Total renewable energy consumption from Power Purchasing Agreements ('ERES-PPA', in kWh)
18. Total renewable energy consumption from on-site renewables ('ERES-OS', in kWh)

2. AREA: ICT capacity indicators

1. ICT capacity for servers ('CSERV')
2. ICT capacity for storage equipment ('CSTOR', in petabytes)

3. AREA: Data traffic indicators

1. Incoming traffic bandwidth ('BIN', in gigabytes per second)

2. Outgoing traffic bandwidth ('BOU', in gigabytes per second)
3. Incoming data traffic ('TIN', in exabytes)
4. Outgoing data traffic ('TOU', in exabytes)

Notice that while the regulation emphasizes energy-related metrics, it does not explicitly mandate the reporting of total CO₂ emissions. However, by reporting energy consumption and the proportion of renewable energy used, data centres provide data that can be used to estimate their carbon footprint. Therefore, while direct reporting of total CO₂ emissions is not explicitly required, the reported energy metrics contribute to assessing the environmental impact of data centre operations. Annex III of EED specifies calculation methodologies for the following **sustainability indicators** that shall be calculated based on the information and key performance indicators communicated to the European database on data centres:

- Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE)
- Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE)
- Energy Reuse Factor (ERF)
- Renewable Energy Factor (REF)

3.1.1 Detailed Analysis of Directive (EU) 2024/1364

Directive (EU) 2024/1364 establishes the first phase of a common European framework for assessing and reporting the sustainability of data centres. Adopted under the revised Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2023/1791, this regulation represents a significant step towards improving transparency, comparability, and accountability of data centre environmental performance across the European Union. It reflects the growing importance of the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector, whose energy consumption is projected to increase substantially, and addresses the need for harmonised monitoring and reporting mechanisms to support the transition towards more sustainable digital infrastructures.

The scope of the regulation is clearly defined and targets data centres with an installed IT power demand of at least 500 kW. By focusing on medium to large-scale infrastructures, the directive addresses facilities that contribute significantly to overall energy consumption and environmental impact. The regulation applies to different operational models, including enterprise, colocation, and co-hosting data centres, thereby ensuring broad applicability across the sector. Importantly, each data centre is considered an individual reporting entity, even when located within a larger campus or operated as part of a distributed infrastructure. This approach ensures that data is reported at a sufficiently granular level to enable meaningful comparisons and analysis across facilities and Member States.

A central component of the directive is the introduction of a mandatory reporting framework that requires data centre operators to provide detailed information on an annual basis. The regulation establishes specific reporting deadlines, beginning with an initial submission followed by yearly updates, and requires that reported data correspond to the previous calendar year. Operators may submit this information through national reporting schemes where available or directly to a centralised European database. The reporting obligations are comprehensive and include a standardised set of

information and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) designed to capture the operational and environmental characteristics of data centres. These KPIs encompass total energy consumption, energy consumption of IT equipment, installed IT power demand, cooling infrastructure characteristics, water usage, renewable energy consumption, waste heat reuse, and temperature-related parameters. The directive further mandates that these indicators be measured using harmonised methodologies, such as those defined in the EN 50600 standards, thereby ensuring consistency and comparability of data across different reporting entities.

The establishment of a European database for data centres is a key innovation introduced by the regulation. This database serves as a central platform for collecting, managing, and analysing the reported data, and provides a common interface and application programming interface (API) to facilitate data submission. While the directive ensures the confidentiality of commercially sensitive information at the level of individual data centres, it also promotes transparency by making aggregated data publicly available at both Member State and Union levels. This aggregated information includes indicators such as average Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE), Energy Reuse Factor (ERF), and Renewable Energy Factor (REF). By enabling benchmarking and comparative analysis, the database supports evidence-based policymaking and encourages improvements in data centre sustainability performance across the EU.

In addition to defining reporting obligations, the directive introduces a structured framework for sustainability assessment based on a set of core indicators. These include PUE, which measures overall energy efficiency; WUE, which evaluates water consumption efficiency; ERF, which captures the extent of waste heat reuse; and REF, which quantifies the share of renewable energy in total energy consumption. Together, these indicators represent a shift away from reliance on a single metric towards a more comprehensive, multi-dimensional evaluation of sustainability. This approach reflects the increasing recognition that energy efficiency alone is insufficient to fully characterise the environmental impact of data centres, and that factors such as water usage, circular energy flows, and renewable energy integration must also be considered.

The directive also places strong emphasis on monitoring and measurement requirements, specifying how data should be collected and ensuring methodological rigor. Operators are required to define clear measurement points within the data centre infrastructure, including the separation of IT and non-IT energy consumption and the measurement of total energy consumption at the system boundary. The regulation requires the use of recognised standards, such as the CEN/CENELEC EN 50600 series, and mandates that measurement data be retained for extended periods to support verification and longitudinal analysis. Furthermore, it introduces advanced monitoring requirements, including the measurement of waste heat reuse at the data centre boundary, the tracking of cooling system parameters such as intake temperatures, and the accounting of water inputs and renewable energy sources. These provisions ensure that the reported data are robust, comparable, and suitable for future development of benchmarking and rating schemes.

From a policy perspective, Directive (EU) 2024/1364 is closely aligned with broader European strategies, including the European Green Deal and the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030. It responds to the increasing energy demand of data centres, which is expected to represent a growing share of total electricity consumption within the Union, and supports the objective of achieving climate-neutral and highly energy-efficient digital infrastructures. By establishing a common framework for sustainability reporting, the directive lays the groundwork for future regulatory developments, including potential performance benchmarks and mandatory efficiency requirements.

Despite its comprehensive scope, the directive presents certain limitations that should be acknowledged. In particular, it does not explicitly address Scope 3 emissions, which are critical for a full lifecycle assessment of data centre environmental impact. Similarly, the embodied carbon associated with the manufacturing and disposal of IT equipment is not directly considered within the current framework. The regulation also allows for temporary flexibility in reporting during initial implementation phases, which may result in incomplete datasets in the short term. Furthermore, while the directive defines a set of sustainability indicators, it does not yet establish binding performance thresholds or enforcement mechanisms. Finally, the current framework focuses primarily on infrastructure-level metrics and does not explicitly address workload-level efficiency or application-driven optimisation, which are increasingly relevant in the context of AI and high-performance computing.

3.1.2 Reporting Methodology and Calculation Framework

Directive (EU) 2024/1364 establishes a comprehensive and harmonised reporting methodology for assessing the sustainability performance of data centres across the European Union. The framework is designed to ensure consistency, comparability, and reliability of reported data by defining a structured set of information requirements, measurement methodologies, and derived indicators. The reporting methodology is organised around four main components, as defined in Annexes I to IV of the regulation, which together form a complete data collection, processing, and evaluation pipeline.

At its core, the methodology follows a layered approach in which raw operational data are first collected, then transformed into Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and finally aggregated into higher-level sustainability indicators. This structure ensures that sustainability assessment is based on measurable and standardised inputs while enabling consistent benchmarking across heterogeneous data centre infrastructures.

The reporting workflow defined by the directive can be summarised as a three-stage process:

1. Collection of descriptive and operational data (Annex I)
2. Measurement and reporting of Key Performance Indicators (Annex II)
3. Calculation of sustainability indicators (Annex III)

These data are then submitted to a centralised European database and made publicly available in aggregated form (Annex IV). The regulation mandates that reporting be performed annually, with data covering the previous calendar year, and requires that all measurements follow recognised standards such as the CEN/CENELEC EN 50600 series.

A more detailed description of the reporting methodology and KPIs defined in Directive (EU) 2024/1364 are provided in **Appendix 12.1**.

3.1.3 Gap Analysis Between EED and Research Infrastructures

While Directive (EU) 2024/1364 establishes a comprehensive and harmonised framework for reporting data centre sustainability, its applicability to Research Infrastructures (RIs) reveals several gaps and limitations. These arise primarily from differences in operational models, workload characteristics, and technological heterogeneity between traditional commercial data centres and research-oriented computing environments.

A first significant gap concerns the scope and classification of infrastructures. The directive is designed around conventional data centre categories, namely enterprise, colocation, and co-hosting facilities. However, many Research Infrastructures operate hybrid environments that combine elements of High-Performance Computing (HPC), High-Throughput Computing (HTC), cloud services, and increasingly AI-specific platforms. These environments often span multiple administrative domains and geographic locations, forming federated infrastructures rather than single, clearly bounded facilities. As a result, the directive's assumption of a well-defined "data centre" as a reporting unit does not always align with the distributed and virtualised nature of RIs.

A second limitation relates to the 500 kW reporting threshold, which determines the applicability of the regulation. While large HPC centres clearly fall within this range, many smaller or distributed RI nodes may fall below the threshold individually, despite collectively representing substantial computational capacity and energy consumption. This creates a fragmentation effect in which parts of a federated research infrastructure may be excluded from reporting, leading to incomplete visibility of the overall environmental impact. Consequently, the directive may underestimate the cumulative footprint of research infrastructures that are composed of multiple smaller sites.

Another important gap concerns the focus on facility-level metrics, which are central to the directive's reporting methodology. Indicators such as total energy consumption, PUE, WUE, and cooling parameters provide valuable insights into infrastructure efficiency but do not capture the efficiency of computational workloads themselves. In Research Infrastructures, energy consumption is strongly influenced by workload characteristics, including job scheduling, data movement, and algorithmic efficiency. For example, HPC and AI workloads can exhibit highly variable resource utilisation patterns, and inefficient scheduling or over-provisioning can significantly increase energy consumption without being reflected in facility-level metrics. The absence of workload-level or application-level indicators therefore limits the ability of the directive to fully assess the efficiency of research computing environments.

Closely related to this is the lack of support for dynamic and time-dependent optimisation, which is increasingly relevant in research infrastructures. Many RIs are exploring carbon-aware scheduling strategies that shift workloads in time or location based on the availability of low-carbon energy. While the directive includes indicators related to renewable energy consumption and grid interaction, it does not explicitly account for temporal variations in carbon intensity or for the optimisation strategies used to exploit them. As a result, innovative approaches to reducing environmental impact through intelligent workload management are not directly captured within the current framework.

The directive also presents limitations in its treatment of accelerators and heterogeneous computing architectures, which are central to modern research infrastructures. HPC and AI systems increasingly rely on GPUs and other accelerators that have significantly different power profiles compared to traditional CPUs. These components can dominate energy consumption, particularly in AI training workloads, yet the directive does not provide specific guidance on how to measure or report their utilisation and efficiency. Metrics such as total IT energy consumption aggregate all components, potentially obscuring important differences in efficiency between CPU-based and accelerator-based workloads.

Another area where gaps are evident is the treatment of federated and multi-tenant environments, which are common in Research Infrastructures such as EOSC or EGI. In these environments, resources are shared across multiple user communities and projects, and energy consumption must be attributed to individual workloads or users. The directive focuses on data centre-level reporting and does not

define mechanisms for allocating energy consumption to specific users or experiments. This limits its usefulness for research contexts where accountability and optimisation often need to be performed at finer levels of granularity.

From an environmental perspective, the directive primarily addresses operational energy consumption (Scope 2 emissions) and provides only limited consideration of broader lifecycle impacts. In Research Infrastructures, the procurement, upgrade, and disposal of specialised hardware, such as HPC systems and storage platforms, contribute significantly to the overall environmental footprint. The lack of explicit consideration of embodied carbon (Scope 3 emissions) therefore represents a notable limitation, particularly given the relatively short refresh cycles of high-performance computing equipment.

Furthermore, the directive assumes the availability of advanced monitoring and measurement capabilities, which may not yet be fully implemented across all research infrastructures. While large data centres often deploy sophisticated Data Centre Infrastructure Management (DCIM) systems, many RIs operate heterogeneous environments with varying levels of instrumentation. The requirement to measure detailed KPIs, such as waste heat reuse or ICT capacity, may therefore pose practical challenges, particularly for legacy systems or distributed infrastructures where monitoring is not standardised.

Finally, the directive's framework is primarily oriented towards static reporting and benchmarking, rather than real-time optimisation and control. Research infrastructures, on the other hand, increasingly require real-time monitoring and feedback mechanisms to support adaptive scheduling, dynamic resource allocation, and energy-aware decision-making. The absence of explicit support for real-time data integration and control loops limits the direct applicability of the directive to advanced optimisation scenarios.

In summary, while Directive (EU) 2024/1364 provides a strong foundation for standardised sustainability reporting, its current scope and methodology do not fully capture the complexity of Research Infrastructures. Key gaps include the lack of support for federated and distributed environments, insufficient consideration of workload-level efficiency, limited treatment of accelerators and heterogeneous architectures, and the absence of lifecycle and real-time optimisation perspectives. Addressing these gaps will be essential for aligning regulatory frameworks with the evolving technological landscape of scientific computing and for enabling more comprehensive sustainability assessment in research contexts.

3.2 Monitoring Architectures for Sustainable Digital Infrastructures

Monitoring architectures play a fundamental role in enabling sustainable digital infrastructures by providing comprehensive visibility into energy consumption, resource utilisation, and system performance across all layers of the computing stack. It presents a unified monitoring architecture model that integrates facility-level measurements with system- and application-level telemetry, enabling consistent sustainability assessment, optimisation, and reporting across heterogeneous environments.

A unified monitoring architecture must address several key requirements:

1. End-to-end, multi-layer visibility across the infrastructure.

The architecture must enable continuous monitoring from physical facilities and power systems to nodes, virtualised environments, containers, and application workloads. This requirement is essential because system efficiency and sustainability emerge from interactions across these layers. Recent research on observability for scientific computing highlights that traditional monitoring approaches fail to capture cross-layer dependencies, and proposes end-to-end observability frameworks capable of integrating telemetry from infrastructure and application levels into a unified model [1]. Similarly, modern monitoring stacks such as CEEMS demonstrate the need to combine facility-level energy measurements with workload-level metrics to accurately capture energy consumption in HPC and cloud environments [2].

2. Support for both operational observability and sustainability accounting.

Monitoring systems must simultaneously enable real-time system understanding (observability) and long-term, auditable reporting (accounting). Observability requires high-resolution telemetry and advanced analytics to diagnose system behaviour, while accounting focuses on consistent attribution of energy and resource usage to users, services, or workloads. Recent work on observability architectures for next-generation computing systems emphasises decoupling telemetry collection from workload execution, allowing persistent monitoring and retrospective analysis without affecting system performance [3]. In parallel, energy-aware monitoring frameworks in HPC and AI infrastructures underline the importance of workload-level energy accounting for sustainability reporting and optimisation [4].

3. Scalability and interoperability in distributed and federated infrastructures.

Monitoring architectures must be capable of operating across large-scale, heterogeneous, and federated environments, integrating data from multiple systems with different technologies and administrative domains. This requires modular, extensible designs and standardised data models to ensure interoperability. Recent studies on large-scale observability platforms highlight the need for scalable data collection and processing pipelines capable of handling diverse telemetry sources, including metrics, logs, and traces, while supporting integration across clusters and facilities [5]. Furthermore, research on energy-efficient data centres and AI infrastructures stresses that future monitoring systems must support cross-domain integration to enable coordinated optimisation of infrastructure, workloads, and energy systems [6].

3.2.1 Multi-layer Monitoring

The foundation of a unified monitoring architecture for sustainable digital infrastructures is a multi-layer monitoring model that reflects the hierarchical and heterogeneous nature of modern computing systems. Digital infrastructures, particularly in research environments, are composed of tightly coupled layers ranging from physical facilities to application-level workloads. As a result, monitoring must be designed to capture telemetry across all these layers, typically structured as: facility → node → virtualisation → container → job or application, as can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Multi-layer monitoring architecture from facility to application level.

At the lowest level, facility monitoring captures metrics related to power consumption, cooling systems, and environmental conditions. These measurements are typically obtained through power distribution units, cooling infrastructure, and environmental sensors, and correspond to the infrastructure-level indicators required by regulatory frameworks such as Directive (EU) 2024/1364. While essential for assessing overall energy efficiency, facility-level metrics alone are insufficient to explain how energy is consumed by specific workloads or services.

At the node level, monitoring focuses on individual compute resources, including CPUs, GPUs, memory, and network interfaces. Hardware performance counters and embedded telemetry interfaces provide fine-grained insights into resource utilisation and energy consumption. In modern HPC and AI systems, this layer is particularly important due to the increasing dominance of accelerators, whose power consumption profiles differ significantly from traditional CPU-based architectures.

Higher layers introduce abstraction through virtualisation and containerisation technologies. Monitoring at the virtual machine and container levels enables the attribution of resource usage to specific execution environments, supporting multi-tenancy and workload isolation. This is especially relevant in cloud-native and hybrid HPC environments, where container orchestration platforms such as Kubernetes are increasingly used to manage workloads.

At the highest level, job or application monitoring captures workload behaviour, including execution time, resource consumption, and data movement. This layer is critical for understanding the relationship between application design, scheduling strategies, and energy efficiency. In research infrastructures, where workloads can vary significantly in complexity and resource requirements, application-level monitoring provides the necessary context to interpret lower-level metrics and identify optimisation opportunities.

The key advantage of a multi-layer monitoring approach lies in its ability to correlate data across layers. For example, high facility-level energy consumption can be traced back to inefficient workload scheduling, low hardware utilisation, or suboptimal application behaviour. Such cross-layer analysis enables root-cause identification and supports advanced optimisation strategies, including energy-aware scheduling and resource allocation.

Recent research emphasises that effective sustainability monitoring requires the integration of telemetry across all system layers into a unified observability framework. Studies on HPC and cloud

observability highlight that isolated monitoring solutions are insufficient for capturing system-wide behaviour and advocate for architectures that combine facility, system, and application-level data into a single analytical model [1]. Similarly, emerging energy-aware monitoring platforms demonstrate that combining infrastructure-level measurements with workload-level metrics is essential for accurate energy attribution and optimisation in large-scale computing environments [7].

In this context, multi-layer monitoring is not only a technical requirement but a fundamental design principle for sustainable digital infrastructures. It enables a shift from isolated metric collection to integrated system understanding, providing the foundation for both real-time optimisation and long-term sustainability assessment.

3.2.2 Hardware-based vs Software-based Telemetry

Telemetry constitutes the foundational layer of any monitoring architecture, enabling the collection of quantitative data describing system behaviour, resource utilisation, and energy consumption. In the context of sustainable digital infrastructures, telemetry can be broadly categorised into hardware-based and software-based approaches, each providing complementary perspectives on system operation, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Layered view of hardware- and software-based telemetry in a unified monitoring system.

Hardware-based telemetry relies on measurements obtained directly from physical components and embedded sensors within the infrastructure. These include power meters at the facility level, as well as on-chip sensors and performance counters integrated into CPUs, GPUs, and memory subsystems. Technologies such as Intel Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) and vendor-specific interfaces like NVIDIA Management Library (NVML) provide fine-grained insights into energy consumption and thermal behaviour at the component level. Hardware telemetry is generally characterised by high accuracy and low measurement overhead, making it particularly suitable for energy accounting and sustainability reporting. It also aligns closely with the requirements of regulatory frameworks such as

Directive (EU) 2024/1364, which rely on precise measurements of energy consumption and environmental parameters.

However, hardware-based telemetry alone is insufficient to fully characterise system behaviour, as it does not provide contextual information about how resources are used by specific workloads. This limitation is addressed by software-based telemetry, which captures metrics at the level of operating systems, virtualisation layers, containers, and applications. Such metrics include CPU utilisation, memory usage, I/O activity, and application-level performance indicators, enabling attribution of resource consumption to individual processes, users, or jobs.

While software telemetry provides essential context, it may introduce overhead and is generally less accurate in estimating physical quantities such as energy consumption, especially when based on indirect models.

The integration of hardware-based and software-based telemetry in monitoring architectures is supported by recent research:

Hardware vs software measurement comparison: Studies show that hardware-based measurements (e.g., power meters, RAPL, NVML) provide high accuracy, while software-based approaches enable workload-level attribution, despite introducing estimation errors [8].

Cloud and container monitoring architectures: Surveys of energy monitoring in cloud-native environments highlight the need for hybrid telemetry pipelines combining physical measurements with software metrics, particularly in Kubernetes-based infrastructures [9].

Container-level energy observability frameworks: Recent systems such as Kepler and KubeWatt integrate hardware counters with Kubernetes APIs and exporters to provide energy visibility at the container and application level [10].

Unified observability frameworks: Modern observability approaches emphasise the integration of telemetry across hardware and software layers into unified pipelines, enabling end-to-end monitoring and optimisation in complex infrastructures [1].

3.2.3 DCIM Integration

Data Centre Infrastructure Management (DCIM) systems constitute a key component of monitoring architectures for sustainable digital infrastructures, as they provide detailed visibility into facility-level operations, including power distribution, cooling systems, and environmental conditions. These systems collect data from physical infrastructure components such as power distribution units (PDUs), uninterruptible power supplies (UPS), cooling equipment, and environmental sensors, forming the basis for infrastructure-level metrics such as total energy consumption, temperature, and cooling efficiency.

Within a unified monitoring architecture, DCIM systems represent the primary source of **hardware-based telemetry at the facility level**. However, traditional DCIM platforms are typically designed as standalone systems focused on infrastructure management and lack integration with IT-level monitoring and workload-level telemetry. This separation limits their ability to support advanced sustainability use cases, such as attributing energy consumption to specific applications or optimising resource allocation based on energy efficiency.

To address these limitations, recent approaches emphasise the integration of DCIM data into broader observability frameworks. By combining facility-level measurements with node-level and application-level telemetry, it becomes possible to correlate energy consumption with workload behaviour and system utilisation. This integration enables more accurate energy accounting and supports optimisation strategies such as energy-aware scheduling and dynamic workload placement. In particular, studies on energy-efficient data centre management highlight that combining DCIM data with IT monitoring systems is essential for achieving end-to-end visibility and improving overall energy efficiency [11].

Modern architectures increasingly adopt **data pipelines and common data models** to integrate DCIM systems with software-based monitoring platforms. This involves collecting data from DCIM interfaces (e.g., SNMP, Modbus, Redfish APIs) and normalising it alongside system and application metrics within a unified telemetry framework. Such integration is also aligned with emerging regulatory requirements, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, which require consistent reporting of facility-level and IT-level metrics.

Despite these advances, several challenges remain. DCIM systems often rely on vendor-specific interfaces and proprietary data formats, which complicates interoperability with other monitoring components. Furthermore, differences in sampling rates and measurement granularity between facility-level and IT-level data require careful synchronisation and aggregation. Addressing these challenges requires the adoption of open standards and modular architectures that enable seamless integration across heterogeneous systems.

Overall, DCIM integration represents a critical step towards achieving unified monitoring architectures, bridging the gap between physical infrastructure and digital workloads, and enabling comprehensive sustainability assessment and optimisation.

3.2.4 Observability vs Accounting

Within a unified monitoring architecture, it is essential to distinguish between observability and accounting, as these represent two complementary but fundamentally different functions. Both rely on telemetry data collected across the infrastructure, but they serve distinct objectives and impose different requirements on monitoring systems.

Observability refers to the capability to understand and analyse the internal state and behaviour of a system based on the data it produces. It extends traditional monitoring by enabling not only the detection of known issues but also the investigation of unexpected behaviours through the correlation of metrics, logs, and traces. In the context of digital infrastructures, observability supports real-time analysis of system performance, anomaly detection, and optimisation of resource utilisation. It requires high-resolution, near real-time data collection and advanced analytics capabilities to provide insights into complex, dynamic environments. Modern observability frameworks, such as those based on OpenTelemetry⁷, emphasise standardised telemetry collection and the integration of metrics, logs, and traces into unified pipelines, enabling end-to-end visibility across distributed systems.

In contrast, accounting focuses on the systematic measurement and attribution of resource usage and energy consumption over time. Its primary purpose is to support reporting, auditing, billing, and policy

⁷ OpenTelemetry: Observability Framework for Cloud-Native Software (<https://opentelemetry.io/>)

enforcement. In research infrastructures and multi-tenant environments, accounting is essential for attributing resource consumption to individual users, projects, or workloads. Unlike observability, accounting prioritises consistency, reproducibility, and auditability over high temporal resolution, and typically relies on aggregated data collected over longer time intervals.

The distinction between observability and accounting is particularly important in the context of sustainability. Observability enables dynamic optimisation strategies, such as energy-aware scheduling and real-time workload adaptation, by providing immediate insights into system behaviour. Accounting, on the other hand, provides the basis for sustainability reporting and compliance with regulatory frameworks, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, which requires consistent and standardised reporting of energy and environmental metrics. Recent studies on energy-aware computing systems highlight that combining real-time observability with workload-level accounting is essential for achieving both operational efficiency and accurate sustainability assessment [1].

Modern monitoring architectures increasingly aim to integrate both functions within a unified framework. This is achieved by designing telemetry pipelines that support both high-resolution data streams for observability and aggregated, structured datasets for accounting. Such integration ensures that the same underlying data can be reused for multiple purposes, reducing duplication and improving consistency between operational insights and reported metrics.

3.2.5 Real-time vs Aggregated Reporting

Monitoring architectures for sustainable digital infrastructures must balance the requirements of real-time data processing with those of aggregated reporting. These two approaches serve complementary purposes and are both essential within a unified monitoring framework.

Real-time monitoring focuses on the continuous collection and analysis of high-resolution telemetry data, enabling immediate visibility into system behaviour. It supports operational use cases such as anomaly detection, performance debugging, and dynamic optimisation of resource utilisation. In the context of sustainability, real-time monitoring enables energy-aware strategies, including adaptive workload scheduling, demand-response mechanisms, and optimisation based on current system conditions or energy availability. Achieving real-time capabilities requires low-latency data pipelines, streaming analytics, and scalable telemetry collection mechanisms capable of handling large volumes of data.

However, real-time monitoring introduces significant challenges. High-frequency data collection generates large data volumes, leading to increased storage, processing, and network overhead. Moreover, the complexity of analysing real-time data across multiple layers of the infrastructure requires advanced correlation and analytics techniques. As a result, real-time monitoring systems must be carefully designed to balance data granularity with system overhead.

In contrast, aggregated reporting focuses on summarising monitoring data over defined time intervals, such as minutes, hours, or days. This approach reduces data volume and provides a stable basis for long-term analysis, benchmarking, and regulatory reporting. Aggregated metrics are essential for sustainability assessment frameworks, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, which relies on standardised indicators derived from time-aggregated data. Aggregation also improves data comparability across infrastructures and supports auditing and reproducibility.

Modern monitoring architectures integrate both approaches through hierarchical data processing pipelines. High-resolution telemetry is collected and processed in real time for operational purposes, while aggregation mechanisms compute derived metrics and summaries for reporting and analysis. Techniques such as multi-resolution storage, down sampling, and time-series aggregation are commonly used to manage data volume while preserving essential information.

Recent research highlights that combining real-time and aggregated data processing is critical for achieving both operational efficiency and sustainability objectives. Studies on observability systems and HPC monitoring frameworks emphasise the need for scalable telemetry pipelines that support streaming analytics alongside long-term data retention and aggregation. Similarly, energy-aware monitoring approaches demonstrate that real-time insights must be complemented by aggregated indicators to enable both optimisation and compliance with reporting requirements.

Overall, the integration of real-time monitoring and aggregated reporting within a unified architecture enables a comprehensive approach to sustainability, supporting both immediate operational decision-making and long-term performance assessment.

3.2.6 Integration Challenges in Federated Infrastructures

The implementation of unified monitoring architectures becomes significantly more complex in federated infrastructures, where multiple independent systems must be integrated into a coherent monitoring framework. Such environments are typical of research infrastructures, distributed cloud systems, and cross-organisational platforms, where resources are geographically dispersed and managed by different administrative domains.

One of the primary challenges lies in the **heterogeneity of systems and technologies**. Federated infrastructures often combine diverse hardware platforms, software stacks, and monitoring tools, each producing data in different formats and using different measurement methodologies. This heterogeneity complicates the integration of telemetry data and limits the ability to perform consistent analysis across sites. Addressing this challenge requires the adoption of common data models, standardised interfaces, and interoperable protocols for data collection and exchange.

Another major challenge is the **integration and correlation of multi-layer telemetry across domains**. In a federated environment, monitoring data must be collected from facility-level systems, compute nodes, virtualisation layers, and application workloads across multiple sites. Correlating this data to obtain a unified view of system behaviour requires scalable aggregation mechanisms and synchronisation of data streams with different temporal resolutions. Without such integration, it is difficult to attribute energy consumption to specific workloads or identify optimisation opportunities across the federation.

Scalability represents an additional concern, as federated infrastructures may include thousands of nodes and generate large volumes of telemetry data. Monitoring architectures must therefore support distributed data collection and processing, often using hierarchical or decentralised approaches to avoid bottlenecks. Recent work on large-scale observability systems emphasises the need for scalable telemetry pipelines and distributed analytics to manage data efficiently in such environments.

Interoperability and standardisation are closely related challenges. Many monitoring systems rely on proprietary interfaces or vendor-specific solutions, which hinder integration across organisational boundaries. The adoption of open standards, such as Redfish for hardware management or

OpenTelemetry for telemetry collection, is increasingly recognised as a key enabler for interoperability in federated infrastructures.

In addition to technical challenges, **data governance, privacy, and security constraints** play a significant role. Monitoring data may include sensitive information about system usage, workloads, or organisational activities, and sharing such data across administrative domains may be restricted. This requires the implementation of access control mechanisms, data anonymisation techniques, and policies that balance transparency with confidentiality.

Finally, federated infrastructures must address challenges related to **data ownership and responsibility**. Different organisations may have different policies regarding data collection, storage, and usage, leading to inconsistencies in monitoring practices. Ensuring consistent and reliable monitoring across the federation requires coordination and agreement on common practices, as well as mechanisms for validating and verifying reported data.

Recent studies on federated cloud and HPC environments highlight that addressing these challenges requires flexible, modular, and standards-based monitoring architectures capable of operating across heterogeneous and distributed systems. In this context, unified monitoring frameworks must be designed not only for technical integration, but also for organisational interoperability, enabling collaboration while respecting the autonomy of participating entities.

Overall, the integration of monitoring systems in federated infrastructures remains a complex but essential task for achieving end-to-end visibility and sustainability assessment across modern digital ecosystems.

3.3 Metrics Infrastructures for Federated Environments

This section provides an overview of those existing software infrastructures that can be considered as baseline for the 'GreenDIGIT Environmental Metrics Infrastructure'.

3.3.1 EGI Accounting System for Metrics

The EGI Accounting Repository and Portal is a service designed to collect, store, aggregate, and display information about the consumption of resources for High Throughput Compute jobs, Virtual Machines, and online storage providers. The providers supporting these types of services can connect their different service endpoints to the Accounting Service, which is centrally managed and that will provide collected data about the service usage.

Probes and sensors that gather accounting information according to certain data formats are deployed locally at the service providers, and subsequently a network of message brokers is forwarding the data to a central Accounting Repository where the data are processed to generate various summaries and views for display in the Accounting Portal⁸.

Current metrics are '*Number of Virtual Machines*' (exemplified in Figure 5), '*Disk Used*', '*Memory Used*', '*Number of ProcessorHours*' (for Cloud), '*Number of Jobs*', '*CPU Efficiency*', '*Total CPU time used*', '*Number of ProcessorHours*' (HTC) and they can be displayed by Resource Centres and various time units (from '*Month*' to '*Year*'). A common format to report GPU use and utilization in infrastructure

⁸EGI Accounting Portal: <https://accounting.egi.eu/>

clouds has also been developed, and different components of the ecosystem are being extended to support it.

From the GreenDIGIT perspective, specific probes and sensors that are implemented within the project partner premises could gather relevant environmental impact related metrics and feed them in the metrics framework at the Accounting Portal level to be consumed via API by a broad category of readers (platforms, tools, brokers, web pages).

Features useful for the project and provided by the EGI Accounting framework are:

- scalable for O(100) providers
- scalable for O(10) consumers
- can store historical values for the stored metrics
- support for time-series queries
- available GUI and read-write API
- support for cumulative reporting of consumption of long-running workflows

Infrastructure Cloud Accounting The EGI Accounting Portal is an EGI service provided by CESGA
This work is co-funded by the EOSC-hub project (Horizon 2020) under Grant number 777536.

Metric: Metric Unit: Start Time: End Time:

Row Variable: Column Variable:

VO Filtering: LHC TOP 10 ALL EGI Official Custom VO Selection

Local Jobs: Infrastructure Jobs Only Infrastructure and Local Jobs Local Jobs Only

The Cloud Compute EGI view shows the accounting data from all Cloud Resource centres in the EGI infrastructure. Data can be organized by Operations Centre or country. Accounting information is only gathered from Resource Centres that are part of the EGI Federation and are certified in GOCD. The metric shown is Total number of VM run, grouped by Resource Centre and Month, the official EGI VOs are shown. No local jobs are shown

Cloud — Total number of VM run by Resource Centre and Month (Official VOs)

Resource Centre	Jul 2024	Aug 2024	Sep 2024	Oct 2024	Nov 2024	Dec 2024	Total
CEN	2,403	1	1,332	2,221	1,790	652	8,399
CESGA-CLOUD	1,367	659	1,011	2,272	1,883	2,099	9,291
CESNET-MCC	4,061	2,800	2,598	2,433	2,053	2,556	16,501
CESNET-MCCG2	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
CETA-GRID	3,379	2,922	2,049	382	1,204	497	10,433
CLOUDFIN	3,728	3,371	2,207	2,239	1,789	2,247	15,581
CSTCLOUD-EGI	2,313	2,612	2,302	2,360	2,035	2,308	13,930
ELKH-CLOUD	1,104	4	4	4	1,300	2,052	4,468
EDGC	4	4	4	4	4	4	24
GRNET-OPENSTACK	2,520	2,158	2,185	2,249	1,860	2,108	13,080
IFCA-LCG2	7,414	2,679	2,996	1,476	190	141	14,896
ISISAS-FedCloud	3,372	3,018	2,252	2,233	1,879	2,122	14,876
ILFU-UCT	0	0	906	1,524	1,847	2,110	6,387
IN2P3-IRES	16,558	27,180	22,489	4,172	673	500	71,572
INFN-CLOUD-BARI	2,842	1,964	1,637	1,293	1,198	1,771	10,705
INFN-CLOUD-CNAF	3,654	3,445	2,134	2,248	1,810	2,244	15,535
NGC-INGRID-PT	3,530	2,848	2,389	2,324	1,939	2,344	15,374
SCAI	1,905	2,889	2,001	691	1,580	2,013	11,079
TR-FC1-ULAKBIM	4,342	3,807	2,292	2,235	1,881	2,109	16,666
UA-BITP	1,343	251	1,952	114	221	700	4,581
WALTON-CLOUD	3,292	2,902	2,223	1,860	766	1,407	12,450
fedcloud_srcs.hr	3,013	0	0	0	0	0	3,013
Total	72,144	65,514	56,963	34,334	27,902	31,985	288,842

Figure 5. Total number of VMs run by each EGI Federation Cloud centre during H2 2024.

The framework is already being used by the GreenDIGIT partners that are also members of the EGI Federation and are contributing to the EGI infrastructure with HTC and Cloud resources.

The Grid Usage Record and Cloud Usage Record are very similar to each other, and easily extensible. The consumer is not sensitive to extra attributes added by producers, making it forward-compatible with producers publishing additional consumption attributes, e.g., power, utilization rate, or carbon cost.

3.3.2 EOSC Accounting System for Metrics

The EOSC Accounting Service is a platform designed to efficiently collect, aggregate and exchange metrics across various infrastructures, providers and projects, all part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) EU Node⁹.

The main functions of the platform are expressed by a REST API (see Figure 6).

- Accept input from several different resources
- Define and support metrics
- Database secure storage and intelligent aggregation of incoming data
- Make aggregated data available to various clients
- Search, filter, offer data for a specific time period.

Figure 6. Snapshot of EOSC Accounting system API structure.

In addition, API resources must only be obtainable by authenticated clients. For this reason, every client who wants access to API resources should be authenticated.

The platform also offers an intuitive User Interface¹⁰, see Figure 7, that allows clients to interact effortlessly with the Accounting Service. Users can access and manage accounting data for specific time periods through a user-friendly dashboard.

From the GreenDIGIT perspective, probes and sensors that are deployed at a project partner premises could gather the relevant environmental impact related metrics and feed them in the metrics framework at the EOSC Accounting Service level to be consumed via API by a broad category of readers (platforms, tools, brokers, web pages).

⁹EOSC EU Node: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

¹⁰EOSC Accounting service: <https://ui-acc.open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

The framework is used by the GreenDIGIT partners that are also contributing with services to the EOSC EU Node platform.

Figure 7. EOSC Accounting service UI.

3.3.3 Prometheus

Prometheus¹¹ is an open-source monitoring and alerting system designed for time-series data. It is widely used for observability in cloud-native environments, especially with Kubernetes. Prometheus is already used for local metrics collection purposes at some of the GreenDIGIT members, including CSIC and SZTAKI.

Key features of Prometheus are:

- Time-Series Database (TSDB) – Stores numerical data over time, indexed by labels
- Pull-Based Model – Prometheus scrapes metrics from instrumented services instead of waiting for them to push data
- PromQL (Prometheus Query Language) – Enables powerful queries and analysis of time-series data
- Multi-Dimensional Data Model – Uses labels (key-value pairs) to categorize and filter metrics
- Alerting & Visualization – Works with Alertmanager for notifications and integrates with Grafana for graphical dashboards
- Service Discovery – Dynamically detects targets using Kubernetes, Consul, or static configurations

The typical use cases where Prometheus is applied are:

- Infrastructure monitoring (CPU, memory, disk usage)
- Tracking application performance (API response times, request counts)
- Observability in microservices and Kubernetes clusters
- Generating alerts for anomalies (e.g., high error rates)

Some of the most common Prometheus metrics are:

- Counter – A cumulative metric (e.g., HTTP requests count)

¹¹Prometheus: <https://prometheus.io/>

- Gauge – A metric that can go up or down (e.g., memory usage)
- Histogram – Distributes values into buckets (e.g., response time)
- Summary – Similar to Histogram but includes quantiles

Points of convergence already exist between Prometheus as the consumer service and the accounting system in EGI. There is an exporter service,¹² which accepts Cloud Accounting Records in the format used by EGI, and exports them as metrics into Prometheus. It can be operated either at site-level (before the message queue) or at consumer side (after the record is delivered through the message queue).

3.4 Metrics Collection and Management of Cloud (OpenStack) and AI Environments

Since energy consumption is one of the main causes of the environmental impact of research infrastructures, it is necessary to measure and control its use in these facilities. Beyond Virtual Machines, in a cloud computing environment, there is a large number of different hardware equipment that needs to be monitored. In addition, to optimize their use, it is necessary to measure them at different levels of abstraction, from the technical room to the virtual machine deployed in the cloud.

3.4.1 Metric Collection at Site Level

At this level of detail, which monitors the energy consumption of the entire infrastructure as a whole, it is necessary to instrument the electrical panels with power meters, and then monitor these sensors.

3.4.2 Metric Collection at Node Level

Servers are the most energy-consuming hardware equipment. Broadly speaking, these have a set of sensors on the motherboard, which are managed by the Baseboard Management Controller (BMC), and can be queried through the Intelligent Platform Management Interface (IPMI). It should be noted that although the communication protocols are standard, the implementation of the BMC and the available sensors vary with the vendor and device model, based on the tests we have performed on a wide variety of hardware and in different data centers. Through this source, we can obtain the power consumption of the entire server, and in most cases broken down by power supply (PSU), fans, CPU, and memory.

Using this approach, it is possible to obtain the total energy consumption per server, but in order to use this consumption to get a realistic carbon footprint, we need to correct this value with some correction factor, since for that server to work, more systems are needed, such as cooling, which also consumes a significant percentage of energy. To correct this measure, we can use a very well-known metric such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE)¹³, since it relates the total consumption of the data center with what is consumed by the IT equipment, which we can consider practically the sum of the power consumption of the compute servers.

¹²<https://github.com/goat-project/exporter>

¹³ https://datacenters.lbl.gov/sites/default/files/isc13_tuepaper.pdf

Another common way to measure power consumption, used by most existing software tools for this purpose, is to use RAPL (Running Average Power Limit)¹⁴. This is a feature of Intel/AMD's x86 CPUs, manufactured after 2012, which allows setting limits on the power used by the CPU and other nearby components. Also allows, as feedback, to report the cumulative power consumption of various system-on-chip (SoC) power domains. According to existing documentation, there are the following domains: Core/PP0, which encompasses the power consumed by the aggregate of CPU cores. Uncore/PP1: power consumed by components close to the CPU cores, which in most cases refers to the integrated GPU chipset. DRAM: power consumed by the memories. Package/PKG: includes "Core" and "Uncore". In some documentation and some of our experiments, it seems to include "DRAM", but this does not seem to be true in all cases. Finally, the specification also establishes a last domain, PSys, which measures the power consumption of the whole SoC, but in our tests, we have not found any CPU model that supports this domain, nor does the documentation detail what other components are taken into account, other than those already mentioned above in other domains. The RAPL power data is exposed to the operating system through the model-specific registers (MSR), read, in a Linux environment, through the power cap sensor, available in a kernel module.

Due to security issues (CVE-2020-8694, CVE-2020-8695 / INTEL-SA-00389) it is not always possible in some cases to read these registers, or the values are not entirely accurate. The vulnerability exploits what are known as power-side channel attacks, which exploit the unprivileged access to RAPL Interface [12]. An attack called Platypus [13] can recover cryptographic keys from Intel SGX (Software Guard Extension) and the Linux Kernel, inferring such data from the CPU power consumption when computing them. To protect against such attacks there are several fixes, both software and hardware. First, the Linux kernel was updated as of v5.10 to make the registers accessible only to privileged users, but this update does not protect against a privileged attacker. Therefore, CPU manufacturers also acted: On the one hand, Intel released directly a microcode update¹⁵, so that when SGX is enabled, the measurement read from the CPU voltage regulators is filtered before being written to the registers. On the other hand, AMD disabled support for the power cap sensor in the Linux kernel, and after some patches by Google to the power cap sensor¹⁶, the registers became available again for the 17h family of AMD processors as of kernel version 5.8, and as of version 5.11 for the 19h family¹⁷.

Finally, it should be considered that this last measurement method does not include all the equipment of the machine, and consequently, other hardware that is highly demanding in terms of power consumption, such as external GPUs, will not be taken into account. Therefore, when calculating the carbon footprint of a machine using this approach, it will be necessary to adjust the measurement value obtained by a corrective factor, to obtain a realistic power consumption and get a real carbon footprint at the end. This correction factor can be the ratio between the energy consumed by the server and the energy consumed by the CPU, or as defined by Patterson: ITUE [14], IT Usage Effectiveness, or at data center level, the energy consumed by the data center divided by the energy consumed by the CPU, defined by Patterson as: TUE, Total Usage Effectiveness.

¹⁴ <https://hubblo-org.github.io/scaphandre-documentation/explanations/rapl-domains.html>

¹⁵ <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/developer/articles/technical/software-security-guidance/advisory-guidance/running-average-power-limit-energy-reporting.html>

¹⁶ <https://www.phoronix.com/news/Google-Zen-RAPL-PowerCap>

¹⁷ <https://www.phoronix.com/news/AMD-RAPL-Linux-Now-19h>

3.4.3 Metric Collection at Virtual Machine (VM) Level

Finally, at this level of detail, we focus on the energy consumption of the main asset used by users and the platforms deployed on them in a cloud computing environment: virtual machines. This level of technicality is more complex than the one described above since it is a virtual resource, which runs on a physical resource but is shared due to virtualization. Furthermore, there is no single alternative since we are introducing a new element into the system stack, such as hypervisors. The two major open-source virtualization platforms, KVM/QEMU and Xen Project take different approaches to address this problem. Starting with the latter, the Xen middleware exposes RAPL model-specific registers directly to the dom0 (host), and then this is replicated to all domUs (virtual machines), but based on our tests, it does not proportionally adjust the value based on the usage a virtual machine makes of the hardware. This also leads to a security and isolation problem. Some publications like “Enabling power-awareness for the Xen hypervisor” [15] propose adding power-awareness capabilities to the Xen dom0 to share the energy consumption of each machine proportionally to the hardware usage. On the other hand, when virtualizing with KVM/QEMU, the virtual machine does not have access to the RAPL registers, since this virtual machine is just another process in the set of processes of the host operating system. For this purpose, there are already tools that allow the energy consumption per process to be calculated from the host machine. These types of tools are based on the fact that a multitasking CPU does timesharing, being able to execute only one process in each jiffy. Therefore, we can measure CPU consumption only when the process is running, counting the jiffies that said process uses. A tool that is based on this methodology is Scaphandre¹⁸, an open-source metrology agent dedicated to electric power and energy consumption metrics created by Hubblo, which has to be deployed on every host machine. In addition, it has been specifically designed to monitor the power consumption of virtual machines and containers running on a host machine, since it is capable of sharing said measurements with the virtual machine or container itself¹⁹, through a hypervisor-shared file system in memory (virtiofs²⁰), and this measurement can be read by a Scaphandre agent deployed inside the VM as if it were a physical machine. Virtiofs is a shared file system purposed for virtualization, it is specifically designed to take advantage of the locality of virtual machines and the hypervisor, using memory-shared pages.

With Scaphandre, obtaining the power consumption of a virtual machine is easy, but sharing that measurement across a variable multi-tenant computing environment (i.e., a cloud infrastructure operated by OpenStack) is non-trivial. First, since virtiofs is included in libvirt v6.2.0, it requires that all operating systems on both host machines and VMs be upgraded to at least version 21.04 (Hirsute Hippo) in the case of Ubuntu. Also, libvirt v6.2.0 requires at least version 22.0.0 of OpenStack Nova. On the management side, libvirt v6.2.0 requires at least OpenStack Nova version 22.0.0²¹. Second, there is a lack of automation support in OpenStack to provide a feature in OpenStack Nova to manage virtiofs mounts, between VM and host. To create the shared filesystem, it is necessary to modify the XML definition of the KVM/QEMU VM. Nova fully manages this file, and only Nova can change it. There are some nova-specs proposing changes to support this feature²².

¹⁸ <https://hubblo-org.github.io/scaphandre-documentation/>

¹⁹ <https://hubblo-org.github.io/scaphandre-documentation/explanations/how-scaph-computes-per-process-power-consumption.html>

²⁰ <https://libvirt.org/kbase/virtiofs.html>

²¹ <https://docs.openstack.org/nova/latest/reference/libvirt-distro-support-matrix.html>

²² <https://specs.openstack.org/openstack/nova-specs/specs/2023.1/approved/virtiofs-scaphandre.html>

As previously mentioned, and since Scaphandre in its 1.0.0 version only obtains measurements from RAPL registers²³, the virtual machine's energy consumption does not include consumption from other specific hardware such as network cards or GPUs. Therefore, it is also necessary to apply a correction factor, the same as explained above for servers using RAPL as a measurement source, to obtain a real carbon footprint.

Finally, it is also possible to obtain the energy consumption and utilization of an NVIDIA GPU, since these measurements are available in the card driver, and can be read with CLI tools such as `nvidia-smi` or through an API using one of the management services oriented to datacenters such as NVIDIA DCGM²⁴

3.5 Metrics Collection and Management of High Throughput Compute Environments

Environmental sustainability is a strategic area of priority for many research infrastructures that provide High Throughput Compute (HTC) environments and for their funding agencies. WLCG²⁵ is one such international collaboration that is driving several activities aiming to estimate the energy consumption needed by the computing resources used by the LHC²⁶ experiments and also to help partners reduce the carbon footprint of their computing needs. Several GreenDIGIT partners are also WLCG participants, therefore involved in the above mentioned activities (e.g. CNRS, CSIC, CESNET).

The survey on RIs landscape review run by GreenDIGIT in 2024 highlighted that the energy has been considered by the respondents to have the primary environment impact, with water coming second. Therefore, the initial focus will be the capability to record and track the energy related environmental impact of HTC services and applications over time by choosing the right metrics that capture these aspects.

While the possible frameworks to collect and aggregate these metrics are discussed in Chapter 5, this section briefly describes the methodology on metrics implementation and reporting suitable for the HTC computing resources.

3.5.1 Metrics at Site Level

Sites providing HTC services have similar hardware configurations to sites providing cloud services. Therefore, similar metrics are expected to be collected.

One common metric is the Power Usage Effectiveness (**PUE**) used to determine the energy efficiency of a data center. While many sites are reporting **PUE** values, for missing sites a default value could be assumed until sites can update it to demonstrate improvement. The idea is to reward sites that make an effort to improve the infrastructure to be more environmentally friendly, while not penalising the ones that have no immediate means to do that. This is not just for **PUE** but also and more generally for carbon emissions. The more important aspect is to measure improvements, rather than absolute values that might be difficult to interpret.

²³ https://hubblo-org.github.io/scaphandre-documentation/explanations/host_metrics.html

²⁴ <https://developer.nvidia.com/dcgm>

²⁵ <https://home.cern/science/computing/grid>

²⁶ <https://home.cern/science/accelerators/large-hadron-collider>

Along with power consumption, HTC sites are also measuring or expected to measure their carbon footprint (**CFP**). This is a more complex endeavour since it has to encompass all Scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions²⁷, but initially only scope 2 (mainly the operations) will be part of the measurement and monitoring.

With this simplification in place an initial formula for **CFP** is $E * U * C$, where:

- **E** is the total energy used (kWh) by site
- **U** is the share of the HW (%) used for a specific workflow (parallel workflows at a time are assumed)
- **C** is the Carbon content (kg/kWh) in energy provided.

3.5.2 Metrics at Worker Node Level

A worker node is the basic computing unit responsible for executing individual tasks or jobs submitted to the HTC service.

Historically the HTC specific payloads were submitted as single core workloads and while nowadays this changed, with several cores allocated per job, the most useful related metric is the **power consumption per CPU core**. Sites are expected to report this metric either as a single value, or as a list depending on the hardware involved. Alternatively, for non-reporting sites a default value could be provided, and this could act as an incentive for sites to update the numbers every time they improve.

Ongoing work and investigations are taking place on how job-based measurements can be done and validated. For example, the average **power consumption per HS23**²⁸ can be estimated based on the hardware inventory at sites and the workload reported. Another possibility would consist in using the batch system capabilities to report back energy consumption and report it further upstream in the accounting tools, but this approach is in its early stages.

All these metrics that are characterising consumption by particular payloads can be evaluated by tools described in Section 6 and then collected by pilot jobs submitted by DIRAC workload manager to report consumption of power and other resources per executed user task.

3.5.3 Metrics at Service Level

The systems and services used for scheduling jobs to the HTC clusters can be also subject of power consumption monitoring and reporting. For example, the EGI Workload Manager²⁹ service (based on DIRAC WMS – section 14.4) consists of a number of VMs (10 mid-range virtual servers) running various components of the service. The service uses also database servers hosted in the same computing centre. The load of the service can vary in a large range depending on the user's activity. This load and the corresponding power consumption are subject to a dedicated monitoring and optimization using tools described in Section 6. In particular, the next generation of the DIRAC services that will be used for the GreenDIGIT orchestration demonstrator will be deployed using a Kubernetes infrastructure. This will allow to allocate resources dynamically as required by the current loads and not assuming

²⁷ <https://www.carbonneutral.com/news/scope-1-2-3-emissions-explained>

²⁸ HEPSCore: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2879939/files/document.pdf>

²⁹ <https://www.egi.eu/service/workload-manager/>

peak loads as it is done now. This will require measurements of the system loads and elaborating algorithms for load prediction and the corresponding resources allocation.

3.6 Energy Carbon Content Collection

3.6.1 Carbon Intensity of Electricity

In addition to basic parameters such as consumption and price, carbon intensity is essential for data centers and their power consumption. This parameter is driven by both grid regulation (production vs consumption) and the fact that renewable energy is highly dependent on weather conditions. To help with the regulation requirements on the consumption side, it can be used flexibility, the ability to control or shift load. The power grids are operated by Transmission System Operators (TSOs), which are responsible for the stable and efficient use of currently available resources.

Carbon intensity of electricity is referred to as Operating Emissions Rate which can be in general a metric formed from mix of pollutants (Green House Gases, or GHG intensity) not only the CO₂. We distinguish two types of rates:

- Marginal rate – based on the emissions of power plant needed in response to a change in consumption, serving as a signal for load shifting and indicates how much can be avoided.
- Average rate – an average of emissions of all power plants needed to cover current demand. It can describe the current carbon impact of a particular data center or workload.

The use of marginal carbon intensity as a signal for load shifting and avoided emissions reporting is attractive, but controversial due to issues of accountability, accuracy, and reliability. Therefore, more complex life cycle tracking methods are proposed and simple and easy to understand load shifting signals are used (solar + wind ratio in the current power mix).

3.6.2 Carbon Intensity Data Availability

The current carbon intensity of electricity is not a value generally available, compared to price or production mix. Although in some countries the data is available directly from the TSO, in most it must be calculated from the actual production mix. To the calculation enters typically estimates (carbon intensity of individual fuels and embedded emissions) and methodical decisions (reflecting imports/exports and counting batteries and pumped-storage hydroelectricity). There are 3 levels of data sources. Individual TSOs, European Association of TSOs (ENTSO-E) and aggregation platforms focused on providing data for reporting emissions and load shifting.

Current generation mix is available through APIs of individual TSOs or through the ENTSO-E, where all data is available in full granularity and frequency. In addition, the ENTSO-E provides historical data and even forecasts, all free of charge. To calculate the carbon intensity of the generation mix, we need emission factors for each source. A freely available reference table can be found in the contributions section of the well-known aggregator platform, ElectricityMaps³⁰. Well curated data (current and forecasted carbon intensity) are available directly from aggregator platforms (Electricity Maps, WattTime³¹, OpenClimateFix), but are typically commercially available or incomplete.

³⁰ <https://github.com/electricitymaps/electricitymaps-contrib/wiki/Default-emission-factors>

³¹ <https://watttime.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/WattTime-MOER-modeling-20221004.pdf>

In terms of data granularity and frequency, the generally available data described above covers regions in Europe that are typically equivalent to countries and is provided on an hourly basis. Datasets are available, for example from the European Environment Agency (EEA), that cover historical data with granularity such as years.

Standardization efforts are underway, in particular by the Linux Foundation's Carbon Data Specification Consortium (CDSC). The Green Software Foundation provides the Carbon Aware SDK, an abstraction layer that decouples applications from data sources.

3.7 Energy data model and format

The existing energy monitoring tools, such as Scaphandre³², PowerAPI³³, or Kepler³⁴, generally implement a standard approach. First, the data is collected by a software or hardware probe, second, the collected metrics are stored in an energy database, and third, the stored data is reported to a user through monitoring tools. To facilitate industrial adoption, such tools are designed to integrate into existing monitoring systems, such as Prometheus for storage and Grafana for reporting.

To keep track of usage history, energy metrics are stored as time-series of the power usage in Watts, or in Ampere-hours per second if the device is battery-powered. The energy data of a system can be implemented as a set of time-series rather than a single one, to provide a finer granularity. For instance, each core of a CPU can be monitored independently. As a consequence, simultaneously monitoring different granularity levels of a given system may lead to redundancy in measures. For instance, the energy used by a given core of a CPU will appear in the time-series of this core, of the CPU it belongs to, of its server, and of its infrastructure. Thus, the exact scope that the time-series represent must also be stored, to clarify how such energy data can be aggregated. In addition, details such as the methodology used to obtain such data are relevant to store with such data, to quantify the level of confidence in said data. For instance, modelled power values are not as trustworthy as measured power values, and may not be considered as a ground truth for further research.

In addition to energy metrics, the Green Software Measurement Model (GSMM) [16] recommends to monitor usage activity, such as the CPU, GPU or RAM usage, expressed as a percentage, or the amount of data permanently stored or transmitted over network. Such metrics will allow for quantifying the efficiency of the monitored system as the amount of useful work produced per unit of energy used. While GSMM proposes a framework to unify the setup, tools, and procedures regarding energy measure, it does not propose a standardized data model for energy measures.

³² <https://github.com/hubblo-org/scaphandre>

³³ <https://powerapi.org/>

³⁴ <https://github.com/sustainable-computing-io/kepler>

3.8 Sustainability and Monitoring Considerations in HPC and HPC-AI Data Centre Architectures

The evolution of HPC and HPC-AI data centre architectures is reshaping the way sustainability must be monitored, interpreted, and reported. Architectural trends such as heterogeneous CPU-GPU nodes, increasing rack power density, advanced cooling strategies, and emerging orchestration models do not only affect computational performance, but also determine what can be measured reliably and how energy, carbon, and infrastructure overheads can be attributed across the system. For this reason, the following sections examine the main architectural and operational characteristics of contemporary HPC and HPC-AI environments from the perspective of observability and sustainability assessment, providing a bridge between monitoring design and the advanced sustainability metrics.

3.8.1 Architectural Characteristics of Traditional HPC and HPC-AI Systems

Traditional HPC systems are typically organized around tightly integrated compute nodes, high-speed interconnects such as InfiniBand, parallel storage, and batch-oriented resource management, all designed to maximize performance for large-scale scientific workloads. In contrast to general-purpose cloud environments, where elasticity and multi-tenancy are central design features, HPC platforms are usually optimized for tightly coupled execution, low-latency communication, and predictable runtime behaviour [17]. This architectural model has important sustainability implications because energy demand is shaped not only by processors, but also by communication patterns, memory behaviour, storage access, and the efficiency of the interconnect fabric itself. Energy-aware HPC operation therefore emphasizes that sustainability monitoring in HPC must consider the system as a coordinated infrastructure rather than as a collection of isolated servers [18].

These characteristics are becoming more pronounced as HPC systems evolve toward heterogeneous HPC-AI platforms. Current trends visible across leading supercomputing systems, including those represented in recent Top500-era discussions and pre-exascale system designs, show increasing reliance on GPU-rich and hybrid architectures, often organized around dense nodes or fat nodes that combine many cores, large memory capacity, and multiple accelerators within a single server [19]. Such designs improve computational capability and locality for demanding workloads, but they also complicate energy attribution and monitoring because the behaviour of CPUs, GPUs, memory, interconnects, and software stacks must increasingly be interpreted together rather than separately. Recent studies on heterogeneous and pre-exascale systems show that while fine-grained telemetry is becoming more available, it is also becoming more difficult to aggregate and compare consistently across components and platforms [20].

A further architectural consequence of this evolution is rising rack power density, especially in GPU-accelerated and AI-oriented deployments. As computational density increases, so do the demands on power delivery, thermal control, and system-level observability [21]. This is one reason why newer HPC-AI facilities are increasingly associated with advanced cooling strategies, including liquid-assisted approaches, although the monitoring implications of cooling technologies are discussed separately in Section 3.8.3. Architectural characterization determines what needs to be measured, how energy and carbon impacts can be attributed, and whether sustainability metrics remain comparable across traditional HPC, GPU-rich HPC-AI, and federated RI environments [22] [23].

3.8.2 GPU-Accelerated and AI-native HPC Clusters

GPU-accelerated and AI-native clusters represent a major architectural shift from traditional CPU-centric HPC systems [24]. Rather than treating accelerators as optional co-processors, these platforms are increasingly designed around GPUs as the primary source of computational throughput, with CPUs taking on orchestration, data preparation, communication, and control-plane responsibilities. Multi-GPU inference shows that this balance is critical: poor CPU provisioning can leave GPUs underutilized even when ample accelerator capacity is available, meaning that the effective **CPU-GPU ratio** becomes an important performance and efficiency parameter rather than a simple hardware specification [25]. For sustainability monitoring, this implies that energy efficiency in such clusters cannot be inferred from GPU deployment alone, but must account for how well CPUs, GPUs, and software pipelines are matched in practice.

This architectural trend is also changing the physical profile of computing infrastructure. Recent analyses of AI-oriented data centres show that high-performance accelerated servers create far greater infrastructure demands than conventional server platforms, with AI computing racks commonly reaching power densities in the range of **30-100+ kW per rack** [26]. Such densities are substantially above those of traditional data centre racks and place greater pressure on power delivery, cooling systems, and operational control. In AI-native clusters, sustainability assessment must therefore extend beyond node-level compute metrics to include rack-level power behaviour, transient load variability, and the interaction between accelerator utilization and facility infrastructure. This is particularly important because accelerated servers are now a major driver of future data centre electricity demand growth [27].

The main significance of GPU-accelerated and AI-native clusters is that they require more fine-grained and architecture-aware monitoring than traditional systems. Energy attribution becomes harder because compute activity is distributed across CPUs, GPUs, memory subsystems, and high-speed interconnects, while efficiency depends not only on hardware capability but also on workload balance, orchestration overhead, and the ability to keep accelerators productively occupied. As a result, these clusters strengthen the case for multi-layer telemetry, device-level observability, and sustainability metrics that can distinguish between installed accelerator capacity and effectively utilized accelerator capacity. In this sense, GPU-accelerated and AI-native clusters are not simply faster versions of earlier HPC systems; they introduce a different sustainability measurement problem that must be reflected in monitoring design and reporting practice.

3.8.3 Cooling and Thermal Management Implications

Cooling has become a central sustainability issue in modern HPC and HPC-AI data centres because thermal management affects not only hardware reliability and performance stability, but also a substantial share of total facility energy use. Traditional air cooling remains the dominant approach in many installations, yet its effectiveness becomes increasingly constrained as computational density rises and as GPU-rich nodes push rack-level heat loads beyond what conventional airflow-based systems can efficiently handle [28]. In such environments, cooling is no longer a background facilities function; it directly shapes operational efficiency, influences the facility overhead captured in metrics such as PUE, and affects how energy consumption should be interpreted across the full infrastructure stack. As a result, sustainability assessment in HPC-AI environments must consider cooling as an integral component of the computing system rather than as an external service layer [29].

This challenge is becoming more pronounced with the shift toward dense accelerator-based architectures, where liquid-assisted approaches are increasingly adopted to cope with higher thermal loads. Direct liquid cooling and immersion cooling offer clear advantages in such settings because they can remove heat more efficiently, support higher rack power densities, and reduce the cooling overhead associated with maintaining stable operation under heavy computational demand [30]. At the same time, these approaches are not without trade-offs. They introduce different infrastructure requirements, integration complexity, maintenance considerations, and operational risks, and their sustainability benefits depends on how they are implemented in the broader facility context. The significance of cooling technologies lies not only in their engineering performance, but in the way they reshape the energy profile, thermal behaviour, and reporting boundaries of HPC and HPC-AI data centres [31].

For sustainability monitoring and reporting, the main implication is that different cooling strategies alter both what needs to be measured and how those measurements should be interpreted. Air, liquid, and immersion-cooled facilities differ in thermal behaviour, cooling energy demand, water dependency, and potential for heat capture or reuse, meaning that site-level sustainability metrics are not directly comparable unless these differences are made explicit [32]. This is especially important in research infrastructures and federated environments, where consistent assessment depends on clearly defined monitoring boundaries and comparable treatment of facility overheads. In this sense, cooling and thermal management directly affect the quality of observability, the completeness of energy attribution, and the reliability of sustainability reporting across heterogeneous digital infrastructure environments.

3.8.4 Energy and Sustainability Challenges in Exascale Systems

Exascale systems intensify sustainability challenges because they combine unprecedented computational capability with very high and tightly coupled demands on power delivery, cooling, system software, and operational control [33]. At this scale, energy efficiency is no longer a secondary optimization target, but a primary design constraint that shapes architecture, procurement, and runtime management. Energy-aware HPC operation shows that modern supercomputing centres increasingly treat power as a managed resource, using power caps, workload-aware control, and coordinated facility strategies to balance performance against electricity cost and energy efficiency [34]. This reflects a broader shift in exascale thinking: the challenge is not only to reach extreme performance, but to do so within realistic energy, thermal, and infrastructure limits.

A central difficulty is that exascale energy use cannot be understood solely at the level of processors or accelerators. Large systems rely on dense heterogeneous nodes, high-speed interconnects, parallel storage, resilience mechanisms, and increasingly complex software stacks, all of which contribute to the total operational footprint. Recent analyses of supercomputing trends show that gains in peak performance often remain closely associated with rising power consumption, even as systems improve in energy efficiency rankings [35]. This means that sustainability assessment at exascale must account not only for efficiency per operation, but also for total system demand, facility overheads, and the trade-offs between absolute performance growth and operational energy intensity. In this context, exascale systems expose a persistent tension between computational ambition and sustainable operation.

These challenges also make monitoring and reporting more difficult. Energy data must increasingly be collected across multiple levels, from node and device telemetry to scheduler, facility, and cooling

infrastructure, if exascale systems are to be assessed meaningfully. While harvesting energy consumption across European HPC systems highlights the importance of integrating heterogeneous measurement sources for more consistent accounting [36], while broader studies of exascale-era operation emphasize that power-performance trade-offs, resilience overheads, and infrastructure boundaries all influence what sustainability metrics actually mean in practice. The main implication is that exascale sustainability cannot be captured by a single efficiency indicator; it requires multi-layer observability, careful system-boundary definition, and metrics that remain interpretable across heterogeneous architectures and sites [37].

3.8.5 Sustainability Assessment Challenges in HPC and Cloud Environments

Sustainability assessment differs significantly between HPC and cloud environments because the two models are built around different operational assumptions, resource allocation practices, and observability boundaries. HPC systems are typically optimized for tightly coupled, batch-oriented workloads running on dedicated resources, whereas cloud environments are designed for elasticity, virtualization, multi-tenancy, and dynamic consolidation [38]. This affects not only how energy is consumed, but also how it can be measured and attributed. In HPC, power and efficiency are often assessed in relation to full-system execution, scheduler-managed jobs, and facility-level infrastructure, while cloud sustainability assessment must additionally account for virtualized resource sharing, fluctuating tenant demand, and the difficulty of attributing operational overheads fairly across workloads [39]. These structural differences mean that sustainability metrics cannot always be transferred directly from one environment to the other without adjustment.

A major challenge lies in comparability and attribution. In cloud systems, energy and carbon accounting are complicated by abstraction layers that separate users from the underlying hardware, making it difficult to determine how much of the operational and embodied footprint should be assigned to individual services or tenants [40]. Whereas fair carbon attribution in cloud data centres highlights exactly this problem, showing that multi-tenant environments require explicit allocation models rather than simple hardware-level measurement alone [41]. In HPC, attribution is often more direct because jobs are scheduled on identifiable nodes or partitions, but comparability remains difficult across sites because reported energy figures may differ in whether they include storage, interconnects, cooling, or only compute components. This creates a common assessment problem across both domains: sustainability reporting depends not only on collecting data, but also on defining consistent system boundaries and attribution rules.

These differences also affect which sustainability strategies are visible through monitoring. Cloud environments can often exploit consolidation, elastic scaling, workload migration, and virtualization-aware optimization to improve utilization and reduce idle overheads, whereas HPC systems are constrained more strongly by tightly synchronized execution, reservation models, and performance-sensitive communication patterns. Conversely, HPC platforms may expose richer scheduler and node-level telemetry for scientific jobs, while cloud platforms often expose less direct hardware observability to end users even when internal providers have detailed infrastructure insight. The main implication is that sustainability assessment in HPC and cloud environments should not be treated as a single uniform monitoring problem. Instead, metrics, telemetry models, and reporting practices must be adapted to the operational logic of each environment if assessments are to remain meaningful, comparable, and useful for decision-making across research infrastructures and digital platforms.

3.8.6 Orchestration and Observability in Emerging HPC-AI Platforms

The increasing convergence of High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) workloads has led to the adoption of cloud-native technologies, particularly Kubernetes, within traditionally HPC-oriented infrastructures. While HPC systems have historically relied on tightly coupled architectures and specialised schedulers, the growing demand for flexible, scalable, and reproducible environments has driven the integration of container orchestration platforms into HPC-AI data centres.

Cloud-native HPC

Cloud-native HPC refers to the application of containerisation, microservices, and orchestration frameworks to HPC environments. Kubernetes provides a platform for deploying and managing containerised workloads at scale, enabling features such as portability, dynamic scaling, and automated resource management. In HPC-AI contexts, this is particularly relevant for machine learning workflows, which often require complex software stacks, reproducibility, and rapid iteration.

By leveraging containers, HPC systems can decouple software environments from underlying hardware, simplifying deployment and improving interoperability across infrastructures. This approach also facilitates integration with cloud environments, supporting hybrid and federated computing models. However, cloud-native HPC must address challenges related to performance overhead, network latency, and efficient utilisation of specialised hardware such as GPUs and high-speed interconnects.

Slurm vs Kubernetes

Traditional HPC environments are typically managed using job schedulers such as Slurm, which are optimised for batch processing of tightly coupled workloads. Slurm provides fine-grained control over resource allocation, prioritisation, and scheduling policies, making it well-suited for large-scale simulations and MPI-based applications.

In contrast, Kubernetes is designed for orchestrating containerised workloads in distributed systems, with a focus on service-oriented architectures and long-running applications. While Kubernetes has evolved to support batch workloads and GPU scheduling, it does not natively provide the same level of optimisation for tightly coupled HPC applications as Slurm.

As a result, the two systems are often viewed as complementary rather than competing. Slurm excels in performance-critical HPC scheduling, while Kubernetes provides flexibility and ease of deployment for AI and cloud-native workloads. The choice between them depends on workload characteristics, infrastructure design, and operational priorities.

Hybrid Schedulers

To address the limitations of using a single scheduling system, many HPC-AI data centres adopt **hybrid scheduling approaches** that combine Slurm and Kubernetes. In such architectures, Slurm is used to manage compute resources and schedule traditional HPC jobs, while Kubernetes orchestrates containerised workloads on allocated nodes or within dedicated partitions.

Figure 8. Hybrid Kubernetes and Slurm architecture for HPC-AI workloads.

Hybrid schedulers enable the coexistence of HPC and cloud-native workloads within the same infrastructure, improving resource utilisation and operational flexibility. Integration mechanisms include running Kubernetes clusters on top of Slurm-managed resources, or using Slurm as a backend scheduler for Kubernetes workloads. These approaches allow organisations to leverage the strengths of both systems while maintaining compatibility with existing HPC workflows, see Figure 8.

Container Overhead vs Virtual Machines

Containerisation is a key enabler of cloud-native HPC, offering lightweight virtualisation compared to traditional virtual machines (VMs). Containers share the host operating system kernel, resulting in lower overhead, faster startup times, and higher resource efficiency. This makes them particularly suitable for HPC-AI workloads, where performance and scalability are critical.

In contrast, virtual machines provide stronger isolation but incur higher overhead due to full OS virtualisation. This can lead to reduced performance, particularly for compute-intensive and latency-sensitive applications. As a result, containers are increasingly preferred in HPC-AI environments, especially when combined with technologies such as GPU passthrough and high-performance networking.

However, containers may introduce challenges related to security, multi-tenancy, and resource isolation, particularly in shared infrastructures. Additionally, achieving near-native performance requires careful configuration of container runtimes and integration with HPC-specific technologies.

Overall, the adoption of Kubernetes in HPC-AI data centres reflects a broader shift towards flexible, software-defined infrastructures. By combining traditional HPC scheduling with cloud-native orchestration, these environments can support a wider range of workloads while enabling more efficient and sustainable resource utilisation.

3.9 Advanced Sustainability Metrics for Data Centres

Assessing the sustainability of modern data centres requires moving beyond traditional single metrics, such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), towards a more comprehensive set of indicators that capture energy efficiency, environmental impact, and resource utilisation. Directive (EU) 2024/1364 introduces a harmonised framework of sustainability indicators, including metrics such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE), Energy Reuse Factor (ERF), and Renewable Energy Factor (REF), which together provide a multi-dimensional view of data centre performance. Building on this framework, advanced sustainability metrics extend the analysis to include carbon emissions, lifecycle impacts, and resource efficiency, supporting regulatory compliance, enabling benchmarking, and guiding the development of more sustainable digital infrastructures.

3.9.1 CUE (Carbon Usage Effectiveness)

Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) is a key sustainability metric used to quantify the carbon efficiency of a data centre by relating total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to the energy consumption of IT equipment. Unlike Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), which focuses solely on energy efficiency, CUE explicitly incorporates the carbon intensity of the energy supply, thereby providing a more comprehensive measure of environmental impact. The metric is defined by the Green Grid and has been adopted within the European regulatory framework, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, as part of the harmonised set of sustainability indicators for data centre reporting.

CUE is expressed as the ratio of total data centre carbon emissions to the energy consumption of IT equipment, typically measured in kgCO₂e per kWh. It captures both direct and indirect emissions associated with electricity consumption and depending on the reporting scope, may include additional sources such as on-site fuel use or purchased thermal energy. As such, CUE aligns primarily with Scope 2 emissions under the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol, while extensions of the metric may incorporate elements of Scope 1 emissions when on-site generation is present.

The metric is particularly relevant in the context of increasing electrification and the transition towards renewable energy sources. Data centres with identical PUE values may exhibit significantly different environmental impacts depending on the carbon intensity of their electricity supply. Consequently, CUE provides a critical complement to energy-based metrics, enabling a more accurate assessment of sustainability performance across different geographical regions and energy mixes.

Calculation Methodology

CUE is calculated as:

$$CUE = \frac{E_{CO2}}{E_{IT}}$$

where E_{CO2} represents the total carbon emissions associated with the data centre's energy consumption (kgCO₂e), and E_{IT} is the energy consumed by IT equipment (kWh).

In practice, carbon emissions are derived by applying an emission factor to the total energy consumption:

$$E_{CO2} = E_{total} \times EF$$

where E_{total} is the total energy consumed by the data centre and EF is the carbon intensity of the electricity supply (kgCO₂e/kWh). The emission factor may be based on national grid averages, supplier-specific data, or real-time carbon intensity signals, depending on the level of accuracy required.

Estimation Approaches

Several approaches can be distinguished for estimating CUE, differing in the granularity and accuracy of the underlying data.

Static grid-based estimation: This approach uses average national or regional emission factors for electricity generation. It is the simplest method and is widely used for reporting purposes, including compliance with regulatory frameworks. However, it does not capture temporal variations in carbon intensity or the impact of renewable energy procurement strategies.

Supplier-specific or contractual estimation: In this approach, emission factors are derived from energy contracts, such as Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) or Guarantees of Origin (GOOs). This enables more accurate accounting of renewable energy usage but may still rely on averaged values and does not necessarily reflect real-time grid conditions.

Time-resolved (carbon-aware) estimation: More advanced approaches incorporate time-dependent carbon intensity data, enabling the calculation of dynamic CUE values that reflect variations in the energy mix over time. This method is particularly relevant for energy-aware scheduling and optimisation strategies, where workloads can be shifted to periods of lower carbon intensity. Such approaches are increasingly explored in HPC and cloud environments as part of carbon-aware computing frameworks.

Interpretation and Limitations

CUE provides a direct link between energy consumption and environmental impact, making it a valuable metric for benchmarking and sustainability reporting. Lower CUE values indicate lower carbon emissions per unit of IT energy consumption, reflecting either improved energy efficiency, a cleaner energy supply, or both.

However, several limitations must be considered. First, CUE does not account for **embodied carbon**, which may represent a significant portion of total lifecycle emissions, particularly in high-performance computing environments. Second, the metric is sensitive to the choice of emission factors, which can vary depending on the data source and methodology. Third, CUE does not capture workload efficiency or application-level optimisation, meaning that improvements in software efficiency may not be directly reflected in the metric.

Standards and Regulatory Context

CUE is defined and standardised by the Green Grid and is incorporated into broader sustainability reporting frameworks. Within the European context, Directive (EU) 2024/1364 includes carbon-related indicators as part of its harmonised reporting scheme, complementing metrics such as PUE, WUE, ERF, and REF. Additionally, carbon accounting methodologies are aligned with the Greenhouse Gas Protocol, which provides guidance on Scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions.

As regulatory frameworks evolve, there is increasing emphasis on integrating operational metrics such as CUE with lifecycle-based indicators, including embodied carbon, to provide a more comprehensive assessment of data centre sustainability. Future developments, such as the anticipated Data Centre Energy Efficiency Package (DCEEP), are expected to further formalise carbon reporting requirements and introduce benchmarking schemes that incorporate carbon efficiency metrics.

3.9.2 WUE (Water Usage Effectiveness)

Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE) is a key sustainability metric used to quantify the water efficiency of a data centre by relating total water consumption to the energy usage of IT equipment. As data centres increasingly rely on water-intensive cooling technologies, WUE has become an essential indicator for assessing environmental impact beyond energy consumption. The metric was introduced by the Green Grid and is incorporated into European sustainability reporting frameworks, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, which requires the monitoring and reporting of water-related indicators.

WUE captures the total volume of water used directly or indirectly for data centre operations, including cooling systems, humidification, and other auxiliary processes. It is typically expressed in litres per kilowatt-hour (L/kWh) of IT energy consumption, providing a normalised measure that enables comparison across facilities of different sizes and operational profiles. By linking water consumption to IT energy usage, WUE enables a consistent evaluation of water efficiency in relation to computational output.

The metric is particularly relevant in the context of increasing water scarcity and environmental constraints, especially in regions where water resources are limited. Data centres employing evaporative or adiabatic cooling technologies may achieve lower energy consumption but at the cost of higher water usage. As a result, WUE provides a critical complement to energy efficiency metrics such as PUE, enabling a more balanced assessment of trade-offs between energy and water consumption.

Calculation Methodology

WUE is calculated as:

$$WUE = \frac{W_{total}}{E_{IT}}$$

where W_{total} represents the total water consumption of the data centre (litres), and E_{IT} is the energy consumed by IT equipment (kWh).

Water consumption includes all sources of water entering the data centre boundary for operational use. In alignment with Directive (EU) 2024/1364, this may be further distinguished between total water input (WIN) and potable water input (WIN-POT), allowing for a more detailed assessment of water resource usage. Where applicable, water reuse and recycling mechanisms may be accounted for to refine the metric.

Estimation Approaches

Several approaches can be distinguished for estimating WUE, depending on the level of measurement detail and data availability.

Direct measurement of water input: This approach relies on physical water meters installed at the facility boundary and within cooling systems. It provides the most accurate representation of water

consumption and is recommended for compliance with regulatory reporting requirements. Sub-metering of individual systems (e.g., cooling towers, humidifiers) enables more granular analysis and identification of inefficiencies.

System-level estimation: In cases where direct measurement is not available, water consumption may be estimated based on cooling system characteristics and operational parameters. For example, water usage in cooling towers can be approximated using evaporation rates, blowdown cycles, and system load. While less precise, this approach provides a practical alternative for facilities lacking detailed instrumentation.

Lifecycle and indirect water usage estimation: Advanced approaches extend the scope of WUE by considering indirect water consumption associated with electricity generation (often referred to as “water footprint” of energy). This broader perspective captures upstream environmental impacts but is not typically included in standard WUE calculations under current regulatory frameworks.

Interpretation and Limitations

WUE provides a valuable indicator of water efficiency, with lower values indicating reduced water consumption per unit of IT energy usage. However, the interpretation of WUE must consider regional and operational context. For example, a data centre located in a water-abundant region may prioritise energy efficiency over water conservation, while facilities in water-scarce regions must minimise water usage even at the expense of higher energy consumption.

Several limitations should also be considered. First, WUE does not capture the source or sustainability of water use, such as the distinction between potable and non-potable water. Second, the metric does not account for the environmental impact of water discharge or treatment. Third, trade-offs between energy and water efficiency may not be fully reflected when WUE is considered in isolation, highlighting the need for multi-metric evaluation.

Standards and Regulatory Context

WUE is defined by the Green Grid and is included in the set of sustainability indicators required under Directive (EU) 2024/1364. The directive mandates the reporting of water-related KPIs, including total water input and potable water consumption, enabling the calculation of WUE and supporting comparative analysis across data centres.

In addition, water efficiency is increasingly addressed in broader sustainability frameworks, including the EU Code of Conduct for Data Centres and emerging regulatory initiatives focused on environmental impact. As water availability becomes a critical constraint in many regions, WUE is expected to play an increasingly important role in data centre design, operation, and policy compliance.

3.9.3 ERF (Energy Reuse Factor)

Energy Reuse Factor (ERF) is a sustainability metric used to quantify the extent to which energy consumed by a data centre is recovered and reused outside its operational boundaries. As data centres generate significant amounts of waste heat, ERF provides a measure of how effectively this energy is captured and repurposed, contributing to overall energy efficiency and reducing environmental impact. The metric was introduced by the Green Grid and is incorporated into European sustainability reporting frameworks, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, which recognises energy reuse as a key component of sustainable data centre operation.

ERF reflects the transition from linear energy consumption models towards more circular approaches, where waste heat is considered a valuable resource rather than a by-product. Typical reuse applications include district heating systems, industrial processes, and nearby building heating. By quantifying the proportion of energy that is reused, ERF enables data centres to demonstrate their contribution to local energy ecosystems and broader sustainability goals.

The metric is particularly relevant in high-density computing environments, such as HPC and AI data centres, where large volumes of low- to medium-grade heat are generated. Advances in cooling technologies, including liquid cooling and heat recovery systems, have increased the feasibility of capturing and reusing this heat, making ERF an increasingly important indicator in modern data centre design.

Calculation Methodology

ERF is calculated as:

$$ERF = \frac{E_{reuse}}{E_{total}}$$

where E_{reuse} represents the amount of energy recovered and reused outside the data centre (kWh), and E_{total} is the total energy consumed by the data centre (kWh).

In accordance with Directive (EU) 2024/1364, energy reuse is typically measured at the boundary of the data centre, ensuring that only energy exported for external use is included. Internal reuse, such as heat recirculation within the facility, is not considered in the ERF calculation. Accurate measurement requires metering systems capable of capturing heat flows and conversion efficiencies in heat recovery systems.

Estimation Approaches

Several approaches can be used to estimate ERF, depending on the level of infrastructure maturity and measurement capabilities.

Direct measurement of recovered energy: This approach relies on heat meters installed at the point where energy is transferred from the data centre to external systems, such as district heating networks. It provides the most accurate assessment and is required for regulatory reporting and benchmarking purposes.

System-level estimation: In cases where direct measurement is not available, energy reuse may be estimated based on cooling system parameters, such as heat exchanger efficiency, flow rates, and temperature differentials. While less precise, this method provides a practical approximation for facilities in early stages of heat recovery implementation.

Model-based estimation: Advanced approaches use thermodynamic models and simulation tools to estimate potential heat recovery based on system design and operational conditions. These models are particularly useful for planning and optimisation but may require validation through real measurements.

Interpretation and Limitations

ERF provides a measure of circular energy utilisation, with higher values indicating more effective reuse of energy that would otherwise be wasted. In principle, ERF values range from 0 (no energy reuse) to values approaching 1 in highly optimised systems with extensive heat recovery.

However, several limitations must be considered. First, ERF does not account for the quality or usability of the recovered energy, as low-temperature heat may have limited practical applications. Second, the metric does not consider the efficiency of the reuse process or the environmental impact of the systems receiving the energy. Third, ERF is highly dependent on external factors, such as the availability of nearby heat demand and infrastructure for heat distribution, which may limit its applicability in certain locations.

Standards and Regulatory Context

ERF is defined by the Green Grid and is included in the sustainability reporting framework established by Directive (EU) 2024/1364. The directive requires the reporting of energy reuse indicators, enabling the calculation of ERF and supporting the assessment of circular energy practices in data centres.

In addition, energy reuse is increasingly emphasised in European sustainability initiatives, including the EU Code of Conduct for Data Centres and policies promoting district heating and waste heat utilisation. Future regulatory developments, such as the Data Centre Energy Efficiency Package (DCEEP), are expected to further formalise the role of energy reuse in data centre sustainability assessments.

3.9.4 REF (Renewable Energy Factor)

Renewable Energy Factor (REF) is a sustainability metric used to quantify the proportion of a data centre's energy consumption that is supplied from renewable energy sources. As energy consumption represents the dominant component of data centre environmental impact, REF provides a key indicator of the extent to which operations are decoupled from fossil-based energy systems. The metric is defined by the Green Grid and is incorporated into European regulatory frameworks, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, which requires the reporting of renewable energy usage as part of a harmonised sustainability assessment.

REF reflects the increasing importance of energy sourcing in evaluating data centre sustainability. While traditional metrics such as PUE focus on energy efficiency, they do not account for the environmental impact of the energy used. A data centre with a low PUE may still have a high carbon footprint if powered by carbon-intensive electricity. REF addresses this limitation by explicitly measuring the share of renewable energy, thereby complementing metrics such as CUE and enabling a more comprehensive assessment of environmental performance.

Renewable energy sources considered in REF calculations include on-site generation (e.g., solar photovoltaic systems), as well as off-site procurement mechanisms such as Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) and Guarantees of Origin (GOOs). The inclusion of different sourcing mechanisms allows organisations to adopt flexible strategies for increasing renewable energy usage, although these approaches may differ in terms of their environmental impact and temporal alignment with consumption.

Calculation Methodology

REF is calculated as:

$$REF = \frac{E_{renewable}}{E_{total}}$$

where $E_{renewable}$ represents the total energy consumption sourced from renewable energy (kWh), and E_{total} is the total energy consumption of the data centre (kWh).

In accordance with Directive (EU) 2024/1364, renewable energy consumption may be categorised based on its origin, including on-site generation, direct procurement through PPAs, and certified renewable energy through guarantees of origin. Accurate calculation of REF requires consistent accounting to avoid double counting and to ensure alignment with recognised reporting standards.

Estimation Approaches

Several approaches can be distinguished for estimating REF, depending on the availability and granularity of data.

Contractual (market-based) estimation: This approach uses information from energy contracts, including PPAs and guarantees of origin, to determine the share of renewable energy. It is widely used for reporting purposes and aligns with market-based accounting methods defined in the GHG Protocol. However, it may not reflect the actual temporal availability of renewable energy.

Location-based estimation: In this approach, renewable energy share is derived from the average energy mix of the local or national grid. While simpler to implement, it provides less control over renewable sourcing and may underestimate the impact of targeted procurement strategies.

Time-resolved (carbon-aware) estimation: Advanced approaches incorporate time-dependent data on renewable energy availability and grid composition, enabling the calculation of dynamic REF values. This method supports energy-aware workload scheduling and allows data centres to align energy consumption with periods of high renewable generation, improving overall sustainability performance.

Interpretation and Limitations

REF provides a direct measure of renewable energy utilisation, with values ranging from 0 (no renewable energy) to 1 (fully renewable energy supply). Higher REF values indicate a lower reliance on fossil-based energy and contribute to reduced carbon emissions.

However, several limitations must be considered. First, REF does not account for the temporal mismatch between renewable energy generation and data centre consumption, particularly in the case of contractual instruments such as guarantees of origin. Second, the metric does not capture the carbon intensity of residual non-renewable energy sources, requiring complementary metrics such as CUE for a complete assessment. Third, differences between market-based and location-based accounting can lead to inconsistencies in reported values, highlighting the need for transparent methodologies.

Standards and Regulatory Context

REF is defined by the Green Grid and is included in the sustainability reporting framework established by Directive (EU) 2024/1364. The directive requires the reporting of renewable energy consumption and its sources, enabling the calculation of REF and supporting benchmarking across data centres.

In addition, renewable energy usage is a central component of broader European sustainability policies, including the European Green Deal and climate neutrality targets. Future regulatory developments, such as the Data Centre Energy Efficiency Package (DCEEP), are expected to further formalise renewable energy reporting and introduce mechanisms to evaluate the quality and temporal alignment of renewable energy sourcing.

3.9.5 Scope 1, 2 and 3 Emissions

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with data centre operations are commonly classified into three categories—Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3—according to the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol. This classification provides a structured framework for assessing the full carbon footprint of digital infrastructures, encompassing both direct and indirect emissions across the value chain. Within the context of data centres, this categorisation is increasingly relevant due to evolving regulatory requirements, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364 and broader European sustainability reporting frameworks such as the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS E1).

Scope 1 emissions refer to **direct emissions** from sources owned or controlled by the data centre operator. These include emissions from on-site fuel combustion, such as diesel generators used for backup power, as well as refrigerant leakage from cooling systems. Although typically smaller in magnitude compared to other scopes, Scope 1 emissions remain important due to their direct environmental impact and regulatory implications, particularly in relation to F-gas regulations and emissions reporting obligations.

Scope 2 emissions correspond to **indirect emissions from purchased energy**, primarily electricity consumed by the data centre. As energy consumption represents the dominant operational component of data centre emissions, Scope 2 is typically the largest contributor to the overall carbon footprint. The magnitude of these emissions depends on both the total energy consumption and the carbon intensity of the electricity supply. Metrics such as Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) are directly linked to Scope 2 emissions, providing a normalised measure of carbon efficiency relative to IT energy usage.

Scope 3 emissions encompass **all other indirect emissions** occurring across the value chain, including upstream and downstream activities. In the context of data centres, this includes embodied carbon associated with the manufacturing, transportation, and disposal of IT equipment, as well as emissions related to construction, supply chains, and outsourced services. Scope 3 emissions are often the most complex to quantify due to their distributed nature and reliance on external data sources, but they can represent a significant, and in some cases dominant, share of total lifecycle emissions, particularly in environments powered by low-carbon electricity.

Estimation Approaches

Different approaches are used to estimate emissions across the three scopes, reflecting differences in data availability and methodological complexity.

Direct measurement and fuel-based calculation (Scope 1): Scope 1 emissions are typically calculated based on the quantity of fuels consumed on-site, using standard emission factors (kgCO₂e per unit of fuel). Refrigerant emissions are estimated based on leakage rates and global warming potential (GWP) values defined under international standards.

Energy-based calculation (Scope 2): Scope 2 emissions are calculated by multiplying electricity consumption by an emission factor. Two approaches are commonly used: location-based accounting, which reflects the average carbon intensity of the grid, and market-based accounting, which considers contractual energy sourcing such as renewable energy certificates or PPAs.

Lifecycle and supply chain assessment (Scope 3): Scope 3 emissions are estimated using lifecycle assessment (LCA) methodologies, supplier-provided data such as Environmental Product Declarations

(EPDs), or sector-specific emission factors. Due to the complexity of supply chains, estimation often involves a combination of bottom-up and top-down approaches, with varying levels of accuracy.

Interpretation and Limitations

The three-scope framework provides a comprehensive view of emissions across the full lifecycle of data centre operations, enabling organisations to identify key emission sources and prioritise mitigation strategies. Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions are generally more straightforward to quantify and manage, while Scope 3 emissions present greater challenges due to data availability and methodological uncertainty.

However, several limitations must be considered. First, differences in accounting methodologies, particularly for Scope 2 (location-based vs market-based), can lead to inconsistencies in reported emissions. Second, Scope 3 estimates often rely on approximations and may lack comparability across organisations. Third, the framework does not inherently account for temporal dynamics or operational efficiency, requiring complementary metrics such as CUE, REF, and embodied carbon indicators for a complete sustainability assessment.

Standards and Regulatory Context

The classification of emissions into Scope 1, 2, and 3 is defined by the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol, which provides internationally recognised standards for carbon accounting. Within the European context, these classifications are embedded in regulatory frameworks such as Directive (EU) 2024/1364 and the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS E1), which require organisations to disclose emissions across all scopes.

In addition, emerging initiatives, including the anticipated Data Centre Energy Efficiency Package (DCEEP), are expected to further standardise emissions reporting and integrate scope-based accounting with operational sustainability metrics. This reflects a broader shift towards comprehensive, lifecycle-based assessment of environmental impact in digital infrastructures.

3.9.6 Embodied Carbon of IT Equipment

There are different principal methods and tools for estimating the embodied carbon footprint of research infrastructure (RI) equipment, with particular focus on servers and storage systems. Embodied carbon refers to the greenhouse gas emissions generated across the full lifecycle of a hardware component outside its operational phase, encompassing raw material extraction, manufacturing, assembly, transportation, and end-of-life disposal. These emissions are classified as Scope 3 under the GHG Protocol and are increasingly subject to mandatory disclosure under EU sustainability reporting frameworks, including ESRS E1 and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED 2024/1364). Recent lifecycle studies demonstrate that embodied carbon can represent the dominant share of a server's total lifecycle emissions, particularly in environments supplied by low-carbon electricity, underscoring the necessity of systematic measurement and structured reporting.

Estimation Approaches

Three principal estimation approaches can be distinguished, differing in the level of input data required and the analytical scope they support.

Process-based Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). A full LCA conducted in accordance with ISO 14044 involves a bottom-up analysis of every material input, manufacturing step, and logistics flow associated with a hardware component or system. This approach yields the highest accuracy but requires detailed input

data typically accessible only to manufacturers or specialist consultants. It is therefore impractical for infrastructure operators managing a data centre fleet, and is most relevant as the methodological basis underpinning manufacturer-published product declarations.

Component-based (bottom-up) Estimation. This approach decomposes a server into its constituent hardware components, processors, memory modules, storage devices (SSD and HDD), network interface cards, chassis, and cooling elements, and assigns an emission factor (kgCO₂e per unit) to each. Total embodied carbon is computed as:

$$C_{\text{embodied}} = \sum (N_{\text{component}} \times EF_{\text{component}})$$

where $N_{\text{component}}$ is the quantity of a given component and $EF_{\text{component}}$ is its emission factor, derived from Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs), published LCA studies, or approximation models. This method is operationally tractable and sufficiently granular for fleet-level analysis. CPU and semiconductor components have been shown to concentrate the majority of a server's embodied carbon — typically 84–99% of the total — and should be prioritised in data collection efforts.

EPD-based (top-down) Estimation. An Environmental Product Declaration (EPD), standardised under ISO 14025 and ISO 14044, is a manufacturer-published document reporting the lifecycle environmental impact of a product in a comparable and verifiable format. Three tiers of data quality can be distinguished. Tier 1 consists of model-specific EPDs, offering the highest accuracy and preferred for procurement decisions and formal regulatory reporting. Tier 2 relies on category-level estimates from established tools such as EcoDiag, applicable for fleet-level assessments where individual EPDs are unavailable. Tier 3 applies cost- or weight-based proxies and represents the least accurate option, applicable only where no primary data source

Standards and Regulatory Context

The selection of an estimation method should be informed by applicable standards and evolving regulatory requirements. EN 15978 defines the standard for building and infrastructure lifecycle assessments, partially applicable to data centre facilities, and has been incorporated into the scope of D4.2. EN 15804+A2 governs the methodology manufacturers must apply when preparing EPDs, ensuring comparability and verifiability across declarations. The EU Level(s) Framework and the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) establish energy and carbon performance reporting requirements for data centre operators with an installed IT power demand of at least 500 kW. From mid 2026, the European Commission is expected to release the Data Centre Energy Efficiency Package (DCEEP), introducing a formal sustainability rating and labelling system that will further formalise embodied carbon reporting obligations for European research infrastructures.

3.9.7 AI Efficiency Metrics (TFLOPS/W, Training Energy per Model)

The rapid growth of artificial intelligence (AI) workloads has introduced new challenges for sustainability assessment in data centres, as traditional metrics such as PUE or CUE do not adequately capture the efficiency of compute-intensive workloads. AI systems, particularly those used for training large-scale models, exhibit highly variable and resource-intensive behaviour, often dominated by accelerator-based architectures such as GPUs and specialised AI processors. As a result, dedicated AI efficiency metrics have emerged to quantify the relationship between computational performance and energy consumption.

A primary metric used to evaluate hardware-level efficiency is **performance per watt**, commonly expressed as tera floating-point operations per second per watt (TFLOPS/W). This metric measures the computational throughput of a system relative to its power consumption and is widely used to compare the efficiency of different processors and accelerator architectures. Higher TFLOPS/W values indicate more efficient utilisation of energy for computation, making this metric particularly relevant for benchmarking GPUs and AI accelerators in high-performance environments.

At the workload level, **training energy per model** has become a critical metric for assessing the environmental impact of AI systems. This metric quantifies the total energy required to train a model from initialisation to convergence, typically expressed in kilowatt-hours (kWh) or megawatt-hours (MWh). It captures the combined effect of hardware efficiency, system utilisation, training duration, and algorithmic complexity. For large-scale models, training energy can reach substantial levels, highlighting the importance of optimising both hardware and software components.

Calculation Methodology

Performance per watt is calculated as:

$$\text{TFLOPS/W} = \frac{\text{Computational Throughput (TFLOPS)}}{\text{Power Consumption (W)}}$$

where computational throughput may be measured using peak theoretical performance or sustained performance under benchmark workloads.

Training energy per model is calculated as:

$$E_{\text{training}} = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} P(t) dt$$

where $P(t)$ represents the total power consumption of the system over the training period from start time t_0 to completion time t_f . In practice, this is often approximated as:

$$E_{\text{training}} \approx P_{\text{avg}} \times T_{\text{training}}$$

where P_{avg} is the average system power and T_{training} is the total training time.

Estimation Approaches

Several approaches are used to estimate AI efficiency metrics, depending on the level of measurement detail and system instrumentation.

Benchmark-based evaluation: Performance per watt is commonly derived from standardised benchmarks, such as MLPerf, which provide comparable measurements across hardware platforms. These benchmarks typically measure sustained throughput under representative AI workloads.

System-level energy measurement: Training energy is estimated using node-level or cluster-level power measurements, obtained through hardware telemetry interfaces (e.g., RAPL, NVML) or external power meters. This approach provides accurate energy estimates but requires high-resolution monitoring infrastructure.

Model-based estimation: In cases where direct measurement is not feasible, energy consumption may be estimated using models based on hardware specifications, utilisation rates, and training duration. While less precise, this approach enables scalability across large deployments.

Interpretation and Limitations

AI efficiency metrics provide valuable insights into the relationship between computational performance and energy consumption. Higher TFLOPS/W values indicate more efficient hardware, while lower training energy per model reflects improvements in system utilisation, algorithm design, and optimisation techniques.

However, several limitations must be considered. First, TFLOPS/W focuses on raw computational performance and may not reflect real-world efficiency for specific AI workloads, particularly those that are memory- or communication-bound. Second, training energy per model is highly dependent on model architecture, dataset size, and training methodology, limiting comparability across different use cases. Third, these metrics do not account for the full lifecycle impact of AI systems, including embodied carbon or inference-phase energy consumption.

Standards and Emerging Practices

While no single standard currently governs AI efficiency metrics, several initiatives are emerging to improve comparability and transparency. The MLPerf benchmark suite provides widely adopted performance and energy benchmarks for AI systems, while research efforts increasingly focus on reporting energy consumption and carbon footprint alongside model performance.

In addition, recent studies on “green AI” advocate for the inclusion of energy and carbon metrics in AI research reporting, promoting more sustainable development practices. These approaches align with broader sustainability frameworks and are expected to play an increasing role in future regulatory and benchmarking initiatives for AI and HPC infrastructures.

3.9.8 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) Approaches

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a methodological framework used to evaluate the environmental impact of a system across its entire lifecycle, from raw material extraction and manufacturing to operation and end-of-life disposal. In the context of data centres and research infrastructures, LCA provides a comprehensive approach to assessing sustainability by integrating both operational impacts (e.g., energy consumption) and embodied impacts (e.g., hardware production and infrastructure construction). As sustainability requirements evolve, LCA is increasingly recognised as a necessary complement to operational metrics such as PUE, CUE, WUE, ERF, and REF.

LCA enables a holistic evaluation of environmental performance by considering multiple impact categories, including greenhouse gas emissions, energy use, water consumption, and resource depletion. For data centres, this includes not only IT equipment such as servers and storage systems, but also supporting infrastructure, including buildings, cooling systems, and power distribution components. As a result, LCA provides a broader perspective than metrics focused solely on operational efficiency, supporting more informed decision-making in design, procurement, and operation.

Methodological Framework

LCA is typically conducted in accordance with internationally recognised standards, including ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, which define a four-phase methodology:

Goal and scope definition: This phase defines the purpose of the assessment, system boundaries, functional unit, and level of detail. In data centre applications, the functional unit may be defined in terms of computational output (e.g., per kWh IT energy, per workload, or per service delivered).

Inventory analysis (LCI): This phase involves the collection of data on all inputs and outputs associated with the system, including materials, energy flows, emissions, and waste. For data centres, this includes manufacturing data for IT equipment, operational energy consumption, and infrastructure-related inputs.

Impact assessment (LCIA): Inventory data are translated into environmental impact indicators, such as global warming potential (GWP), water use, and resource depletion. Carbon footprint (kgCO_{2e}) is typically the primary indicator for sustainability assessments.

Interpretation: The results are analysed to identify key contributors to environmental impact and to support decision-making. Sensitivity analysis and uncertainty assessment are often included to evaluate the robustness of results.

Estimation Approaches

Different approaches to LCA can be distinguished based on data availability and analytical scope.

Process-based LCA: This bottom-up approach models each component and process in detail, using primary data where available. It provides high accuracy but requires extensive data collection and is often limited to specific components or systems.

Input–output (IO) LCA: This top-down approach uses economic input–output models to estimate environmental impacts across entire supply chains. It enables broader system coverage but with lower granularity and accuracy.

Hybrid LCA: Hybrid approaches combine process-based and input–output methods to balance accuracy and completeness. This approach is increasingly used in data centre assessments to capture both detailed hardware impacts and broader infrastructure effects.

Interpretation and Limitations

LCA provides a comprehensive framework for evaluating sustainability across the full lifecycle of data centre systems. It enables the identification of trade-offs between operational efficiency and embodied impacts, supporting more balanced decision-making. For example, improvements in energy efficiency may be offset by increased embodied carbon due to more complex hardware or infrastructure.

However, several limitations must be considered. First, LCA results are highly dependent on data quality and availability, particularly for supply chain and manufacturing processes. Second, methodological choices, such as system boundaries and allocation rules, can significantly influence results, reducing comparability across studies. Third, LCA is typically static and does not capture temporal dynamics, such as changes in energy mix or system utilisation over time.

Standards and Regulatory Context

LCA methodologies are defined by ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 and are widely applied across industries for environmental assessment. In the European context, additional standards such as EN 15978 (for buildings and infrastructure) and EN 15804+A2 (for Environmental Product Declarations) provide guidance relevant to data centre components and facilities.

LCA is increasingly integrated into regulatory and policy frameworks, including the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS E1) and initiatives related to the Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2024/1364. Future developments, such as the Data Centre Energy Efficiency Package (DCEEP), are expected to further formalise lifecycle-based sustainability assessment and promote the integration of LCA with operational metrics.

4 Scheduling Approaches for Green Optimisation of Scientific Workflow

4.1 Motivation

Power-grid aware scheduling is based on a long-term effort to increase efficiency in computing infrastructures. In resource-aware job scheduling, an optimal match between job characteristics (software, data) and available resources (CPU, RAM, GPU) is searched. The basic idea is to add an element describing the consumption view to this concept. Existing work is typically based on power capping, optimising workload placement between nodes (keeping below the level at which modern CPUs are most effective), and automatically powering down nodes [42].

4.2 Carbon-aware Optimisation

An important consideration is the criteria used to optimize. In addition to power consumption and its price, the current carbon intensity of the regional electricity and the demand for power-grid regulation are added. In the case of waste heat reuse, the current heat demand can also be an important input. Flexibility is the ability to manage consumption over time based on demand. It is cited as one of the solutions to energy and climate challenges and is based on smart grid concepts that have been developed over the years [43]. An emerging term to describe these concepts in software design and implementation is carbon-aware. The Green Software Foundation (GSF) represents an industry effort, led by Microsoft, focused on software that runs on personal computers. Notable examples include carbon-aware distribution of updates and carbon-aware scheduling of operating system tasks (including a carbon-aware browser) [44].

For large distributed infrastructures (both public clouds and research infrastructures), time and geographic load planning according to current conditions with a focus on reliability and availability is an essential function. In 2023, Google published its carbon-based load management platform [45], CERN held a workshop focused on the topic in 2024. Google is active in popularizing the benefits in case of extreme events (weather, energy crisis). Existing works in scheduling are typically focused on use cases related to ML loads as [46]. A fundamental factor is the design of scientific workflows, which is usually not in the hands of the research infrastructure. Involvement of scientific users can have a major impact on the efficiency of optimization, specifically for scheduling this can be information about the nature of the tasks in terms of energy consumption (CPU vs IO bound) and priority. Work towards addressing this issue focuses not only on reporting and feedback, but also on the division of responsibilities between infrastructure and scientific users [47].

4.3 Energy-Efficient Resource Management and Workflow Scheduling in Cloud and Data Centers

A number of strategies have been investigated in both industry and academia to lower energy consumption in cloud and data center environments. These methods fall under the following general categories:

1. Resource Scheduling using Heuristics and Rules The application of rule-based and heuristic-based resource allocation is one of the classic resource allocation methods. In determining when to up or downscale resources, such systems apply predetermined rules, i.e., CPU utilization over a given

percentage threshold. Example: By consolidating workloads onto fewer active servers and favouring energy conservation, Power-Aware Best-Fit Decreasing (PABFD) is more sophisticated than classic bin-packing approaches.

Limitations: These methods are easy to use and quick to apply but not easily adaptable to different workloads.

2. Optimization Based on Reinforcement Learning Reinforcement learning (RL), in which an AI agent learns an appropriate scaling policy through interaction with the system, has been investigated recently for cloud resource management. Agents that dynamically distribute resources in response to real-time workload fluctuations have been trained using Deep Q-Networks (DQN) and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO).

Benefits: By continuously adjusting to demand and reducing wasteful energy use, it can outperform rule-based approaches.

Difficulties: Needs a lot of processing power and training data to achieve convergence.

3. Consolidation of Energy-Aware Virtual Machines (VMs) By strategically placing virtual machines on fewer real machines, VM consolidation strategies seek to reduce the number of active servers. These approaches are based on moving workloads from unproductive servers to other servers and shutting down the idle ones is known as "live migration of virtual machines." Dynamic voltage and frequency scaling. (DVFS) is a technique for dynamically modifying processor frequency in order to lower power consumption. One such method is Google's Borg System, which effectively distributes workloads throughout data centers while implementing energy-conscious regulations.

4. Using Edge Computing and Fog Computing to Reduce Power Consumption Edge computing delegates particular workloads to devices that are in proximity to users (for example, local edge nodes or IoT gateways) rather than keeping all processing in large data centers. This saves energy expenses by keeping use of the cloud to a minimum and reducing distant transport of data. As a case in point, fog computing reduces use of large data centers by shifting workloads to neighbouring resources.

Challenges: Effective allocation of tasks demands strong orchestration strategies.

5. Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) and Serverless Models Only when a function is called is serverless computing dynamically provisioning resources. This realizes huge energy savings in that it avoids having to constantly maintain servers in a live status. Examples of these are Google Cloud Functions and AWS Lambda.

Benefits: Workloads scale automatically without virtual machine management needs. Cons: Unsuitable for all applications, especially those that need to process in a stateful manner.

4.4 Task scheduling for HTC/Cloud/HPC computing resources

The most resource consuming part of computations in large research infrastructures is performed using HTC (computational grids), Cloud and HPC resources. The workflows typically consist in producing modelling data (Monte-Carlo simulations, digital twins) as well as processing large volumes of modelling data and data acquired in scientific experiments. The processed data is usually geographically distributed over multiple data centers to optimize the use of computing resources and avoid potential data losses. Treatment of large data volumes is done by execution of a large number of tasks (jobs) that are usually grouped together to form production campaigns. One production is processing a large portion of data of the same type applying the same processing algorithms.

The task schedulers are the services that are responsible for the massive task placement and execution in the distributed heterogeneous computing environments. The primary goal is to optimize the task

placement for the fastest turnaround and to make the most efficient usage of various computing resources. However, other optimization criteria can be included into the scheduling algorithms.

The DIRAC Workload Management System (WMS) is a smart task scheduler in a distributed computing environment [48]. It was developed for the LHCb experiment at CERN and is now used by multiple scientific communities around the world. In particular, the EGI Workload Manager service employs the DIRAC software. The scheduler architecture is based on the concept of pilot jobs and consists of the following components:

- a registry of available sites where their metrics and connection details are collected;
- a central Task Queue service to which the user jobs are submitted;
- pilot factories specific for each computing resource type;
- pilot jobs running on worker nodes and forming together with the central Task Queue a scalable distributed workload management system.

Pilot jobs are sent to various computing centers using appropriate protocols and credentials. They make reservations of computing resources (slots in batch systems or VMs in the cloud sites) that will be available for the scheduler service. Pilot jobs collect precise descriptions of their respective computing resources and present it to the Matcher service interface of the central Task Queue which is choosing one of the waiting jobs suitable for execution on the worker node. The pilot job receives the user task and steers its execution on the worker node, reports its status and uploads the results to storage systems where they are made available for the users.

The DIRAC WMS is well suited for the optimization of massive computational workflows to minimize the overall power consumption and to take into account other metrics characterizing computing resources at various sites:

1. The pilot jobs make resources reservations with the knowledge of properties of user tasks currently available in the central Task Queue. Therefore, the reservations are made in the sites which have currently a spare capacity and are most optimal for the task execution. For example, data processing tasks trigger resource reservations on the sites close to storage systems hosting the required data. This minimizes the use of network resources for data transfers. Other site metrics defined by the GreenDIGIT project as well as more detailed job characteristics can be taken into account. The central Task Queue offers a global view of all the user payloads and allows for general optimization of the resource reservation for multiple user communities and multiple heterogeneous sites served by the WMS services.
2. The pilot jobs prepare and validate the execution environment before the actual job starts. This reduces considerably the user job failure rate preventing the waste of resources and energy.
3. The pilot jobs steer the user job execution on the worker nodes and monitor the exact consumption of CPU, memory, input/output traffic of the job processes. These data are communicated back to the users which allows them to precisely describe the properties of subsequent similar jobs which in turn will result in a more precise scheduling decision.
4. Pilots can detect malfunctioning jobs, e.g. stalled or overusing memory and CPU allocations, and stop them preventing the waste of resources and reducing useless power consumption.
5. The pilots can communicate with the hosting environment and collect detailed information about the worker nodes which can be used later while making resource reservations with better accuracy.
6. In the cases where pilots can interact with the hosting environment, they can trigger certain actions to minimize power consumption, for example, by reducing the CPU frequency while the user job is performing input/output operations.

DIRAC WMS registers resources consumption data, e.g. CPU, data transfers and many others in its Accounting subsystem. Other accountable data can be defined and registered, e.g. power-aware resources consumption metrics. This will allow to monitor and evaluate the effect of power-awareness augmented scheduling algorithms.

4.5 GPU Sharing and Scheduling

Although many energy-efficiency strategies in cloud and data center environments have historically focused on CPU- and VM-level optimization, the growing reliance on GPUs and other accelerators has introduced new scheduling challenges that are directly relevant to sustainability. In modern AI, simulation, and data-intensive workloads, inefficient GPU allocation can result in fragmented usage, underutilized resources, and avoidable energy waste. Accordingly, the state of the art is increasingly moving toward accelerator-aware scheduling approaches that incorporate partitioning, virtualization, sharing, and batching mechanisms to improve both utilization and energy efficiency. This shift is also reflected in modern cloud-native systems, where GPUs and other accelerators are increasingly treated as schedulable resources through mechanisms such as device plugins [49] and dynamic resource allocation [50].

Recent survey work on deep learning scheduling in GPU datacenters shows that accelerator allocation has become a first-class scheduling concern, with trade-offs involving throughput, latency, fairness, locality, and device efficiency all interacting at once [51]. In practice, this means that the sustainability of modern workflow execution depends not only on where jobs are placed, but also on whether accelerators are right-sized, shareable, and sufficiently utilized during execution. The broader point is that accelerator-aware scheduling is now part of green optimization rather than a niche concern limited to AI platforms [52] [53].

4.5.1 Scheduling Challenges of GPU Utilization

GPUs in AI, simulation, and data-intensive computing introduce scheduling challenges that are directly relevant to energy efficiency and sustainability. Unlike traditional CPU-oriented resource allocation, GPU scheduling must address coarse-grained allocation, workload heterogeneity, partial utilization, and the fact that inefficient use of accelerators can lead to avoidable energy waste even when performance remains acceptable. As a result, current state-of-the-art approaches increasingly focus on mechanisms that improve effective GPU utilization through partitioning, virtualization, sharing, and workload-aware execution strategies.

However, underutilized GPUs do not necessarily consume proportionally less power and may still draw substantial energy, meaning that coarse allocation alone does not ensure energy efficiency. Recent empirical work on GPU clusters identifies a recurring execution-idle state, in which GPUs remain at relatively high power despite low visible activity [51]. Across six GPU platforms, this state accounted for 19.7% of in-execution time and 10.7% of energy, making it non-trivial source of inefficiency in real clusters and keeping devices productively occupied over time. [54].

This insight aligns with broader observational and analytical work on GPU utilization in large environments. HPC-oriented analysis also shows that utilization patterns across accelerator workloads are often uneven, and that effective monitoring and scheduling need to capture more than just coarse allocation status. Underutilization should be treated as an energy management problem in its own

right, and scheduling policies should aim to reduce fragmentation, idle reservation, and mismatch between workload size and assigned accelerator capacity [55].

4.5.2 GPU Scheduling and Sharing Techniques

4.5.2.1 Hardware-level GPU Partitioning

A major step toward fine-grained GPU utilization is hardware-supported partitioning. NVIDIA's Multi-Instance GPU, or MIG [56] [57], allows a supported physical GPU to be split into multiple isolated GPU instances, each with dedicated compute and memory resources. NVIDIA describes MIG as enabling secure partitioning for multiple users or workloads while preserving hardware-level isolation, making it especially relevant for multi-tenant environments where many tasks do not require a full accelerator. MIG-based scheduling treats GPU partitioning as a mechanism for executing multiple tasks on isolated slices of the same physical accelerator [58]. In a sustainability context, MIG is important because it reduces the inefficiency of allocating an entire GPU to a workload that could run effectively on only a fraction of the device.

MIG is also increasingly integrated with container and virtualization ecosystems. NVIDIA's documentation notes support for MIG in Kubernetes environments [59] and in vGPU deployments [60], which means partitioned accelerators can now be incorporated into practical scheduling stacks rather than remaining only a hardware feature. However, MIG is not infinitely flexible as it relies on predefined partition profiles. Recent research shows that although MIG can reduce underutilization and improve throughput and energy efficiency, interference and mismatch between application needs and coarse-grained partition profiles may still remain [61]. MIG can improve utilization by better matching workload size to available accelerator capacity, especially when full-GPU allocation would otherwise strand resources [62]. At the same time, MIG introduces new scheduling constraints, including partition-profile selection, dynamic reconfiguration overhead, and potential interconnect bottlenecks [63] [64].

4.5.2.2 Virtualization-level Scheduling

From a virtualization perspective, GPU sharing is commonly implemented through either passthrough or vGPU mechanisms. In passthrough, a full physical GPU is assigned directly to a single virtual machine [65]. This typically provides strong isolation and near-native access, but it limits consolidation because the entire device becomes unavailable to other workloads even when it is only partially utilized. NVIDIA's documentation and platform guidance make clear that passthrough remains useful where full-device exclusivity is required, but it is not an efficient sharing model for mixed or fragmented demand [60].

By contrast, vGPU approaches enable multiple virtual machines to share a single physical GPU. This improves utilization and enables denser multi-tenant deployments, especially in cloud settings. Recent NVIDIA documentation also shows that the distinction between virtualization and hardware partitioning is now less rigid than before, because MIG-backed vGPU allows virtualized sharing on top of hardware-isolated GPU instances [66]. For a sustainability-oriented discussion, the important point is that vGPU and MIG-backed vGPU create additional ways to increase effective utilization and reduce stranded accelerator capacity, although they also introduce management complexity, compatibility constraints, and potential performance trade-offs depending on the workload.

4.5.3 GPU Scheduling and Sharing in Different Computing Environments

4.5.3.1 GPU Scheduling and Sharing in Cloud Environment

OpenStack Clouds and Virtual Machines

In OpenStack-based cloud environments, GPU scheduling and sharing are shaped by the tension between performance isolation and efficient multi-tenant utilization. One established approach is GPU passthrough [67], where a physical GPU is assigned directly to a virtual machine through technologies such as VFIO. A recent implementation study on an OpenStack platform reports that passthrough remains attractive for high-load computing because it preserves strong device control and high performance within the guest, but it also notes the associated complexity of configuration and deployment in production cloud settings [68]. This makes passthrough well suited to workloads that require near-exclusive accelerator access, yet relatively inflexible from a consolidation and sustainability perspective because partially used devices cannot easily be repacked across tenants.

More recent OpenStack accelerator management has moved beyond full-device assignment toward explicit support for virtual GPUs and accelerator life-cycle management. OpenStack Nova documentation describes vGPU support through mediated devices [69], allowing a single physical GPU to expose multiple virtual GPU devices to guest instances, while the Cyborg documentation [70] shows that OpenStack's accelerator framework supports both physical GPUs and vGPUs, with additional configuration needed to map vGPU types to physical PCI devices. This is important for green optimization because it gives the scheduler a finer allocation unit than whole-device passthrough and enables better packing of mixed-demand workloads, especially where tenants do not require the full compute and memory capacity of a dedicated GPU.

Recent systems research suggests that compatibility and isolation remain central to making shared GPU execution practical, which is directly relevant to VM-based cloud environments where tenant separation cannot be sacrificed for efficiency alone [71]. Taken together, these developments suggest that GPU management in OpenStack clouds is evolving from simple whole-device assignment toward more flexible virtualized sharing. The sustainability benefit, however, depends on whether the scheduler can avoid fragmentation, over-allocation, and poor workload matching while preserving predictable performance predictability.

Kubernetes and Containerized Environments

In containerized environments, GPU scheduling has become increasingly important because many AI and data-processing workflows are now orchestrated through Kubernetes rather than only through traditional virtual machines or HPC batch systems. Kubernetes provides a stable device plugin framework that allows vendors to advertise GPUs and other accelerators to the scheduler, and its official scheduling documentation now treats GPUs as standard consumable resources within cluster orchestration [72]. This shifts GPU allocation from ad hoc operational practice into a more formal scheduling layer. At the same time, GPU sharing increasingly relies on orchestration-level mechanisms such as time-slicing and MIG-aware exposure in Kubernetes, making container-level GPU scheduling both a resource-efficiency opportunity and a systems-integration challenge [73].

In practice, however, efficient sharing requires more than merely exposing GPUs to Kubernetes. NVIDIA's cloud-native guidance describes several sharing approaches, including time-slicing, MIG-based partitioning, and operator-supported management. Their technical guidance explicitly frames these mechanisms as methods to improve GPU utilization in Kubernetes clusters, which is directly

relevant to energy efficiency. More recent Kubernetes developments around Dynamic Resource Allocation further show that the ecosystem is moving toward richer device-sharing and claim-based resource models for accelerators, making fine-grained scheduling increasingly feasible [50]. However, practical accelerator sharing in Kubernetes also requires not only partitioning technologies but also orchestration support capable of handling static or dynamic slice allocation [74].

At the same time, this layer introduces practical complexity. NVIDIA's operator documentation notes that mixed environments with full GPUs and MIG slices can present operational and scheduling issues under certain conditions. That shows that accelerator-aware scheduling is not only a question of whether sharing is possible, but also whether it remains reliable, observable, and manageable at scale in production-grade systems [75].

4.5.3.2 GPU Scheduling and Sharing in HPC

In HPC environments, GPU scheduling and sharing are shaped by a different set of priorities than in general-purpose clouds. HPC schedulers must preserve high performance, predictable runtime behaviour, and low interference for tightly coupled scientific applications, while also improving the utilization of increasingly scarce and energy-intensive accelerator resources. Recent large-scale analysis of GPU workloads on Perlmutter, using Slurm job metadata together with DCGM telemetry, shows that inefficiencies in HPC are not limited to simple idle time [76]. It also identifies that spatial and temporal imbalance in utilization and explicitly argues that these patterns provide a foundation for future scheduling improvements such as better load balancing and more adaptive allocation strategies.

Scheduling research on MIG reinforces this direction. For example, [58] studies moldable task scheduling on multi-instance GPUs and shows that partition-aware scheduling must reason jointly about instance size and execution time, rather than treating MIG as a static resource feature. IBM's work on dynamic repartitioning likewise frames MIG-enabled scheduling as a way to reduce energy consumption and tardiness for AI/ML workloads by adapting GPU partitions over time [64]. These works are especially relevant to HPC because they move from static resource reservation toward adaptive accelerator management, which is increasingly necessary as scientific workloads blend simulation, analytics, and AI components.

The recent study on sustainable GPU sharing in scientific workflows evaluates multiple execution scenarios and analyses their effects on performance, energy, and carbon emissions, showing that sharing decisions can no longer be treated as purely performance-oriented scheduling choices [77]. In parallel, current systems research on co-locating inference and training or on adaptive GPU sharing shows that the benefits of sharing depend on workload compatibility and the scheduler's ability to control contention [78]. For HPC centers, this means that GPU sharing is most promising where the scheduler has sufficient observability into job behaviour and where policies can distinguish between tightly coupled jobs requiring exclusivity and smaller or phase-varying jobs that can safely share a device or occupy isolated partitions of it.

Operationally, this also aligns with current HPC practice around Slurm and accelerator telemetry. Recent work analysing VASP GPU workloads using Slurm historical logs and DCGM metrics further shows that efficient utilization and power awareness are becoming critical as GPU demand grows in HPC [79]. This suggests that GPU scheduling in HPC is increasingly moving toward a telemetry-informed model: the scheduler is not only assigning devices, but also using utilization and power signals to refine future placement, sharing, or partitioning decisions. In this sense, GPU scheduling and sharing in HPC

should be understood as an emerging part of sustainable resource management rather than only a throughput optimization problem.

4.5.3.3 GPU Scheduling and Sharing for AI Workloads

Another important direction is workload batching, especially for inference-serving and AI-oriented workloads. Dynamic batching aims to aggregate multiple requests so that the GPU processes them more efficiently, thereby improving occupancy and throughput. Dynamic batching is also increasingly treated as a practical mechanism for reducing energy per inference under suitable workload conditions. Recent experimental work evaluating dynamic batching in GPU-oriented inference environments reports that batching strategies can influence both energy consumption and latency, with the best outcomes depending on model type, request pattern, and operating configuration [80]. This matters because it shifts the focus from static allocation to workload-aware adaptation at runtime.

The same point appears in recent discussions of large language model inference. Work on inference energy considerations notes that continuous batching helps mitigate underutilization by replacing completed requests with new ones, reducing idle compute accumulation [81]. At the same time, recent optimization literature continues to emphasize that lower latency does not automatically mean lower energy, and that multi-objective trade-offs remain central. In other words, batching is not simply a throughput trick; it is part of utilization-aware green scheduling when energy, responsiveness, and service quality must be balanced together [82].

5 Metrics for Energy Efficiency of Network and 5G Infrastructure

5.1 Metrics Collection and Management of IoT Environments

5.1.1 Trends in Energy Efficiency and Metrics Collection in IoT Environment

This section contains an executive summary of the trends, available solutions and current considerations, that are given in terms of IoT energy consumption optimisation.

During the past years, the need for interconnected IoT devices was strongly intensified, which also triggered exponential increments in the user data demands [83]. In such way, escalated interest in IoT energy efficiency raised from the research community as well. With IoT devices being deployed across diverse sectors such as smart cities, healthcare, vehicular networks and industrial automation, the cumulative energy footprint is becoming a critical concern. It is worth noting that there is huge variation in the characteristics and the capabilities of the IoT devices, indicatively ranging from simplistic sensors (e.g. temperature, humidity), smart devices (e.g. watches) to high performance telecommunication devices (e.g. IEEE 802.11ah, LoRa, NB-IoT). Thus, there are already approaches for IoT devices / networks, that intend to lower the power consumption and improve the energy efficiency along different parts of the continuum (IoT Sensor Network, Far Edge, Near Edge and Cloud), as depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9. GreenDIGIT high-level architecture for optimisation.

Energy-efficient communication protocols like Low Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN), e.g., IEEE 802.11ah, LoRa and NB-IoT, are gaining traction for long-range, low-power connectivity. Specifically, in in such type of networks the potential optimisations can be divided into the 4 major categories across the continuum mentioned above.

IoT Sensor Network (Device Layer - Things Layer)

This layer consists of the actual IoT hardware, which is deployed to create the device/ sensor networks. As mentioned above, IoT devices span multiple categories from simplistic sensors (e.g. environmental, motion, industrial sensors and smart wearables) to advanced communication & network devices (e.g. short/long range telecommunication transceivers). The former hardware category is mainly utilized to collect measurements, as the latter to deploy networks and exchange information (data, applications etc.). Additionally, this layer contains the hardware that is used to monitor useful metrics of the IoT ecosystem (e.g. smart meters for energy consumption).

Far Edge (Edge Computing Layer)

This part of the continuum typically contains the companion devices like Single-Board Computers (Raspberry PI, Nvidia Jetson, Intel NUC etc), that are utilized to host the IoT network devices and/or sensors mentioned on the previous category. The companion devices offer in many cases, enough computational power to locally process measurements gathered and exchanged information among the IoT sensor network. In such a way, reduced latency and energy consumption optimisations may accrue. Of course, based on the IoT network architecture (Infrastructure, mesh etc.) which is deployed at each application scenario, these devices may also have different networking roles, such as Access Points (APs), Stations (STAs), Relay nodes and Gateways (GWs).

Near Edge / CDN (Network Layer)

Following the previous two layers, Near Edge (often via content delivery networks) mainly consists of edge gateways, servers and fog computing nodes. These entities are typically placed geographically closer to the user compared to the cloud and provide distributed computing and storage capabilities. The main scope of this layer is to offload computational tasks that can't be executed from Far Edge devices (like Raspberry Pi), while in parallel larger round-trip times to / from Cloud are eliminated. Typical processes that are ported for execution at this point, may include but not limited to more demanding data analysis compared to those performed at the Far Edge. This layer enhances the performance, scalability, and security of IoT applications by caching data closer to end devices and minimizing in many cases unnecessary communication between IoT endpoints and cloud infrastructure.

Cloud

Finally, this layer involves centralized Cloud infrastructures that intend to execute big data processing, Artificial Intelligence (AI) model training and host long-term data storage. Through the training of complex Machine Learning (ML) models, Cloud-based orchestration overall IoT continuum can be achieved. This includes techniques such as, workload allocation, virtualization / containerization and dynamic resource scaling.

Starting from IoT sensor networks design considerations (utilizing low-power IoT devices, harvesting solar energy and reducing transceiver operational times etc), up to sophisticated ML correlated decisions (workload allocation, virtualization etc) on the Cloud side. Below, there is an executive summary for some research approaches correlated with the topics mentioned.

5.1.2 EELAS

Initially, the authors in [84], aim to optimize the deployment and execution of cloud-native ML workloads across the cloud-to-things continuum by balancing energy efficiency and latency constraints. The key contributions of this research approach can be summarized as follows:

- **Multi-Level Scheduling Algorithm:** Optimally distributes ML workloads across IoT, edge, and cloud resources to reduce energy usage while meeting latency constraints.
- **Minimizing energy consumption:** Achieves cloud-to-things continuum energy consumption minimization, when deploying workloads.
- **QoS-Aware Resource Allocation:** Dynamically allocates CPU resources based on real-time demand, ensuring energy-efficient operation without sacrificing performance.

It is worth noting that the scheduling problem is formulated as Integer Linear Programming (ILP) and then, a less complex heuristic algorithm that allows the efficient allocation of resources within the continuum is being developed. It is worth noting that, the developed approach is being evaluated through several extensive testbed scenarios. The experimental results highlight performance improvements in energy efficiency of over 41.8% and compared to the off-the-shelf Kubernetes scheduler.

5.1.3 Study on Energy Consumption Optimization Scheduling for IoT

Following, the authors in [85] deal with the IoT scheduling energy costs themselves (communication costs). The list of this work's contributions is given below:

- **Energy Loss Optimization Scheduling / Multi-Objective Model:** Develops a mathematical model to balance energy consumption and scheduling efficiency in IoT devices. This is achieved through a multi-objective fuzzy optimization algorithm which simplifies the decision-making process.
- **Idle Time Optimization for IoT Device Scheduling:** The algorithm searches for the idle time of the device and optimizes the device scheduling energy consumption model to reduce the overall energy consumption of the device scheduling in the IoT environment.

The authors consider and formulate the mathematical problem as a constrained multi-objective optimization problem, and they use fuzzy mathematics to solve it. Specifically, they set as goals, initially to minimize the total energy consumption in IoT scheduling, by simultaneously minimizing the scheduling time as well. Through MATLAB simulations, the authors showcase higher modelling accuracy and better energy saving effects, compared to "traditional" methods examined.

5.1.4 IoT-enabled Smart Energy Management Device for Optimal Scheduling of Distributed Energy Resources

Additionally, the authors in [86] propose the development of a Smart Energy Management Device (SEMD) designed for real-time optimization of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) in consumer-end energy management. The device operates through three key modules: data preprocessing, forecasting, and optimization. By leveraging machine learning models (Linear Regression, XGBoost, and LSTM), SEMD provides accurate load demand and energy generation predictions, enabling efficient scheduling of DERs such as rooftop PV, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) enabled Electric Vehicles (EVs). The key contribution of this approach can be summarised as follows:

- **Development of SEMD:** A portable IoT-based Smart Energy Management Device with robust software and hardware architecture for real-time energy management is being developed.
- **Machine Learning Forecasting:** Integration of ML-based models (LR, XGBoost, LSTM) to enhance energy demand, PV generation, and price forecasting accuracy.

- **Experimental Validation:** Proof-of-Concept testing on real-world energy consumers, demonstrating economic benefits and grid reliability improvements.

The authors consider and formulate the mathematical problem as a Mixed Integer Non-Linear Programming (MINLP) model with the objective of minimizing energy costs for consumers while maximizing the utilization of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), such as rooftop PV, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), and Electric Vehicles (EVs).

5.1.5 IoT Correlated Metrics

The current survey on energy consumption trends and practices, reveals that the energy efficiency / optimisation, can be characterized as a complex problem to tackle on the IoT environments. There are available approaches that consider some, or all the parts of the IoT continuum, and by providing different outcomes / monitoring solutions. Some common techniques found on the literature include but are not limited to energy-aware task scheduling, adaptive power management, optimised data transmission strategies and network optimisations. Focusing now more on the pure IoT part of the continuum (IoT Sensor Network & Far Edge), some power and network correlated metrics that can be taken into consideration are the following.

- **IoT Device / Sensor Power Consumption Metrics:** This includes the *average power consumption for idle, receive and transmit states* of the wireless adapter (where applicable to be measured). As the IoT Device / Sensor is attached to the Far Edge Device, through short-range local connections like serial (USB, pins etc.), in most of the cases there is no need to measure the data transmission and processing overhead for transferring the measurements. However, the large variety on the connection types given for the IoT devices (USB, pins, Hat etc.), increases the complexity or makes it impossible in some cases to measure the energy consumption on the device itself with appropriate hardware. In some cases, energy consumption measurement through software, or based on reference values, are the only available solutions.
- **Far Edge Device Power Consumption:** This part includes the power consumed during local data processing and before deciding to port them to the next parts of the continuum (Near Edge and Cloud). Thus, the *local data processing energy consumption (e.g. CPU)* can be measured and noted either through software or hardware components (depending on the device). Additionally, depending on the network connection (wired / wireless), it may be also useful to measure the *energy consumption required to transfer data to Near Edge and/or at the Cloud*, which may help in decision making to forward the data for further processing.

Additionally, some further metrics that are not directly relevant to energy consumption, but may affect it in some ways are the following:

- **Wireless Network Efficiency Metrics:** Specifically, for the IoT protocols, most of them operate under the use of the unlicensed spectrum (some exceptions may include protocols like NB-IoT). Thus, in these wireless environments there is always the case of performance uncertainty, as there is no control both number and the type (same or different protocol coexisting in the same frequencies) of contending wireless devices. Thus, in some cases it is useful to retrieve and capture networking metrics, such as *latency and available throughput* with the neighbour nodes. These measurements may also be useful for the decisioning / scheduling, load balancing, or to be compared with potential user constraints for served applications.
- **Energy harvesting:** There are also cases for the IoT and Far Edge device, in which the use of batteries and solar panels are taken into consideration and applied. Therefore, in such cases, it

may be useful to consider and note the amount of *energy that can be collected* at each given time and utilized.

5.2 Metrics Collection and Management of 5G Environments

5.2.1 5G Observability Framework

This part describes the overall 5G state of the art and possible observability framework to be included in GreenDIGIT Digital Infrastructure.

5G state of the art has shifted its architecture towards containerization, where network services are being decoupled from the infrastructure and are divided into smaller elementary models called microservices or network functions. On one hand, this approach has led to a radically new technological framework offering multi-tenant flexibility well beyond classical software-defined environments; on the other side, it posed more than a concern on environmental sustainability.

Studies have shown that the energy consumption of the infrastructure deployed for 5G is much higher with respect to its initial design [1]-[4]. Also, the energy consumption is a performance index of only the infrastructure layer, and it is not propagated to the upper 5G network providers and vertical applications. This means that the vertical stakeholder does not understand the impact on the resource and energy consumption, while infrastructure providers can easily adopt sophisticated resource and power management strategies. Given this issue, it is essential to integrate observability and monitoring frameworks that propagate Key Performance Indexes to all the stakeholders.

Figure 10: Internal architecture of the observability framework

The observability framework is shown in Figure 10. As it can be seen, it is divided into following three components:

5.2.1.1 IDAF (Infrastructure Data Analytics Function)

It's the module responsible for exposing infrastructure related metrics. As illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, the IDAF is composed of five elements that provide metrics in a Prometheus-like format. cAdvisor and Kube State Metrics (KSM) offer insights into the Kubernetes cluster. cAdvisor, which is integrated into the kubelet (the main K8s agent responsible for managing pod deployments and ensuring the health of the K8s cluster), reports on the utilization of computing resources (e.g., CPU, memory, networking, etc.) for each container. KSM, on the other hand, is an

additional service that provides information on the state of various K8s objects (e.g., pods, nodes, replicaset, statefulsets, etc.).

NodeExporter and Scaphandre gather metrics related to the bare-metal servers. NodeExporter collects a wide range of hardware and kernel-related metrics, including server resource utilization (e.g., CPU, memory, networking, etc.). Scaphandre, on the other hand, reports on the power consumption of individual processes running on the server, including containers and VMs. It uses Intel's Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) counters and CPU time spent on each process to calculate power usage. Currently, Scaphandre only tracks CPU power consumption, and in some cases, DRAM controller usage, making it particularly reliable for processes that do not require GPUs, as the CPU is typically the primary power consumer.

Lastly, the Raritan exporter is responsible for reporting the power consumption of Raritan Power Distribution Units (PDUs).

All the above metrics are stored in a Prometheus database, which is accessible by the three functions (i.e., IDAF, MDAF, NWDAF). Prometheus serves as a time-series database that collects metrics, each consisting of a timestamp, value, and optional key-value labels.

5.2.1.2 MDAF (Management Data Analytics Function)

Combines metrics coming from both the infrastructure and the management, allowing to estimate the current and the future carbon/energy footprint induced to the computing and offloading resources in the edge-cloud continuum, and even the availability and the use of green energy sources and hardware offloading engines.

The MDAF is primarily composed of three main components: the metric collector, the analytics blocks (which can include more than one), and the exporter.

The metric collector uses the prometheus-api-client library to query the Prometheus instance and retrieve metrics from Scaphandre and cAdvisor. Its primary purpose is to collect data on the power consumption of each process and the resource utilization of each container. Additionally, it can identify metrics that are not associated with virtualized components—namely, kernel processes essential for the proper functioning of the server and the layers above it, such as the hypervisor and container orchestration platforms. We assume that without these virtualized components (e.g., a containerized 5G network running on K8s), the servers would be inactive. As a result, the power consumption of these kernel processes is considered the "embodied power consumption."

The analytics blocks consist of a set of modular algorithms designed for data processing. These include calculating the embodied power consumption of the virtualized components, enriching the metrics to address Scaphandre's limitation in acquiring container labels for unique identification, and, importantly, mapping the kernel-level power metrics sourced from the IDAF.

Finally, the exporter's purpose is to expose the newly generated metrics in a Prometheus-compatible format. It relies once again on the prometheus-api-client library to ensure compliance with the Prometheus format.

5.2.1.3 NWDAF (Network Data Analytics Function)

Conceived to acquire monitored data at the edge and the cloud part of the infrastructure and to produce and analyse added-value Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), like forecasts of NF workloads.

5.2.2 Connection to GreenDIGIT architecture

A possible solution is to integrate an observability framework to GreenDIGIT that is similar to the one proposed by 6Green Project. This framework allows to:

- retrieve energy consumption of hardware infrastructures
- break down the different contributions from any software instance/ microservice in the 5G infrastructure
- recombine these contributions to estimate the consumption levels ascribable to the virtual resources and artefacts consumed by upper level 5G stakeholders.

Figure 11 provide an illustration where the 6G observability framework can be integrated in GreenDIGIT multi-dimensional infrastructure defining the main data processing, data communication and workflow processing streams.

Figure 11: 5G observability framework and potential connection to GreenDIGIT architecture

In conclusion, there are different available practices, approaches and solutions, that are given in the literature and consider the energy consumption monitoring for the IoT to Cloud continuum. The ideal characteristics for the system under development, is to be hardware agnostic, providing thus support and measurements for different IoT vendors.

5.3 Metrics Collection and Management of Mobile Environments

The power consumption of mobile software has become a critical research area, as excessive power consumption directly impacts end-users by draining batteries, shortening their lifespan over time, and reducing device usability. Thus, energy inefficiencies can lead users to replace hardware more frequently, causing environmental impacts from both the produced e-waste, and the manufacturing of new hardware. This limitation affects both the personal devices of private individuals, and the fleets of devices managed by institutions, such as devices provided to employees performing field work.

Research infrastructure and scientists relying on mobile devices, for instance to study mobile software engineering or wireless networking, are also affected, as their device may be under high workload. This creates a compelling incentive for developers to understand and minimize the power usage of their software. Improving software power efficiency can be achieved by adopting new practices and habits as part of the development processes [87].

Those new routines include:

- Understanding the requirements and goals of the software before the development phase. This involves anticipating optimal software development options [88] [89] and carefully selecting power-efficient third-party libraries, as their power consumption can vary significantly, based on their design [90].
- Testing with environmental impact in mind, on a broader variety of devices to reduce the risk of software obsolescence [91] and identify abnormal consumption patterns during execution.
- Monitoring post-release applications to detect performance variations across environments and address disparities.

However, these power optimizations may conflict with other objectives of the application, such as maintaining performance [92] [93] and security [94], making power efficiency a secondary priority in some cases.

Evaluating the relevance of a power modelling solution requires knowledge of the device's actual power consumption, which serves as the ground truth for validating power model estimations. However, while hardware performance counters are exposed by traditional computer processors [95], they are not included in smartphones' *System-on-Chip* (SoC). Thus, the power usage of mobile devices is often assessed at the battery level, either by integrating a power meter between the battery and the device, or by relying on programmatically available battery charge indicators [96]. However, physical measurement of smartphone power consumption is often impractical due to the increasing trend of non-dismountable design, such as batteries being glued to the casing. Therefore, the overall battery charge is largely used to assess or predict the power efficiency of software, such as mobile applications [97], code snippets [98] [99], or software design decisions [100]. However, such a metric encompasses the whole power usage of the device and offers only a coarse-grained granularity.

To tackle this limitation, since 2021, some Android devices have been equipped with a per-component power meter, the *On-Device Power Rails Monitor* (ODPM). These power meters are hardware probes placed downstream of the battery, directly before the component. ODPM can monitor the power usage of each of the twelve power rails of the device, with each rail powering one or many components. Available power rails include, for instance, each group of CPU cores, the network components, or the screen. However, this tool is still limited as few devices adopted it, and accurate data are only available in test environment, and not in production monitoring scenarios. For devices not equipped with ODPM, it remains possible to model per-component power-usage.

While developers may be interested in the energy efficiency of their software for optimization purpose, this indicator does not convert directly to an environmental impact. The environmental impact of software running on mobile device must account for its power usage and the electricity-mix of its users, but also on the power usage of networking infrastructure and servers used by this software. To comply with a life-cycle assessment approach, a share of the embodied impact of terminals, the networking infrastructures, and hosting infrastructures used by this software must also be imputed to this software. Such a quantification of environmental impacts allows for reporting

results or arbitrating between energy and network optimizations that may shift impacts between the terminals, the network, and the servers, or between different impact categories.³⁵

5.4 Metrics Collection and Management of Networks

The draft specification "Energy Metrics For Data Networks"³⁶ introduces a framework for evaluating and enhancing the energy efficiency of data networks. It emphasizes the growing importance of energy efficiency due to rising energy costs and environmental concerns, highlighting the significant impact of network operations on overall energy consumption. The document proposes standardized metrics to facilitate benchmarking and improvements in network energy performance. Key metrics include:

- **Power Consumption per Data Rate (PCDR):** This metric measures the power consumed relative to the data rate of network equipment, evaluating the energy efficiency of data transmission. The formula for PCDR is:

$$PCDR = \frac{\text{Power Consumption (W)}}{\text{Transmission Rate (Gbps)}}$$

where:

- **Power Consumption (W):** The average power in watts consumed by the specified link, group of links, or the network during the measurement period.
- **Transmission Rate (Gbps):** The average data rate in gigabits per second transmitted over the link, group of links, or the network during the same period.

For example, if a network link consumes 500 watts of power and has a transmission rate of 10 Gbps, the PCDR would be:

$$PCDR = \frac{500 \text{ W}}{10 \text{ Gbps}} \approx \frac{50 \text{ W}}{\text{Gbps}}$$

- **Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE):** PUE assesses the overall energy efficiency of a data center or facility, with a value closer to 1 indicating higher efficiency. The formula for PUE is:

$$PUE = \frac{\text{Total Facility Power}}{\text{IT Equipment Power}}$$

where:

- **Total Facility Power:** The total power consumed by the data center facility (including cooling, lighting, and other overhead).
- **IT Equipment Power:** The power consumed by the IT equipment (servers, storage, and network devices).

For instance, if a data center has a total facility power consumption of 1,000 kW and the IT equipment consumes 700 kW, the PUE would be:

$$PUE = \frac{1000 \text{ kW}}{700 \text{ kW}} \approx 1.43$$

³⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment. (2021). Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/2279 of 15 December 2021 on the Use of the Environmental Footprint Methods to Measure and Communicate the Life Cycle Environmental Performance of Products and Organisations.

³⁶ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-bogdanovic-green-energy-metrics/>

- **Network Equipment Energy Efficiency (NEEE):** NEEE evaluates the energy efficiency of network equipment based on work output per energy input, benchmarking devices to compare energy performance under specific workloads. The formula for NEEE is:

$$NEEE = \frac{\textit{Useful Work Output}}{\textit{Energy Input}}$$

where:

- **Useful Work Output:** The amount of work performed by the network equipment, such as data processed or transmitted.
- **Energy Input:** The total energy consumed by the network equipment during the measurement period.

For example, if a network device processes 5,000 gigabytes of data while consuming 250 kWh of energy, the NEEE would be:

$$NEEE = \frac{5000 \text{ GB}}{250 \text{ kWh}} \approx 20 \text{ GB/kWh}$$

- **Energy Proportionality Coefficient (EPC):** EPC measures how closely a system's energy consumption scales with its workload, where a value close to 1 indicates power consumption is highly proportional to workload. The formula for EPC is:

$$EPC = \frac{\textit{Power Consumption at Idle}}{\textit{Power Consumption at Full Load}}$$

where:

- **Power Consumption at Idle:** The power consumed by the system when it is idle.
- **Power Consumption at Full Load:** The power consumed by the system when operating at full capacity.

For instance, if a server consumes 100 W at idle and 200 W at full load, the EPC would be:

$$EPC = \frac{100 \text{ W}}{200 \text{ W}} = 0.5$$

The draft also underscores the importance of standardized testing conditions (STC) to achieve reliable and consistent results. Adhering to STC ensures fairness, objectivity, valid comparisons, and minimizes confounding variables, thereby supporting test validity and reliability. By defining these metrics and guidelines, the document aims to promote energy efficiency in network design and operation, enabling administrators and designers to identify opportunities for energy savings, optimize performance, and reduce the environmental impact of network operations.

6 Sustainability Aspects in Research Infrastructures for Experimental Research

6.1 Integrated Monitoring Systems and Resource Management

Research infrastructures (RIs) are complex cyber-physical systems composed of multiple interconnected subsystems, including cooling, computing, networking, power distribution units (PDUs), and facility management systems [101]. Each of these subsystems plays a critical role in ensuring the seamless operation of data centers. However, they are typically monitored and managed independently using different tools and teams, leading to significant challenges in achieving integrated optimization and sustainability by addressing energy efficiency aspects in holistic and multi-factor/multidimensional way.

For instance, tools like Prometheus are used for collecting node-level metrics from physical servers [102], while entirely separate tools manage and monitor virtual machines, and cooling systems. This siloed approach creates difficulties in aggregating and synchronizing monitoring data across subsystems due to the heterogeneity of data sources and platforms. Key challenges in individual monitoring include:

- **Heterogeneous Systems:** The diversity of tools and platforms used for monitoring different subsystems creates interoperability issues. These systems often lack standardized protocols for data exchange, complicating efforts to integrate them into a cohesive monitoring framework.
- **Data Synchronization:** Aggregating real-time metrics from disparate sources is challenging due to variations in data formats, sampling rates, and communication protocols. This lack of synchronization can lead to delays or inaccuracies in decision-making.
- **Scalability and Complexity:** As RIs grow in size and complexity, managing individual monitoring systems becomes increasingly resource-intensive. Scaling up monitoring solutions without compromising performance or accuracy remains a significant challenge.

To address these challenges, there is a growing need for integrated monitoring overlay systems that aggregate metrics from all subsystems in real-time. Such systems would enable:

- **Integrated/multi-factor Optimization:** By providing a unified view of all subsystems, operators can identify inefficiencies and optimize resource allocation across the entire infrastructure.
- **Real-Time Decision-Making:** Integrated systems allow for immediate responses to anomalies or changes in operational conditions, improving resilience. For instance, such systems allow dynamic workload distribution and optimized cooling strategies [103].

6.2 VREs for Experiment Reproducibility

Reproducibility is a fundamental principle of Scientific Research, ensuring that experiments can be validated, extended, and built upon by other researchers. However, challenges such as inconsistent data management, lack of computational resources, and difficulties in sharing workflows hinder reproducibility. A Virtual Research Environment (VRE) provides a comprehensive solution by integrating computational tools, data management frameworks, and collaborative platforms into a unified digital workspace.

6.2.1 The Role of VREs for Experiment Reproducibility

A VRE enables scientists to carry out, document, and share their research in a standardised and controlled environment. It offers:

- **Data Management and Provenance management:** VREs ensure that all input data, intermediate results, and final outputs are stored securely and linked through metadata standards like PROV-O (Provenance Ontology), ensuring transparency in data lineage.
- **Standardised Workflows:** throughout systems such as Jupyter Notebooks, Galaxy Workflows, or RStudio integrated into a VRE, users can define and execute analytical pipelines that can be replicated and reused across studies.
- **Collaboration and Version Control:** VREs support versioned repositories for code and datasets, allowing teams to track changes, reproduce analyses, and collaborate effectively through tools like Git and D4Science's workspace versioning.
- **FAIR Compliance:** VREs align with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles by providing persistent identifiers, standardised metadata schemas, and access control mechanisms to promote data sharing and reproducibility.
- **Computational Reproducibility:** By providing access to containerised computing resources (e.g., via Docker or Kubernetes), VREs allow researchers to execute analytical workflows in controlled environments, reducing dependency on specific local machine configurations.

6.2.1.1 Notable Implementations

D4Science VRE

D4Science is an advanced VRE platform that provides researchers with collaborative environments for data analysis, computational modelling, and experiment reproducibility. It supports various scientific domains, including social sciences, environmental sciences, marine research, and biodiversity studies.

Key features:

- **Cloud-based Execution:** Supports computational workflows using Jupyter, RStudio, and ShinyApps and external Cloud Providers such as Google Cloud Platform.
- **Provenance and Versioning:** Tracks execution history, ensuring that analyses can be reproduced.
- **FAIR-Compliant Data Management:** Integrates structured storage and metadata annotation for transparent data reuse.
- **Virtual Laboratories (VLabs):** Customisable environments tailored to specific research needs.

Galaxy Project VRE

Galaxy is a widely used VRE designed to enable reproducible computational research in life sciences and bioinformatics.

Key features:

- **Workflow Management:** Provides a user-friendly interface for creating and executing complex analysis pipelines.
- **Integrated Data Repositories:** Ensures persistent data storage and structured metadata management.
- **Transparent Reproducibility:** Every computational step is logged, and workflows can be easily re-run by other researchers.
- **Containerized Execution:** Uses Docker and Kubernetes to provide scalable and standardized computational environments.

6.2.1.2 Challenges and Future Directions

Despite significant advancements, challenges remain in ensuring long-term reproducibility, interoperability, and accessibility across VREs. Future efforts should focus on:

- **Interoperability across platforms:** enhancing standards for cross-platform workflow execution and integrating VREs with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other global research infrastructures.
- **Sustainable Computing and Energy Efficiency:** as VREs increasingly rely on cloud computing and distributed infrastructures, reducing the carbon footprint of computational workflows is becoming a critical priority.
- **Scalability and Performance:** Optimizing Cloud and HPC resources to efficiently handle large-scale datasets while maintaining responsiveness for real-time collaboration.
- **Persistent Identifiers and Digital Object Linking:** Strengthening reproducibility by ensuring datasets, workflows, and results are persistently citable, retrievable, and reusable across different research environments.

6.2.2 Tools for VRE Energy Efficiency Optimisation and Environmental Sustainability

6.2.2.1 Addressing Energy Efficiency and Environmental Sustainability in VRE Operation

Virtual Research Environments (VREs) are digital platforms that enable researchers to collaborate, share data, and conduct experiments in a virtualised environment [104]. VREs are increasingly critical for large-scale research infrastructures, although they pose environmental challenges—which GreenDIGIT should address. This section focuses on sustainable VREs, focusing on energy-efficient design approaches, resource optimisation, and the integrations to be made in GreenDIGIT's architecture. The main features of VREs are:

- **Experimentation:** VREs support the design, execution, and analysis of experiments.
- **Sustainability resource optimisation:** VREs can be designed and operated in an energy-efficient manner to minimise their environmental impact.
- **Customisation:** VREs can be customised to meet the specific needs of different research communities.
- **Data Management:** VREs provide tools for storing, managing, and analysing large datasets.

The EGI Foundation [105] is one of the prime examples that have taken steps in this direction with the EGI Notebooks tool³⁷. To address the environmental challenges posed by VREs, a range of tools and frameworks have emerged. These can be broadly categorised into metrics and KPI frameworks, which provide standardised ways to measure and understand the carbon intensity of software and infrastructure, and dashboard-like tools, which offer visualisations and real-time insights into energy consumption.

6.2.2.2 Metrics and KPI Frameworks and Tools

Green Metrics Tool³⁸ & SCI Specification³⁹: This framework defines Software Carbon Intensity (SCI) as a standardised metric (gCO₂eq per function unit) to quantify software carbon emissions. The Green

³⁷<https://notebooks.egi.eu/hub/>

³⁸<https://sci.greensoftware.foundation/>

³⁹<https://www.green-coding.io/products/green-metrics-tool/>

Metrics Tool is a developer-focused tool that implements the SCI specification. It functions by measuring the energy consumed by software during execution and converting it to carbon emissions using location-based or grid-average emission factors. Key components include energy meters, CPU utilisation trackers, and emission factor databases. Its unique characteristic is the focus on standardising software carbon measurement through the SCI specification, enabling comparability across different software systems.

EcoVisor [106]: EcoVisor operates as a software layer that virtualises energy systems, allowing applications to dynamically adapt to fluctuating clean energy availability. Functionally, it intercepts application energy requests and optimises them based on real-time clean energy supply data. Key components include energy supply forecasting modules, application energy demand models, and control algorithms that adjust application behaviour. Uniquely, EcoVisor enables carbon-aware application design by providing a software-defined interface to manage energy consumption in response to clean energy variability.

Cloud Carbon Footprint⁴⁰: This tool estimates cloud emissions by analysing cloud provider billing and usage data. It functions by connecting to cloud accounts (AWS, GCP, Azure) and processing billing exports to attribute energy consumption and associated emissions to specific cloud services. Key components include data connectors for each cloud provider, emission factor datasets, and aggregation/reporting modules. Its unique aspect is its focus on cloud environments and its provider-agnostic approach, offering a consolidated view of cloud carbon footprints across different platforms.

6.2.2.3 Dashboard Tools

CodeCarbon⁴¹: CodeCarbon is a Python library that instruments code to measure energy consumption and estimate carbon emissions. It functions by using software-based power meters to track CPU and GPU energy usage during code execution. Key components include runtime libraries, emission factor databases, and logging/visualisation capabilities. Its unique feature is its code-level integration and ease of use, allowing developers to directly measure and visualise the carbon impact of their code.

Zeus⁴²: Zeus is a library specifically designed for deep learning energy measurement and optimisation. Functionally, it provides tools to profile the energy consumption of DL workloads and apply optimisation techniques. Key components include energy profilers, optimisation algorithms (e.g., model pruning, quantisation), and reporting dashboards. Uniquely, Zeus focuses on the specific energy challenges of AI/ML, offering targeted solutions for this domain.

Keit⁴³ (from Aknestic): KEIT monitors Kubernetes clusters to provide insights into the environmental impact of containerised applications. It functions by collecting data from Kubernetes APIs and infrastructure metrics to estimate energy consumption and carbon emissions of workloads running in the cluster. Key components include data collectors, a metrics processing engine, and visualisation dashboards. Its unique aspect is its focus on Kubernetes environments, offering visibility and management of carbon emissions in modern containerised deployments.

⁴⁰<https://www.cloudcarbonfootprint.org/>

⁴¹<https://codecarbon.io/>

⁴²<https://github.com/ml-energy/zeus>

⁴³<https://aknestic.com/keit/>

6.2.3 Outcomes and Recommendations for GreenDIGIT and Connection with its Architecture

Metrics and KPI Frameworks and Tools

- **Green Metrics Tool & SCI Specification**
 - Outcomes for GreenDIGIT: Standardised measurement of software carbon intensity within GreenDIGIT services.
 - Recommendations for GreenDIGIT: Adopt SCI as a core KPI; integrate Green Metrics Tool into software development. - Into Notebooks
 - Connection to GreenDIGIT Architecture: Provides metrics for sustainability within the computing layer.
- **EcoVisor**
 - Outcomes for GreenDIGIT: Carbon footprint reduction through dynamic workload scheduling based on renewable energy availability.
 - Recommendations for GreenDIGIT: Investigate integration as an energy management layer; configure for GreenDIGIT energy data and renewable energy feeds. - Into DIRAC
 - Connection to GreenDIGIT Architecture: Energy management within computing and networking layers.
- **Cloud Carbon Footprint**
 - Outcomes for GreenDIGIT: Clear understanding of carbon emissions from GreenDIGIT's cloud resource usage.
 - Recommendations for GreenDIGIT: Deploy to monitor cloud emissions; set up cost centre tagging for accurate attribution.
 - Connection to GreenDIGIT Architecture: Infrastructure level monitoring and reporting for cloud resources.

Dashboard-like Tools

- **CodeCarbon**
 - Outcomes for GreenDIGIT: Researcher awareness of code-level carbon footprint; encourages energy-efficient coding practices.
 - Recommendations for GreenDIGIT: Promote use amongst researchers; provide integration guidance.
 - Connection to GreenDIGIT Architecture: User/application-level tool for carbon monitoring.
- **Zeus**
 - Outcomes for GreenDIGIT: Energy efficiency optimisation for AI/ML workloads within GreenDIGIT.
 - Recommendations for GreenDIGIT: Recommend for AI/ML research; provide specialised support. – Into AI4EOSC
 - Connection to GreenDIGIT Architecture: Specialised profiling for AI/ML workloads within the computing layer.
- **Keit (from Aknostic)**
 - Outcomes for GreenDIGIT: Insights into energy consumption of containerised applications in Kubernetes.
 - Recommendations for GreenDIGIT: Deploy to monitor Kubernetes clusters (if applicable); configure for GreenDIGIT infrastructure.
 - Connection to GreenDIGIT Architecture: Infrastructure level monitoring for Kubernetes deployments.

Considering these two main categories within a VRE approach can effectively promote sustainability within the researcher workflow, abstracting technical complexity whilst delivering actionable and insightful data.

6.3 Experiment Reproducibility Metadata Formats

Experiment reproducibility is a cornerstone of scientific research, ensuring that results are verifiable, transparent, and reusable. Metadata plays a crucial role in this process, as it provides structured descriptions of experimental setups, execution parameters, and outcomes. Various metadata formats and frameworks have been proposed to facilitate the organization, sharing, and automation of experimental results, particularly in computer science and networking research. This document explores the key metadata formats that support experiment reproducibility, focusing on RO-Crate, FAIR principles, and structured experimental workflows.

6.3.1 RO-Crate: A Standardized Metadata Format

One of the leading approaches to structuring experiment metadata is **RO-Crate**, an initiative designed to encapsulate research artifacts and their associated metadata in a machine-readable and human-readable format. RO-Crate follows the principles of the **FAIR data movement**, which emphasizes **Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability**.

RO-Crate provides the following key features:

- **Standardized Packaging:** Research artifacts (such as experiment scripts, raw data, and analysis results) are stored in a structured format.
- **Rich Metadata Annotations:** Each experiment file or dataset is associated with metadata that describes its authorship, affiliations, software dependencies, hardware specifications, and execution environment.
- **Integration with Open Repositories:** RO-Crate packages can be deposited in platforms such as **Zenodo**, ensuring long-term accessibility and referenceability.
- **Machine-Readable Descriptions:** By using JSON-LD (a linked data format), RO-Crate enables automated processing, making it easier to validate, reproduce, and extend previous experiments [107].

Ro-Crate has three key use cases that potentially can enhance reusability in research infrastructure experiments. These use cases - Autosubmit, COMPSs, and KEDO Data Lake - demonstrate how Ro-Crate facilitates experiment management, workflow execution, and data sharing.

- **Autosubmit:** Autosubmit is a workflow management tool designed to orchestrate and automate complex climate and weather simulations across different computing platforms. By leveraging Ro-Crate, Autosubmit ensures that experiment metadata, execution environments, and dependencies are captured in a structured format. This enhances reproducibility and enables researchers to share and reuse experiment configurations effortlessly.
- **COMPSs:** COMPSs (COMP Superscalar) is a programming framework that simplifies the development and execution of parallel applications in distributed computing environments. Ro-Crate integration allows COMPSs workflows to be packaged with all necessary metadata, input data, and execution logs. This ensures seamless portability and reuse of computational experiments across diverse research infrastructures.
- **KEDO Data Lake:** The KEDO Data Lake provides a scalable solution for storing and managing large datasets used in scientific research. By adopting Ro-Crate, KEDO enables structured metadata

annotation, making datasets more discoverable, interoperable, and reusable. This facilitates seamless data sharing across research communities while maintaining data provenance and integrity.

By adopting Ro-Crate in these use cases, research infrastructures can achieve greater experiment reproducibility, streamline workflow management, and foster collaboration through standardized metadata-driven practices.

6.3.2 FAIR Principles and Metadata for Reproducibility

The **FAIR principles** provide a foundational framework for metadata structuring. These principles emphasize:

- **Findability:** Each experiment dataset should be uniquely identified and indexed in searchable repositories.
- **Accessibility:** Data should be retrievable using open protocols, with metadata remaining accessible even if the data itself is restricted.
- **Interoperability:** Metadata should use standard vocabularies to enable integration with other datasets.
- **Reusability:** Experiments should include detailed documentation, licensing information, and methodological descriptions to facilitate replication.

To align with these principles, reproducibility platforms such as **plain orchestrating service (pos)** and **SLICES** have adopted structured experiment workflows that enforce metadata generation at various stages of an experiment [108] [109].

6.3.3 Experiment Workflow and Metadata Structure

A well-defined experimental workflow consists of multiple stages, each requiring specific metadata:

1. **Setup Phase:**
 - Metadata includes hardware configurations, installed software, dependencies, and initial conditions.
 - RO-Crate and FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) are used to document the environment.
2. **Measurement Phase:**
 - Metadata includes experiment parameters (e.g., network topology, data sampling rates), raw measurements, and logs.
 - Formats such as **Common Workflow Language (CWL)** enable structured execution and reproducibility.
3. **Evaluation Phase:**
 - Metadata includes processing scripts, statistical models, and visualization outputs.
 - Experimental outputs are structured in formats like **JSON or CSV**, with accompanying metadata ensuring clarity.
4. **Publication Phase:**
 - Metadata includes authorship, affiliations, funding sources, and dataset DOIs.
 - Platforms like **Zenodo and GitHub** support direct integration with structured metadata formats.

6.3.4 Metadata Tools and Integration

Several tools facilitate metadata generation and management for experiment reproducibility:

- **Jeppesen:** A tool used for capturing testbed hardware and network topology metadata.
- **RO-Crate-Py:** A Python library that automates the creation of RO-Crate packages for experiments.
- **LLDP (Link Layer Discovery Protocol):** Used for capturing network configurations dynamically.
- **Ansible, Puppet, and Chef:** Configuration management tools that automate experiment setup and documentation.

Metadata is essential for ensuring reproducible experiments, and frameworks like RO-Crate and FAIR principles provide a structured way to achieve this. By embedding metadata into every stage of an experimental workflow, researchers can improve transparency, facilitate collaboration, and enhance the longevity of scientific findings. Future developments in metadata standards will continue to bridge the gap between experiment execution and data management, ensuring seamless interoperability across research domains.

7 Sustainable Software Design Practices for Scientific Software

7.1 Software Sustainability Recommendations by Green Software Foundation

The Green Software Foundation (GSF)⁴⁴ offers several sustainable software design practices that can enhance energy efficiency in scientific software, particularly those focused on data processing, data analytics, and workflow optimization. These practices aim to reduce the carbon footprint of software applications by emphasizing energy efficiency, carbon awareness, and hardware optimization⁴⁵.

1. Energy-Efficient Algorithm Design: Optimizing algorithms to perform tasks more efficiently can significantly reduce computational resource usage. For scientific software, this involves selecting or designing algorithms that minimize computational complexity and energy consumption. Efficient algorithms not only speed up data processing and analytics but also lower energy usage, contributing to greener software solutions.

2. Resource Optimization and Virtualization: Efficient management of computational resources is crucial. Implementing virtualization techniques allows multiple applications to share the same hardware resources effectively, leading to better utilization and reduced energy consumption. For scientific workflows, this means consolidating tasks on fewer servers and leveraging cloud computing resources judiciously to optimize energy use.

3. Carbon Awareness in Computing: Designing software that is aware of its carbon emissions enables it to make informed decisions to minimize environmental impact. This includes scheduling intensive data processing tasks during periods when renewable energy sources are more available or when the carbon intensity of the power grid is lower. By aligning computational workloads with greener energy availability, scientific software can reduce its carbon footprint.

4. Efficient Data Management: Data storage and transfer consume significant energy. Implementing efficient data management practices, such as data compression and minimizing unnecessary data movement, can lead to substantial energy savings. For scientific applications dealing with large datasets, optimizing data handling reduces both processing time and energy consumption.

5. Sustainable Hardware Utilization: Selecting energy-efficient hardware and ensuring that software is optimized for the underlying hardware can lead to better performance per watt. This includes using processors and storage devices designed for low power consumption and high efficiency, which is particularly important in data-intensive scientific computations.

By integrating these practices into the development and deployment of scientific software, developers can enhance energy efficiency and contribute to environmental sustainability. The GSF provides

⁴⁴ <https://greensoftware.foundation/>

⁴⁵ <https://greensoftware.foundation/articles/10-recommendations-for-green-software-development>

resources⁴⁶ and guidelines⁴⁷ to assist in adopting these green software development practices, aiming to reduce the environmental impact of software systems across various domains.

7.2 The Software Carbon Intensity (SCI) Specification by Green Software Foundation

The **Software Carbon Intensity (SCI) Specification**⁴⁸, developed by the Green Software Foundation, provides a standardized methodology to calculate the carbon emissions associated with software systems. Its primary goal is to assist developers and organizations in making informed decisions to reduce the environmental impact of their software applications.

Overview of the SCI Specification:

The SCI metric quantifies the rate of carbon emissions per functional unit of a software system, expressed as:

$$\text{SCI} = (\text{E} \times \text{I}) + \text{M} / \text{R}$$

Where:

- **E:** Energy consumed by the software system.
- **I:** Carbon intensity of the energy source.
- **M:** Embodied emissions from hardware manufacturing.
- **R:** Functional unit representing the software's scale (e.g., per user, per transaction).

This formula encompasses both operational emissions (energy consumption and its carbon intensity) and embodied emissions (hardware production impact), normalized by the software's functional usage.

Applying SCI to Complex Scientific Software in Distributed Data Centers:

Scientific software often operates across multiple data centers, handling intensive data processing and analytics. Applying the SCI framework to such complex systems involves:

1. **Defining System Boundaries:**
 - **Scope Identification:** Determine which components of the distributed system contribute to carbon emissions, including computing nodes, storage units, and networking equipment.
2. **Measuring Energy Consumption (E):**
 - **Granular Monitoring:** Implement monitoring tools to capture energy usage data for each component across all data centers.
 - **Data Aggregation:** Consolidate energy consumption data to obtain a comprehensive view of the system's operational footprint.
3. **Assessing Carbon Intensity (I):**

⁴⁶ GitHub's Green Software Directory [online] <https://github.com/github/GreenSoftwareDirectory>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/Green-Software-Foundation/awesome-green-software>

⁴⁸ <https://sci.greensoftware.foundation/>

- **Regional Analysis:** Evaluate the carbon intensity of energy sources for each data center location, considering local energy grids and their reliance on renewable versus non-renewable sources.
 - **Temporal Factors:** Account for variations in carbon intensity due to time-of-use, as energy sources may shift throughout the day.
4. **Calculating Embodied Emissions (M):**
- **Hardware Inventory:** Document all hardware components, noting their manufacturing emissions.
 - **Lifecycle Assessment:** Estimate emissions based on hardware production, transportation, and expected lifespan.
5. **Determining the Functional Unit (R):**
- **Usage Metrics:** Define a functional unit that reflects the software's purpose, such as computations per second, data processed per hour, or user sessions.
6. **Computing the SCI Score:**
- **Integration:** Apply the SCI formula using the collected data to calculate the carbon intensity per functional unit.
 - **Continuous Monitoring:** Regularly update the SCI score to reflect changes in energy consumption, hardware upgrades, or shifts in workload distribution.

Challenges and Considerations:

- **Data Availability:** Accurate SCI calculation requires detailed energy consumption and carbon intensity data, which may not always be readily accessible, especially in public cloud environments. Collaborating with service providers to obtain this information is crucial.
- **Complexity of Distributed Systems:** The dispersed nature of scientific applications necessitates a coordinated approach to data collection and analysis across all operational regions.
- **Dynamic Workloads:** Fluctuations in computational demand can affect energy usage patterns, requiring adaptive strategies to maintain an accurate SCI assessment.

By systematically applying the SCI Specification, organizations can identify emission hotspots within their scientific software systems and implement targeted optimizations. This proactive approach not only aids in achieving sustainability goals but also promotes operational efficiency and cost savings.

7.3 Sustainable Architecture Design Practices by Cloud Providers

AWS and Microsoft Azure

The two leading cloud and Big Data services providers Amazon Web Services (AWS) and Microsoft Azure provide advanced resources and services to address the whole spectrum of requirements in designing, deploying and operating cloud based services spanning from front-end user services and large scale cloud based user focused services to advanced services that include IoT, sensor network, edge computing, data collection and management, and computation for data analytics and Generative AI services. The technologies used and offered by large cloud providers are advanced and are at the frontline of the technologies developments. Both cloud providers are committed to address the sustainability aspects of their infrastructure and services offered to their customers, providing also necessary design optimisation for customer applications supported by extensive monitoring and fine grained metrics together with services and resources control and management possibilities. Knowing

and understanding the technologies, solutions and tools provided by cloud providers are beneficial for effective applications and solutions development for digital Research Infrastructures, which are generically based on whole spectrum of IoT-edge-cloud continuum of technologies. However, due to Azure and AWS strong business orientation finding necessary and relevant technical information may be difficult. Presented in this section overview of the sustainability design principles and corresponding services formulated by Azure and AWS is intended to provide a guidance for developers of advanced cloud based scientific applications on using State of the Art technologies and architecture design principles, this is supported by references to necessary AWS and Azure resources for further study.

7.3.1 Microsoft Azure Sustainability Framework and Sustainability Design Principles

Microsoft's Azure Sustainability framework is a complex of architecture and design principles proposed by Microsoft Azure's Well-Architected Framework⁴⁹ aim to optimize software development, workflow execution, storage efficiency, and cloud resource usage to minimize carbon emissions and energy consumption. It provides a structured approach to reducing the environmental impact of cloud-based applications, focusing on energy-efficient software design, workflow optimization, storage management, and cloud resource utilization. By integrating carbon-aware computing principles, Azure enables developers and businesses to make more sustainable choices in how they design, deploy, and manage digital workloads.

A key principle in sustainable application design is minimizing unnecessary compute operations through optimized software architecture, microservices, and cloud-native execution models. Azure promotes event-driven serverless computing and containerized workloads, allowing applications to scale dynamically while reducing idle resource consumption. Developers are encouraged to use caching, optimize API calls, and structure applications to reduce processing overhead, ultimately lowering energy use and emissions.

Beyond application architecture, workflow optimization plays a critical role in sustainability. Azure enables carbon-aware scheduling, where AI-driven tools shift computational workloads to low-carbon energy periods or regions with cleaner energy grids. This approach is particularly effective for batch processing, machine learning training, and large-scale analytics, ensuring that intensive computations are performed with minimal environmental impact. Additionally, auto-scaling and adaptive resource allocation ensure that cloud resources are only used when needed, preventing over-provisioning and reducing overall energy waste.

Azure's approach to storage sustainability emphasizes efficient data management, leveraging tiered storage models to classify data based on usage frequency. By compressing files, reducing redundant storage, and implementing intelligent data retention policies, organizations can cut down on unnecessary storage-related energy consumption.

The efficient use of cloud computing resources is another cornerstone of Azure's sustainability strategy. By deploying workloads in regions powered by renewable energy, leveraging spot instances and burstable VMs, and using edge computing to minimize long-distance data transfers, cloud users can significantly reduce their carbon footprint. Serverless platforms and AI-driven workload

⁴⁹ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/well-architected/>

optimizations further enhance resource efficiency, allowing applications to dynamically adjust to demand without consuming unnecessary power.

In general, Azure's sustainability architecture provides a roadmap for building energy-efficient applications and optimizing cloud operations. By integrating carbon-aware computing, adaptive resource management, and sustainable storage strategies, organizations can lower emissions while maintaining high-performance digital services. Through business focused offering like Microsoft Cloud for Sustainability⁵⁰, businesses can track their impact in real-time and make data-driven decisions to move toward net-zero cloud operations. This is well presented in the Sustainability Guide⁵¹ that provides also useful information for making decision technology selection.

The following structured text summarise the main sustainability aspects addressed in the Azure Well-Architected Framework with related technologies and services available from Azure (including also reference to related blog articles).

1. Software and Application Design Principles for Sustainability⁵²

Microsoft advocates for a green software approach, which aligns with the Green Software Foundation's principles to ensure applications are developed with energy efficiency, carbon awareness, and hardware efficiency in mind.

- **Carbon Efficiency:** Applications should minimize resource consumption by using optimized infrastructure and cloud-native services, reducing unnecessary compute and memory overhead.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Developers should optimize code execution by reducing redundant processing, improving API efficiency, and implementing microservice architectures to allow independent scaling of application components.
- **Carbon Awareness:** Applications can be programmed to execute computationally intensive workloads during periods of low-carbon energy availability, leveraging Azure's regional carbon intensity tracking to schedule workloads dynamically.
- **Hardware Efficiency:** Software should be compatible with older devices to extend hardware lifecycles and avoid unnecessary hardware replacements.
- **Key Technologies:**
- **Microservices over Monolithic Design:** Enables scalable, event-driven applications that dynamically adjust to demand.
- **Server-side Rendering and Caching:** Reduces energy-intensive client-side processing by leveraging pre-rendered content and data caching techniques.
- **Cloud-native Design Patterns:** Implements serverless computing and containerization to efficiently utilize shared cloud resources.

⁵⁰ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/sustainability/cloud>

⁵¹ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/sustainability/sustainability-guide>

⁵² Design principles of a sustainable workload - <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/well-architected/sustainability/sustainability-design-principles>

2. Workflow Management for Energy Efficiency and Reduced Environmental Impact^{53 54}

Optimizing workflow execution is critical to reducing unnecessary computation and energy use. Microsoft emphasizes:

- Demand Shifting: Scheduling workloads to execute during periods of renewable energy availability reduces carbon emissions.
- Auto-scaling and Right-sizing: Dynamically adjusting compute resources based on demand prevents over-provisioning.
- Batch Processing During Low-carbon Periods: Computationally intensive tasks such as data analytics and AI model training should be scheduled when energy grids rely more on renewable sources.
- Adaptive Resource Allocation: Workloads should be migrated to Azure data centers with lower carbon intensity, ensuring optimal energy use.
- Deployment and Testing⁵⁵: Run integration, performance, load, or any other intense testing during low-carbon periods, Establish CPU and Memory thresholds in testing

Key Technologies:

- Azure Monitor and AI-driven Auto-scaling: Dynamically adjusts computing power to match workload demand.
- Azure Kubernetes Services (AKS) and Serverless Computing: Supports event-driven execution, reducing idle compute resource waste.

3. Storage Optimization for Sustainable Cloud Computing⁵⁶

Storage solutions play a significant role in cloud sustainability, and Microsoft's Azure Well-Architected Framework provides a structured approach to optimizing data storage and retrieval.

- Storage Tiering: Frequently accessed data should reside in hot storage, while cold or archive storage should be used for infrequent data access, reducing energy-intensive storage operations.
- Compression and Deduplication: Efficient data storage can be achieved by compressing large files and eliminating redundant copies, significantly reducing storage footprint.
- Retention Policies and Smart Backup Strategies: Data backups should be strategically planned to avoid storing unnecessary logs or redundant copies, minimizing storage-related energy consumption.
- Log Optimization: Cloud applications should log only necessary data and avoid excessive data retention that leads to increased storage and processing overhead.

Key Technologies:

- Azure Blob Storage with Hot/Cold/Archive Tiers: Enables energy-efficient storage classification.
- Microsoft Purview for Data Governance: Implements data retention policies to eliminate unnecessary storage use.

⁵³ Application design of sustainable workloads on Azure - <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/well-architected/sustainability/sustainability-application-design>

⁵⁴ Application platform considerations for sustainable workloads on Azure - <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/well-architected/sustainability/sustainability-application-platform>

⁵⁵ Testing considerations for sustainable workloads on Azure - <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/well-architected/sustainability/sustainability-testing>

⁵⁶ Data and storage design considerations for sustainable workloads on Azure – <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/well-architected/sustainability/sustainability-storage>

- Azure Monitor Logs and Compression Strategies: Reduces redundant log storage and optimizes log retrieval efficiency.

4. Cloud Computing Resource Utilization and Carbon Awareness (refer to previously linked blog articles)

Microsoft emphasizes efficient cloud resource utilization to lower energy consumption. Several strategies are recommended:

- Optimized Virtual Machines (VMs): Use auto-scaling and spot instances to prevent underutilized compute resources.
- Regional Carbon Intensity Awareness: Applications should be deployed in Azure regions where data centers use renewable energy, reducing the carbon footprint. Connected to Microsoft Emissions Impact Dashboard (EID)⁵⁷ to Microsoft Sustainability Manager (MSM)⁵⁸ instance
- Serverless and Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) Workloads: Instead of managing dedicated virtual machines, serverless computing allows resources to scale on-demand, reducing idle resource consumption.
- Edge Computing and Content Delivery Networks (CDNs): Reducing data transfers between cloud regions by caching content closer to users minimizes network-related emissions.

Key Technologies:

- Azure Spot VMs and B-Series Burstable Instances: Reduce carbon impact by using idle compute capacity.
- Azure Carbon-aware Scheduling and Low-carbon Data Centers: Enable region-based workload execution for sustainability.
- Azure Kubernetes Services (AKS) for Bin Packing: Optimizes VM utilization by grouping workloads efficiently.

Microsoft's Azure Sustainability Architecture provides a robust framework for organizations to reduce the carbon footprint of their cloud operations. By following sustainable application design principles, optimizing workflows, implementing storage best practices, and leveraging carbon-aware cloud computing, organizations can significantly improve their energy efficiency and environmental sustainability. The Microsoft Cloud for Sustainability platform offers real-time tracking and optimization tools that help companies achieve net-zero cloud computing operations, making energy-efficient cloud computing more accessible and scalable.

7.3.2 AWS Sustainability Design Principles of the AWS Well-Architected Framework

Amazon Web Services (AWS) has developed a Sustainability Pillar⁵⁹ as part of its Well-Architected Framework⁶⁰, providing best practices to reduce the environmental impact of cloud workloads. This framework focuses on software design principles, workflow management, storage optimization, and

⁵⁷ Measure your cloud carbon footprint with the Emissions Impact Dashboard for Microsoft 365 - https://techcommunity.microsoft.com/blog/microsoft_365blog/measure-your-cloud-carbon-footprint-with-the-emissions-impact-dashboard-for-micr/3144426

⁵⁸ Microsoft Sustainability Manager overview - <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/industry/sustainability/sustainability-manager-overview>

⁵⁹ Sustainability Pillar - AWS Well-Architected Framework - <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/wellarchitected/latest/sustainability-pillar/sustainability-pillar.html>

⁶⁰ AWS Well-Architected Framework - <https://aws.amazon.com/architecture/well-architected/>

efficient cloud resource utilization to help organizations build sustainable and energy-efficient cloud architectures. Below we summarise the AWS architecture design principles for sustainability with reference to AWS technology solutions and cloud services.

Software and Application Design for Sustainability

AWS emphasizes energy-efficient software development by encouraging organizations to optimize resource utilization, minimize redundancy, and use carbon-aware cloud computing. Applications should be designed with dynamic scaling, workload consolidation, and event-driven processing to reduce unnecessary resource consumption.

A key principle is maximizing utilization, ensuring that compute, storage, and network resources are fully utilized before scaling up infrastructure. AWS recommends using managed services, such as AWS Lambda for serverless execution and AWS Fargate for containerized applications, to minimize idle resource usage. Additionally, newer energy-efficient hardware options, such as AWS Graviton processors⁶¹ and AWS Inferentia AI chips⁶², enable higher performance per watt, reducing overall energy demand.

AWS offers SageMaker⁶³ as a powerful cloud based IDE for ML and AI applications development. SageMaker provides functionality for ML models deployment as a part of MLOps environment and process⁶⁴, connecting to multi-model endpoints for ML inference, which allow multiple models to share a single endpoint, reducing unnecessary compute resource duplication.

For machine learning (ML) workloads, AWS suggests adopting pre-trained models and transfer learning instead of training large models from scratch, significantly reducing carbon footprint and training costs. The Amazon SageMaker Training Compiler⁶⁵ further optimizes GPU and CPU utilization, cutting down processing time and energy consumption.

Workflow Management for Energy Efficiency

AWS promotes carbon-aware scheduling for workload execution, where tasks are shifted to times and regions with low-carbon energy availability. This ensures optimal workload execution with the lowest environmental impact. Services like AWS IoT Greengrass enable local inference, reducing the need for continuous cloud interactions. For AI/ML workloads, AWS recommends batch processing and edge computing together with using pre-trained models to reduce unnecessary data transfers and computation, especially in the model development stage⁶⁶.

⁶¹ <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/graviton/>

⁶² <https://aws.amazon.com/ai/machine-learning/inferentia/>

⁶³ Amazon SageMaker - <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/sagemaker/>

⁶⁴ <https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/mlops/>

⁶⁵ Amazon SageMaker Training Compiler- <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/sagemaker/latest/dg/training-compiler.html>

⁶⁶ <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/architecture/optimize-ai-ml-workloads-for-sustainability-part-2-model-development/>

Storage Optimization for Reduced Environmental Impact⁶⁷

AWS advocates tiered storage management, ensuring that data is stored based on access frequency and long-term retention needs.

Best practices include:

- Using Amazon S3 Intelligent-Tiering to automatically move infrequently accessed data to lower-energy storage classes.
- Compressing and deduplicating data to reduce storage footprint and eliminate redundant copies.
- Minimizing log retention and automating data lifecycle management to delete obsolete data.

For database workloads, AWS recommends serverless databases such as Amazon Aurora Serverless, which dynamically scales based on workload demand, reducing idle database instances.

Efficient Use of Cloud Compute Resources⁶⁸

AWS encourages organizations to right-size their compute instances, ensuring that resources are not over-provisioned.

Key strategies include:

- Using energy-efficient AWS Graviton-based instances, which offer better performance per watt than traditional x86 instances.
- Deploying workloads in AWS regions with renewable energy sources, reducing reliance on fossil-fuel-powered data centers.
- Employing AWS Trainium and Inferentia chips for AI/ML inference, which significantly cut down power consumption.
- Reducing data movement across networks by using AWS Direct Connect and edge computing solutions.

In summary, AWS provides a structured approach to sustainable cloud computing, enabling organizations to design, deploy, and manage workloads with minimal environmental impact. Through efficient software design, intelligent workload scheduling, storage optimization, and energy-conscious compute resource allocation, AWS helps businesses achieve their sustainability goals while maintaining high performance.

7.3.3 AWS Sustainability Design Principles and Recommended Architecture Styles

Understanding and applying right architecture style for applications and system design provides multiple benefits with sustainability being one of the benefits. The topic of the software architecture styles and system architecture styles is sufficiently supported by multiple technical blog articles^{69 70} and one of blog articles at Medium forum provides the most complete reference of software architecture

⁶⁷ <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/architecture/optimizing-your-aws-infrastructure-for-sustainability-part-ii-storage/>

⁶⁸ <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/architecture/optimizing-your-aws-infrastructure-for-sustainability-part-i-compute/>

⁶⁹ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/architecture/guide/architecture-styles/>

⁷⁰ https://medium.com/@learnwithwhiteboard_digest/all-major-software-architecture-patterns-explained-8ed6b50a16e3

styles⁷¹. The recent author papers [110] [111] provided summary and suggestions about architecture styles generally suitable for such projects as digital research infrastructures and complex scientific applications.

AWS promotes sustainability through energy-efficient cloud architecture, integrating sustainability principles into software design, workflow execution, storage management, and compute resource allocation. By selecting the right architecture styles, organizations can maximize energy efficiency and reduce their cloud-based environmental impact. The following text provides a summary and suggestions based on the referenced above AWS technical blog posts.

7.3.3.1 Sustainability Design Principles in AWS Well-Architected Framework

AWS outlines key sustainability principles to help organizations reduce the carbon footprint of cloud workloads:

A. Optimize Utilization & Reduce Waste

Design applications to fully utilize allocated resources before scaling up. This reduces idle capacity and energy waste.

Best Architecture Styles: Serverless, Microservices, and Event-Driven Architectures

- Serverless computing (e.g., AWS Lambda) ensures compute resources are only used when needed.
- Microservices architectures improve efficiency by decoupling services, avoiding monolithic inefficiencies.
- Event-driven models (e.g., AWS Step Functions) eliminate always-on infrastructure, improving energy utilization.

B. Use Managed Services to Reduce Operational Overhead

AWS fully-managed services optimize hardware utilization across multiple tenants, reducing energy consumption per user.

Best Architecture Styles: Managed Cloud-Native & SaaS-Based Architectures

- Using AWS Fargate for containers or Aurora Serverless for databases minimizes idle resource waste.
- Cloud-native architectures leverage auto-scaling to efficiently match demand.

C. Optimize Workload Execution for Energy Efficiency

Applications should schedule workloads in energy-optimal locations and times based on grid carbon intensity.

Best Architecture Styles: Edge Computing, Hybrid Cloud, and AI-Driven Workload Scheduling

- Edge computing (AWS IoT Greengrass) moves processing closer to users, reducing cloud data transfers.
- Hybrid cloud architectures allow workloads to run on-premises when energy-efficient and move to AWS when needed.
- AI-based carbon-aware scheduling shifts workloads to AWS regions with renewable energy availability.

⁷¹ <https://medium.com/bytebytego-system-design-alliance/the-architects-blueprint-understanding-software-styles-and-patterns-with-cheatsheet-5c1f5fd55bbd>

D. Optimize Storage and Data Transfer

Storing and transferring data more efficiently reduces storage costs, energy use, and network traffic. Best Architecture Styles: Data Mesh & Federated Data Processing

- Data mesh architecture reduces data duplication and improves energy efficiency.
- Amazon S3 Intelligent-Tiering moves data to lower-energy storage automatically.
- Federated data processing allows data to be processed at the source, reducing transfer-related energy costs.

7.3.3.2 Architecture Styles and Their Benefits for Energy Efficiency

A. Serverless Architectures (e.g., AWS Lambda, Fargate)

Serverless computing eliminates the need for provisioned infrastructure, using only the required compute capacity. Energy Benefits:

- Reduces idle energy consumption – no constantly running servers.
- Scales automatically, adjusting to demand.
- Lower hardware footprint – shared across multiple workloads.

B. Microservices Architectures (e.g., Amazon ECS, API Gateway)

Applications are broken into smaller, independent services, ensuring more efficient scaling. Energy Benefits:

- Prevents over-provisioning – services scale independently.
- Reduces resource waste by only running the necessary components.
- Compatible with auto-scaling, making it energy-efficient.

C. Event-Driven & Asynchronous Architectures (e.g., AWS Step Functions, SNS/SQS)

Workloads are triggered only when needed, reducing constant polling and CPU waste. Energy Benefits:

- Eliminates unnecessary background processing.
- Better suited for burst workloads, minimizing idle power consumption.
- Efficient use of compute resources, especially for ML and IoT workloads.

D. Edge Computing & Hybrid Cloud (e.g., AWS Wavelength, AWS IoT Greengrass)

Processes data closer to the user, reducing cloud round trips and improving network energy efficiency. Energy Benefits:

- Minimizes cloud data transfer, lowering carbon emissions.
- Uses local resources first, shifting to AWS only when needed.
- Improves application responsiveness while consuming less power.

E. Data Mesh & Federated Learning (e.g., Amazon S3, AWS SageMaker)

Allows distributed data storage and processing, reducing the need for centralized cloud operations. Energy Benefits:

- Lowers energy-intensive data transfers across multiple regions.
- Enables efficient, localized AI training, reducing cloud compute costs.
- Optimizes storage tiers, ensuring high-performance data retrieval with minimal energy impact.

By aligning AWS sustainability design principles with energy-efficient architectures (defined by Architecture Styles), organizations can optimize cloud workloads while minimizing environmental impact.

- Serverless and Microservices reduce idle capacity and scale dynamically, eliminating unnecessary energy use.
- Event-driven and asynchronous workflows ensure computing only happens when needed.
- Edge computing and hybrid cloud models shift workloads closer to the user, improving energy efficiency.
- Data mesh and federated learning optimize data storage and transfer, reducing cloud dependency.

AWS provides a range of sustainable cloud solutions that allow organizations to design energy-efficient architectures without compromising scalability or performance. As cloud adoption grows, selecting the right architecture will be critical to achieving sustainability goals. Learning from AWS can help RI and cloud based services developers to implement effective solutions on their platforms.

7.4 Software Energy Efficiency Tactics and Application to Scientific Software

A potentially useful approach to the general aspects of scientific software design is proposed in the papers by Patricia Lago (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam) that explore multiple facets of sustainability in cloud computing, software architecture, and machine learning systems. One of her key studies focuses on optimizing energy efficiency in the public cloud. The papers identify a set of reusable architectural tactics aimed at cloud consumers rather than providers [112]. Through interviews with industry professionals, the authors outline methods such as dynamic scaling, workload migration, and energy-aware scheduling, emphasizing that cloud users must take active measures to optimize software for energy efficiency, despite the lack of transparency in cloud energy consumption reporting.

Another major contribution examines green architectural tactics for machine learning (ML)-enabled systems, addressing the growing energy demands of AI applications [113]. The authors synthesize thirty tactics from an extensive literature review and validate them with industry experts. Their findings emphasize reducing model complexity, optimizing data preprocessing, and leveraging energy-efficient hardware to mitigate the carbon footprint of ML workflows. This study highlights the tension between accuracy-driven AI development and sustainable computing practices, advocating for a balanced approach where performance does not come at an unsustainable energy cost.

In a broader survey of software energy efficiency tactics [114], the authors/researchers collaborate on a systematic review of 163 tactics extracted from over 140 studies. The research shows that interest in energy-efficient software peaked in 2015 but has since declined and that most existing tactics focus on code-level optimisations or dynamic monitoring. However, industry adoption remains low due to a disconnect between academic research and real-world implementation, with many developers unaware of software energy consumption or lacking practical tools to address it. The methodology used in the paper can be used for a new study to understand the software development companies attitude at the present time with the growing importance of sustainability and reduced environmental impact in the whole digital ecosystem.

Table 1 provides a mapping of energy efficiency software design tactics to scientific software design that can be further discussed and applied in project development.

Table 1. Mapping Energy Efficiency design tactics to Scientific Software Design

Category	Proposed Tactics	Applicability to Scientific Software Design
Resource Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automatic monitoring of workload efficiency - Experimentation with alternative architectures 	Highly relevant: Scientific software often involves large-scale data processing and benefits from automated performance monitoring to optimize energy consumption.
Resource Allocation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dynamic scaling (horizontal & vertical) - Task scheduling for energy efficiency - Workload migration 	Highly relevant: Scientific workflows often involve high-performance computing (HPC), cloud, and edge computing. Scheduling and workload migration are critical for energy savings.
Resource Adaptation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-adaptive resource management - Reducing computation redundancy - Efficient data caching and storage 	Highly relevant: Many scientific workflows involve iterative computations and large data transfers. Adaptation techniques can reduce duplicate computations and data movement overheads.
Green AI/ML Tactics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reducing ML model complexity - Efficient data preprocessing - Energy-efficient training (e.g., TPU, GPU) 	Partially relevant: Applicable only if scientific software uses ML-based analysis (e.g., bioinformatics, climate modelling).
Cloud Data Storage KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storage efficiency monitoring - Minimizing "dark data" - Energy-efficient replication 	Highly relevant: Scientific datasets are large, and reducing unnecessary storage and replication is crucial.

The recent paper [115] is focused on the cloud distributed data storage energy efficiency aspects, that the study defines key performance indicators (KPIs) for monitoring the energy efficiency of cloud-based storage systems. The study proposes three primary KPIs—energy consumption, storage utilization, and capacity per watt—offering a structured approach to track and optimize data storage efficiency. The research underscores the critical role of cloud storage in the growing energy footprint of data centers and calls for greater transparency in cloud providers' sustainability metrics.

The summarised papers may provide an approach to bridge the gap between theoretical research and practical implementation, providing actionable frameworks for software architects, cloud users, and data scientists to make more energy-efficient design choices. The surveyed research underscores the urgent need for sustainability in software engineering, advocating for energy-aware architectures, smarter cloud resource management, and transparent energy reporting mechanisms to reduce the environmental impact of digital infrastructures. This is also linked to the research on the integrated/multi-factor energy monitoring in complex digital infrastructures.

8 Data Management

8.1 Sustainability Aspects in Data Management

Sustainability aspects in data management are not well defined and implemented in research community. Current trends in research data management are primarily focused on ensuring efficient data management, including data, documenting, storing and sharing, what is best defined by FAIR data principles for research data that should ensure that data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. FAIR compliance provides a basis for the sustainability of data storage, sharing and contributes to the reproducibility of research and interdisciplinary research that require well-documented data and reliable/guaranteed data access with the possibility of their use/integration in future research, with potentially wider scope than initially created data.

However, sustainability aspects in building and operating Data Management Infrastructure (DMI) are primarily discussed and addressed by industry and, in particular, Big Data and cloud service providers. This section provides an overview of existing publications related to both sides/aspects in relation between data management and sustainability.

Sustainability aspects in data management are considered in two main aspects:

1. Data management practices and recommendations to support organisational measures and processes to support energy efficiency and environmental sustainability.
2. Infrastructure and architecture-related approaches to ensure energy efficiency and environmental sustainability (reduce environmental impact or CO₂ footprint) of the Data Management Infrastructure and related services to support its corresponding operation. These aspects must be addressed by applying necessary infrastructure and system design principles.

There are known approaches and frameworks being developed and implemented by companies and operators that deal/require extensive/large scale data management related infrastructure services. This relates to necessary data management infrastructure for cloud services providers, data analytics applications, and emerging Generative AI (GenAI) and LLM applications that besides requiring strong computational ability also must supported by distributed and multilayer data storage and access infrastructure (that includes/require access to raw and training dataset, well attributed models, knowledge bases, and semantic caching).

8.2 Data management recommendations and practices to support energy efficiency and environmental sustainability.

This also relates to research infrastructure and services that are focused on monitoring and protecting the environment and ecosystems. Well-established data management must ensure that data are well documented, reliably stored and maintained, and provide sufficient functionality for efficient data sharing. For modern digital Research Infrastructures and wide research communities, these solutions and practices should comply with the FAIR data principles and be supported with well-defined metadata registries and WebAPI.

Valuable overview and analysis provided by the Dutch Coalition for Sustainable Digitalisation (Nederlands Coalitie Duurzame Digitalisering (NCDD) [116] [117]). Sustainable data management has therefore emerged as a critical strategy for organizations to address the environmental footprint of their data lifecycle. Sustainable data management is not just a technical or operational issue; it is a

strategic imperative at the executive level as well as a cultural mind shift. This paper uses the DMBok⁷² phases to address the sustainability considerations in all the phases of your data lifecycle, from planning, creation until the data is destroyed.

NCDD also provides a reference to the position paper published by the group of Prof Patricia Lago (Vrij Universiteit Amsterdam) that has long time experience from years of active research 2010-2022 on the sustainability of software based applications and related infrastructure components. The referred paper of 2021 provided valuable analysis and an overview of disruptive technologies that are transforming industries, this defined as the Lower Energy Acceleration Program (LEAP) [118]. This guide helps stakeholders who want to contribute to building a future-proof energy-efficient digital infrastructure to identify and understand technology trends. Through in-depth analysis and up-to-date information, the LEAP Technology Landscape supports decision-makers and innovators in accelerating innovation.

The current approaches to sustainability data management are analysed in the one of industry leading companies dealing with ESG related data management [119]. Current data management practices are largely ad-hoc within the enterprises, alarming for a shift from reactive to proactive methods. In addition, companies need to collaborate to manage their sustainability data efficiently (e.g., having common standards and definitions), since it becomes more difficult to survive as a sole fighter. Therefore, CC CDQ launches co-innovation group to elaborate on these issues and to join forces in developing a scalable approach to sustainability data management. In this close collaboration between researchers and practitioners, the group will address various sustainability scenarios (e.g., carbon footprint along the supply chain, supplier qualification, and product labelling), the underlying data requirements, as well as the data management capabilities for sustainability.

Science Europe's Practical Guide to Sustainable Research Data [120] offers complementary maturity matrices for funders, performers, and data infrastructures to create a common understanding of the approaches needed by the different stakeholders involved. It will support the alignment of policies and requirements for sustainable research data.

Sustainable Research Data Sharing and re-using data to reproduce research and build upon it, are a cornerstone of Open Science. The sustainability of research data refers to their long-term preservation, accessibility, and interoperability. It is something that needs to be addressed by everyone involved. Aligned policies and requirements can limit the collective effort needed and increase the usefulness of research data management.

This Practical Guide provides guidance to ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of research data. Three complementary maturity matrices provide funders, performers, and data infrastructures with a way to create a common understanding of the approaches needed. These allow them to evaluate the current status of their policies and practices, and to identify next steps towards sustainable data sharing and seeking alignment with other organisations in doing so.

⁷² DMBok is a Data Management Body of Knowledge defined by the Data Management Association International. It is considered as industry standard accepted by majority of companies dealing with the data management in their business and operations.

8.3 Reducing Energy Consumption and Environmental Impact of the Data Management Infrastructure

Data Dynamics company [121] provides a valuable introduction briefing on their view on environmentally sustainable data management that should balance the growth of data infrastructure with environmental responsibility. This includes the following key points:

1. **Environmental Impact of Data Centers.** Data centers contribute 2% of global carbon emissions, with the US responsible for 0.5%. The growing demand for digital services and exponential rise in unstructured data strains resources and increases environmental concerns.
2. **Challenges with Unstructured Data:** Unstructured data accounts for 80% of stored data, much of which is unused or redundant ("dark data"), consuming energy unnecessarily. Organizations need to shift from indiscriminate data storage to strategic analysis, reducing clutter and environmental impact.
3. **Strategies for Sustainable Data Management.**
 - Hybrid Cloud Adoption, combining on-premises and cloud resources for optimized storage and reduced carbon footprints.
 - Data tiering ensures critical data is stored on-premises while less-used data is migrated to energy-efficient cloud environments.
4. **Data Minimization:** Reduces redundant, obsolete, and trivial data through governance, audits, and lifecycle management. Adopting technologies like data deduplication and compression enhances storage efficiency and lowers energy use.
5. **Unified Data Management (UDM)** supported by necessary tools for actionable data insight and use, employs AI, ML, and automation to streamline data operations securely and efficiently.

Dataversity company that is primarily focused on professional training on enterprise data management [122], highlights the growing environmental impact of digital data and the necessity of sustainable data management to mitigate it. The following aspects need to be addressed:

Environmental Impact of Data and IT Infrastructure

- **Data Growth:** The exponential increase in digital data requires vast energy resources for storage, processing, and transmission, contributing to carbon emissions and resource depletion.
- **E-Waste:** Manufacturing and disposal of electronic devices create hazardous waste, harming ecosystems and human health.

Strategies for Sustainable Data Management

- **Energy-Efficient Data Centers:** Incorporate advanced cooling technologies, renewable energy sources (solar, wind, hydroelectric), and energy-efficient hardware to minimize energy consumption and carbon emissions.
- **Cloud Computing:** transitioning to sustainable cloud platforms leverages energy-efficient, large-scale data centers and reduces organizational carbon footprints.
- **Data Optimization:** Implement data compression, deduplication, and lifecycle management to reduce redundant and obsolete data.
- **Waste Management:** Embrace a circular economy through refurbishing, recycling, and proper disposal of outdated equipment.
- **Governance and Compliance Data Governance:** Establish policies ensuring efficient, secure, and transparent data handling while meeting regulatory and ethical standards. Certifications:

- Achieving certifications like LEED, Energy Star, or EPAT demonstrates commitment to sustainable practices.

Technological and Operational Advancements

- **Green Computing:** environmentally friendly technologies, including energy-efficient hardware, virtualization, and renewable energy integration.
- **Unified Data Management (UDM):** tools like UDM enhance data quality, integration, and visibility, enabling better decision-making and sustainability.
- **Metrics and Future Outlook** Real-time monitoring of energy consumption, emissions, and waste ensures compliance and enables targeted sustainability measures. The importance of sustainable data management is expected to grow in 2024, driven by data value, regulatory changes, and environmental concerns.

The principles of sustainable data management align with reducing environmental impact while supporting business growth, paving the way for a greener digital future.

9 Ongoing Research, Initiatives, and Community Efforts on Sustainability in Research Infrastructures

Sustainability in Research Infrastructures (RIs) revolves around their ability to provide cutting-edge services while adhering to principles of environmental, economic, and social responsibility. Sustainable RIs require well-defined architectural principles that ensure long-term evolution and integration of modern technologies, addressing the lifecycle of resources from development to decommissioning [123]. Another paper emphasize that adopting green infrastructure practices, such as renewable energy and resource-efficient technologies, can significantly reduce the ecological footprint of RIs while fostering socio-economic benefits [124].

Case studies like SLICES-RI highlight the importance of integrating digital and data-driven solutions to enhance operational efficiency while maintaining sustainability [123] [124]. A comprehensive framework for sustainable RIs includes policies promoting energy-efficient infrastructure, federated data management, and lifecycle-oriented design principles [124]. However, challenges persist in balancing high performance with sustainability, particularly as advanced computational needs increase energy consumption and resource dependency. Effective strategies, such as leveraging multi-functional green infrastructure and integrating AI-driven resource optimization, are crucial to maintaining this equilibrium while achieving broader sustainability goals.

9.1 Evaluation and Comparative Analysis

The evaluation of sustainability in Research Infrastructures (RIs) necessitates a comprehensive analysis of their environmental impact, especially regarding energy consumption, resource utilization, and waste production. Current practices, while effective in operational terms, often contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and resource inefficiency. The adoption of green infrastructure, as highlighted in , represents a pivotal strategy for sustainable development, leveraging natural systems to reduce ecological footprints while providing economic and social benefits.

Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) for sustainable solutions vary widely, with innovative approaches like renewable energy-powered data centers and advanced cooling systems reaching higher TRLs (7-9) in some applications, while others remain in early development stages (TRL 4-6). A comparative analysis of technologies reveals key trade-offs: for instance, while green roofs and permeable pavements significantly mitigate urban heat islands and water runoff, their implementation costs can be a barrier. Similarly, AI-driven resource optimization tools improve energy efficiency but demand substantial adaptation of existing infrastructures. As emphasized in [124] effective planning and investment in green technologies are crucial to balance development and ecosystem preservation. This underscores the need for a systematic framework that integrates advanced technologies with sustainable practices, ensuring long-term viability without compromising RI performance.

9.2 Recommendations for Research Infrastructures

To ensure the sustainability of Research Infrastructures (RIs), immediate actions should focus on implementing energy-efficient technologies, such as renewable energy sources and advanced cooling systems, and adopting green infrastructure practices to reduce environmental impact. Existing RIs must also enhance data management frameworks, integrating federated solutions to optimize resource use and reduce redundancies. For long-term strategic directions, the paper [110] proposes

adopting sustainable architectural design principles, which include lifecycle-oriented planning, modularity, and scalability to support evolving technological needs while minimizing waste.

Policies should prioritize funding mechanisms that incentivize green innovations, such as nature-based solutions and low-impact development strategies, alongside fostering international collaboration to share expertise and resources. Regulatory frameworks must emphasize compliance with sustainability standards and promote training programs for personnel to address skill gaps in managing complex, sustainable RI systems. These steps are essential to position RIs as leaders in sustainable development and as contributors to global ecological resilience.

9.3 GenAI Impact on Energy Efficiency

Generative AI (GenAI) has emerged as a transformative technology with significant implications for energy efficiency in data centers and broader energy systems [125]. The immense computational demands of GenAI models, such as training and inference for large language models, require energy-intensive infrastructure. For instance, the energy consumption of a single training session for a large model can exceed the annual electricity use of multiple households. To address this challenge, we need to investigate systematically energy impact of GenAI models on infrastructures [126]. Companies like Hitachi are integrating renewable energy sources, energy storage systems, and smart grid technologies to power data centers sustainably, ensuring resilience and efficiency in energy consumption.

Moreover, GenAI itself offers tools for optimizing energy systems. As highlighted by recent research, GenAI can enhance energy harvesting technologies in wireless networks, improving resource allocation, network deployment, and real-time energy management [125]. Applications such as UAV-assisted energy transfer and renewable energy forecasting demonstrate the role of GenAI in creating dynamic, adaptive systems capable of balancing energy generation and consumption. These capabilities enable the reduction of carbon footprints and operational costs while maintaining high performance.

To fully realize sustainable GenAI applications, it is essential to align the development of AI models with green computing principles, leveraging energy-efficient hardware and algorithms. Additionally, policies must support investments in renewable energy and the integration of AI-driven solutions in energy management to minimize the environmental impact of this transformative technology. This multifaceted approach ensures that GenAI contributes not only to technological advancement but also to global sustainability goals.

9.4 Sustainability Initiatives, Industry Programmes, and Research Efforts in Digital Infrastructures

In addition to regulatory frameworks and technical standards, a broad range of industry initiatives, research programmes, and collaborative efforts contribute to advancing sustainability in digital infrastructures. These initiatives bring together stakeholders from academia, industry, and policy-making bodies to develop best practices, promote transparency, and accelerate the adoption of energy-efficient and environmentally sustainable technologies.

They address multiple dimensions of sustainability, including energy efficiency, carbon reduction, resource optimisation, and circular economy principles. Furthermore, they play a key role in bridging the gap between policy objectives and practical implementation by providing guidelines,

benchmarking methodologies, and shared tools for monitoring and improving data centre performance.

The following subsections provide an overview of key European and global initiatives, as well as recent research and innovation projects, that are shaping the development of sustainable data centres and digital infrastructures.

9.4.1 Climate Neutral Data Centre Pact

The Climate Neutral Data Centre Pact (CNDCP) is a voluntary self-regulatory initiative established by leading European data centre operators and industry associations to support the transition towards climate-neutral digital infrastructures by 2030. Launched in 2021 and aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal, the Pact represents a coordinated industry response to increasing regulatory and societal pressure to reduce the environmental impact of data centres.

The initiative brings together hyperscale providers, colocation operators, and industry stakeholders, committing signatories to a set of measurable targets and key performance indicators across five main areas: energy efficiency, clean energy usage, water conservation, circular economy, and heat reuse. These commitments are designed to complement European regulatory frameworks, including Directive (EU) 2024/1364, by promoting best practices and accelerating the adoption of sustainability measures beyond minimum compliance requirements.

A central element of the Pact is the commitment to achieving high levels of energy efficiency, with targets for Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) adapted to different climate zones. In parallel, signatories commit to sourcing 100% carbon-free energy by 2030, using a combination of renewable energy procurement mechanisms such as Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), guarantees of origin, and on-site generation. Water usage is addressed through the adoption of water-efficient cooling technologies and the monitoring of Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE), particularly in water-stressed regions.

The Pact also places strong emphasis on circular economy principles, including the repair, reuse, and recycling of IT equipment, as well as the reduction of waste across the lifecycle of data centre infrastructure. In addition, signatories are encouraged to implement heat recovery solutions, contributing to local energy systems through district heating or other reuse mechanisms, thereby improving overall energy utilisation.

Progress under the Pact is monitored through annual reporting and independent verification, ensuring transparency and accountability. Aggregated results are published to provide insights into industry-wide performance and to track progress towards climate neutrality targets. This reporting approach aligns with broader European efforts to standardise sustainability metrics and improve comparability across data centres.

While participation in the Pact is voluntary, its influence is significant, as it includes many of the largest data centre operators in Europe. As such, it plays an important role in shaping industry practices and supporting the transition towards more sustainable digital infrastructures. The Climate Neutral Data Centre Pact can be seen as a bridge between regulatory requirements and operational implementation, providing a flexible yet structured framework for achieving climate neutrality in the sector.

9.4.2 European Code of Conduct for Data Centres

The European Code of Conduct for Data Centres (EU CoC) is a voluntary initiative developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) aimed at improving the energy efficiency of data centres through the adoption of best practices and standardised methodologies. Established in 2008, the initiative provides a structured framework for data centre operators, owners, and service providers to reduce energy consumption in a cost-effective manner while maintaining service performance and reliability.

The EU CoC defines a comprehensive set of **best practices** covering all aspects of data centre design and operation, including IT equipment, cooling systems, power distribution, monitoring, and management processes. These practices are categorised into expected minimum requirements and recommended actions, enabling participants to progressively improve their energy performance. The framework promotes a holistic approach, emphasising that efficiency gains must be achieved through the optimisation of both infrastructure and IT systems.

A key feature of the Code of Conduct is its strong focus on **measurement and monitoring**, recognising that effective energy management requires accurate and consistent data collection. Participants are required to report energy consumption and efficiency indicators, including metrics such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), while also providing detailed information on implemented best practices. This aligns closely with the principles later formalised in Directive (EU) 2024/1364, particularly in terms of standardised reporting and benchmarking.

In addition to operational practices, the EU CoC encourages the adoption of **advanced technologies and design strategies**, such as free cooling, high-efficiency power systems, and workload consolidation. It also supports the implementation of management processes, including capacity planning, lifecycle management, and continuous improvement mechanisms, which are essential for sustaining long-term efficiency gains.

Participation in the EU CoC involves a formal commitment to implement applicable best practices and to report progress periodically. The initiative provides recognition for compliant data centres, enhancing transparency and supporting benchmarking across the sector. Over time, the Code of Conduct has become a widely recognised reference for energy-efficient data centre operation in Europe and has influenced both industry practices and policy development.

Overall, the European Code of Conduct for Data Centres plays a foundational role in promoting energy efficiency and sustainability, serving as a practical guide for operators and a precursor to more recent regulatory frameworks. It complements initiatives such as the Climate Neutral Data Centre Pact by providing detailed technical guidance and supporting the systematic improvement of data centre performance.

9.4.3 Open Compute Project (OCP)

The Open Compute Project (OCP) is a global collaborative initiative founded in 2011 with the objective of redesigning hardware technologies to support more efficient, scalable, and sustainable data centre infrastructures. Originally initiated by Meta (Facebook), OCP has evolved into a broad industry consortium involving hyperscalers, hardware vendors, research institutions, and solution providers, working together to develop open specifications for data centre hardware and infrastructure.

A central principle of OCP is the promotion of **open and standardised hardware designs**, enabling greater efficiency, interoperability, and innovation across the data centre ecosystem. OCP specifications cover a wide range of components, including servers, storage systems, networking equipment, power distribution, and cooling technologies. By optimising hardware design for large-scale deployment, OCP aims to reduce energy consumption, improve resource utilisation, and lower total cost of ownership.

From a sustainability perspective, OCP places strong emphasis on **energy efficiency and thermal optimisation**. This includes the development of high-efficiency power systems, such as Open Rack architectures with centralised power supplies, as well as advanced cooling solutions, including direct liquid cooling. These approaches reduce energy losses in power conversion and improve heat removal efficiency, contributing to lower PUE values and enabling higher-density computing environments, particularly for HPC and AI workloads.

OCP also addresses **hardware lifecycle and circularity**, promoting modular and serviceable designs that extend equipment lifespan and facilitate repair, reuse, and recycling. Standardised components and disaggregated architectures allow operators to upgrade individual subsystems without replacing entire systems, thereby reducing embodied carbon and electronic waste.

Another important aspect of OCP is its support for **monitoring and telemetry standardisation**, including the use of open interfaces such as Redfish for hardware management. This aligns with the requirements of unified monitoring architectures, enabling consistent data collection across heterogeneous systems and supporting advanced sustainability metrics and reporting frameworks.

Through its open and collaborative model, OCP has significantly influenced the design of modern hyperscale data centres and is increasingly relevant for research infrastructures adopting similar architectures. By combining hardware innovation with sustainability objectives, the Open Compute Project contributes to the development of more efficient, transparent, and environmentally responsible digital infrastructures.

9.4.4 Top500 and Green500

The Top500 and Green500 rankings are widely recognised benchmarking initiatives that evaluate the performance and energy efficiency of the world's most powerful supercomputers. While the Top500 list, established in 1993, ranks systems based on their computational performance using the LINPACK benchmark, the Green500 list, introduced in 2007, complements this perspective by assessing energy efficiency, measured as performance per unit of power consumption. Together, these rankings provide a dual perspective on high-performance computing (HPC), balancing raw computational capability with sustainability considerations.

The Green500 ranking evaluates systems based on **performance per watt**, typically expressed in gigaflops per watt (GFLOPS/W), making it conceptually aligned with metrics such as TFLOPS/W used in AI and accelerator-based systems. This metric enables direct comparison of energy efficiency across different architectures, including CPU-based systems, GPU-accelerated platforms, and emerging specialised accelerators. As a result, the Green500 has become a key reference for assessing technological progress in energy-efficient computing.

The combined use of Top500 and Green500 rankings highlights the increasing importance of **energy efficiency as a core design objective** in HPC systems. Modern supercomputers are no longer evaluated

solely on peak performance but also on their ability to deliver computational power within constrained energy budgets. This has driven the adoption of energy-efficient architectures, including heterogeneous systems with accelerators, advanced cooling solutions such as liquid cooling, and optimised system software.

From a sustainability perspective, the Green500 provides valuable insights into best practices and technological trends that can be transferred to broader data centre and research infrastructure contexts. For example, the leading systems in the Green500 ranking demonstrate the benefits of tightly integrated hardware–software optimisation, efficient workload scheduling, and advanced cooling techniques in achieving high energy efficiency.

However, certain limitations must be considered. The Green500 metric is based on benchmark performance under controlled conditions and may not fully reflect real-world workloads or operational variability. Additionally, it focuses on operational energy efficiency and does not account for lifecycle impacts such as embodied carbon or infrastructure-level energy consumption.

Despite these limitations, the Top500 and Green500 rankings play a significant role in promoting transparency, benchmarking, and innovation in energy-efficient computing. They provide a globally recognised reference for evaluating progress in sustainable HPC and contribute to the development of more efficient architectures that can be adopted in data centres and research infrastructures.

9.4.5 Sustainable Digital Infrastructure Alliance (SDIA)

The Sustainable Digital Infrastructure Alliance (SDIA) is a European multi-stakeholder initiative focused on accelerating the transition towards environmentally sustainable digital infrastructures. Established to support the objectives of the European Green Deal, SDIA brings together industry actors, policymakers, researchers, and civil society organisations to develop frameworks, tools, and best practices for reducing the environmental impact of data centres, cloud services, and digital technologies.

A central objective of SDIA is to promote **holistic sustainability approaches** that go beyond energy efficiency and consider the full lifecycle and systemic impact of digital infrastructures. This includes addressing carbon emissions, resource consumption, circular economy principles, and supply chain transparency. SDIA advocates for the integration of operational metrics with lifecycle-based indicators, aligning closely with emerging regulatory requirements and sustainability reporting standards in Europe.

One of the key contributions of SDIA is the development of **methodologies and tools for sustainability assessment**, including frameworks for carbon accounting, energy transparency, and digital product passports. These approaches aim to improve comparability and accountability across the digital infrastructure sector, supporting both regulatory compliance and voluntary sustainability commitments.

SDIA also places strong emphasis on **policy alignment and standardisation**, working closely with European institutions to inform the development of regulations such as the Energy Efficiency Directive and related initiatives. By bridging the gap between industry practices and policy objectives, SDIA contributes to the creation of a coherent and interoperable sustainability framework for digital infrastructures.

In addition, the alliance promotes **collaboration and knowledge sharing** through working groups, pilot projects, and partnerships with research initiatives. These activities support the adoption of innovative technologies and practices, including renewable energy integration, energy-aware computing, and circular hardware design.

Overall, the Sustainable Digital Infrastructure Alliance plays a strategic role in shaping the sustainability agenda for digital infrastructures in Europe. By combining technical expertise, policy engagement, and collaborative action, SDIA contributes to the development of more transparent, efficient, and environmentally responsible data centre ecosystems.

9.4.6 Industry Hyperscaler Sustainability Strategies

Large-scale cloud providers, commonly referred to as hyperscalers, play a central role in shaping the sustainability landscape of digital infrastructures. Companies such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud operate global data centre networks with significant energy demand, and have therefore developed comprehensive sustainability strategies aimed at reducing environmental impact while maintaining scalability and performance.

A key pillar of hyperscaler strategies is the transition towards **carbon-free or net-zero energy operation**. Most major providers have committed to sourcing 100% renewable energy, primarily through long-term Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), on-site generation, and participation in energy markets. More advanced strategies focus on achieving **24/7 carbon-free energy**, ensuring that data centre operations are continuously matched with carbon-free electricity on an hourly basis rather than relying on annual balancing.

Hyperscalers also invest heavily in **data centre energy efficiency and infrastructure innovation**. This includes the deployment of custom-designed hardware optimised for performance per watt, advanced cooling technologies such as direct liquid cooling and immersion cooling, and highly efficient power distribution systems. These innovations contribute to low PUE values and enable high-density computing, particularly for AI and HPC workloads.

Another important dimension is **carbon-aware computing and workload optimisation**. Hyperscalers increasingly leverage real-time data on energy availability and carbon intensity to optimise workload placement and scheduling. By dynamically shifting workloads across regions or time periods, they can reduce carbon emissions while maintaining service quality. This approach aligns with emerging trends in energy-aware and sustainability-driven computing.

In addition to operational emissions, hyperscalers are addressing **Scope 3 emissions and embodied carbon** through supply chain engagement and circular economy practices. This includes the use of low-carbon materials, modular hardware design, refurbishment and reuse of equipment, and improved lifecycle management. Some providers also publish Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) and sustainability reports to increase transparency.

Hyperscalers further contribute to sustainability through **innovation and ecosystem impact**, developing tools and services that enable customers to monitor and reduce their own carbon footprint. Examples include carbon footprint dashboards, energy-aware APIs, and sustainability analytics platforms integrated into cloud services.

Despite significant progress, challenges remain, particularly in ensuring transparency and consistency in reporting methodologies, as well as addressing the full lifecycle impact of rapidly expanding

infrastructure. Nevertheless, hyperscaler sustainability strategies represent a major driver of innovation and set benchmarks for best practices that influence the broader data centre and research infrastructure ecosystem.

Overall, hyperscalers are at the forefront of integrating sustainability into large-scale digital infrastructure design and operation, combining renewable energy sourcing, efficiency optimisation, and advanced monitoring to reduce environmental impact at scale.

More detailed hyperscaler sustainability initiatives, including user-facing tools and resources, are presented in **Appendix 12.2**.

9.4.7 Recent Horizon Europe and RI Cluster Projects

Recent research and innovation activities under Horizon Europe and related Research Infrastructure (RI) clusters play a key role in advancing sustainability in digital infrastructures. These projects bring together academic institutions, industry partners, and infrastructure providers to develop new technologies, methodologies, and frameworks for energy-efficient, low-carbon, and resource-aware computing. In addition to technical innovation, they contribute to standardisation efforts, open science practices, and the dissemination of best practices across the European ecosystem.

A significant focus of these initiatives is the integration of **energy-aware computing, advanced monitoring, and sustainability metrics** into large-scale infrastructures. Projects address topics such as workload optimisation, carbon-aware scheduling, efficient data management, and lifecycle assessment, aligning closely with the requirements of Directive (EU) 2024/1364 and broader European sustainability policies. Many of these efforts also contribute to the development of interoperable monitoring frameworks and shared data models, supporting the implementation of unified monitoring architectures in federated environments.

Within this landscape, the **EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU)** plays a central role in coordinating Europe's high-performance computing and AI capabilities. EuroHPC JU supports the deployment of world-class supercomputers and the development of a European HPC and AI ecosystem, with increasing emphasis on sustainability and energy efficiency. Modern EuroHPC systems incorporate advanced technologies such as accelerator-based architectures, liquid cooling, and energy-efficient system design, reflecting best practices observed in initiatives such as the Green500.

A major recent development is the emergence of **AI Factories**, which extend the EuroHPC infrastructure towards integrated AI and data ecosystems. These facilities combine HPC systems, AI-optimised hardware (e.g., GPUs and specialised accelerators), data platforms, and software environments to support large-scale AI development and deployment. From a sustainability perspective, AI Factories introduce both challenges and opportunities. On one hand, AI workloads significantly increase energy demand and infrastructure density. On the other hand, they drive innovation in energy-efficient hardware, workload optimisation, and advanced cooling technologies.

The consolidation of AI Factory infrastructures within the EuroHPC ecosystem enables the **centralisation of sustainability data and practices**, providing a unique opportunity to harmonise monitoring approaches, standardise metrics, and benchmark performance across facilities. By integrating monitoring systems, telemetry pipelines, and sustainability indicators, these infrastructures can support comprehensive analysis of energy consumption, carbon footprint, and

resource utilisation at scale. This aligns with the broader objective of creating a unified and transparent framework for sustainability assessment across European research infrastructures.

In addition, Horizon Europe projects and RI clusters contribute to **knowledge sharing and capacity building**, providing open tools, datasets, and methodologies that can be adopted by data centre operators and researchers. These initiatives often serve as testbeds for innovative approaches, including carbon-aware scheduling, digital twins for data centres, and AI-driven optimisation of infrastructure performance. By combining large-scale infrastructure deployment with research-driven innovation and coordinated data sharing, they enable the development of more efficient, transparent, and environmentally responsible computing ecosystems.

Overall, Horizon Europe and RI cluster projects, together with EuroHPC JU and AI Factory initiatives, form a critical component of the European strategy for sustainable digital infrastructures.

10 Conclusion and Future Work

The GreenDIGIT project has provided a comprehensive State of the Art (SotA) assessment of sustainability in research infrastructures (RIs) and digital infrastructure. This report has explored and examined key technological, methodological, and policy dimensions of sustainable digital operations, including sustainability metrics and monitoring, energy-efficient computing, carbon-aware scheduling, green software design, sustainable data management, and research reproducibility. Taken together, these areas highlight the need for integrated solutions that can reduce the environmental footprint of digital infrastructures while supporting the performance and reliability requirements of modern scientific research.

The findings of this report emphasize that sustainability in research infrastructures is no longer optional, but a necessary transition toward more energy-conscious and environmentally responsible digital operations. RIs must adopt a multi-layered approach that combines energy-efficient hardware and accelerators, optimized workload scheduling, unified monitoring and reporting, sustainable software practices, and responsible data management. The report further shows that sustainability assessment can no longer rely on energy metrics alone, but increasingly requires broader environmental indicators related to carbon, water, energy reuse, renewable energy contribution, lifecycle impacts, embodied emissions, and AI-specific efficiency.

Despite substantial progress in energy-efficient computing and sustainable infrastructures design, several challenges remain. The adoption of harmonized sustainability metrics across heterogeneous federated computing infrastructures requires further refinement, particularly where cloud, HTC, HPC, and AI-enabled systems differ in architecture, observability, and reporting boundaries. The report also shows that modern accelerator-rich and HPC-AI environments create new challenges for energy attribution, telemetry integration, and sustainability assessment. In parallel, the use of machine learning and AI-driven optimizations for energy-aware scheduling remains an emerging field, with potential trade-offs between performance, computational efficiency and environmental impact that require further analysis.

The outcome of the presented SotA provides an important foundation for ongoing GreenDIGIT research and development activities. In particular, it supports the design and validation of prototype solutions for federated environmental monitoring, multi-layer telemetry integrations, automated sustainability reporting, and energy-aware workload scheduling across distributed RIs. The project will also continue to investigate data lifecycle management techniques aimed at reducing redundant data transfers and improving energy efficiency and sustainability of the data management infrastructure and distributed storage systems.

To support the practical implementation of these findings, GreenDIGIT will collaborate with research institutions, universities, industry stakeholders, and cloud providers to help embed sustainable practices into the design and operation of digital infrastructures. Additionally, the project will contribute to awareness building and capacity development by supporting training and knowledge-sharing activities for research communities, enabling them to better understand the environmental implications of computing and to adopt greener digital practices.

Ultimately, the goal is to position European RIs at the forefront of sustainable computing. By leveraging advanced sustainability metrics, federated monitoring, carbon-aware computing, sustainable software

practices, and optimized data workflows, GreenDIGIT aims to support the development of a scalable framework for the next generation of environmentally responsible RIs.

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12 Appendix

12.1 Detailed Description of Reporting Methodology and KPIs (Directive (EU) 2024/1364)

Annex I – General Information on Data Centres

Annex I defines the contextual information required to characterise each data centre. This includes identification details such as the name, ownership, and geographical location of the facility, as well as its classification (enterprise, colocation, or co-hosting). In addition, the directive requires reporting of structural attributes such as the total floor area of the data centre (SDC) and the computer room floor area (SCR), which are essential for normalising performance indicators.

Furthermore, operators must describe infrastructure characteristics, including redundancy levels for electrical and cooling systems. Redundancy is typically expressed using standard notation such as N+1 or 2N, indicating the level of fault tolerance built into the system. These parameters are crucial for interpreting energy and sustainability metrics, as higher redundancy levels generally imply increased energy overheads. By standardising these descriptors, Annex I ensures that differences in design and operational context are properly accounted for in subsequent analyses.

Annex II – Key Performance Indicators and Measurement Methodologies

Annex II defines the core set of Key Performance Indicators that must be monitored and reported, together with detailed measurement methodologies. These indicators provide a quantitative description of data centre operation across multiple dimensions, including energy consumption, environmental impact, infrastructure performance, and ICT capacity.

A central indicator is the Installed Information Technology Power Demand (PDIT), expressed in kilowatts, which represents the nominal power demand of all IT equipment installed within the data centre. This parameter defines the scale of the infrastructure and is used to categorise data centres and normalise other indicators. Closely related to this is the total energy consumption of the data centre (EDC), measured in kilowatt-hours, which captures the overall energy input to the facility, including cooling, power distribution, and auxiliary systems. In contrast, the energy consumption of IT equipment (EIT) isolates the portion of energy directly used by computing resources, enabling the separation of productive and overhead energy use.

Water-related indicators are also explicitly included, reflecting the increasing importance of water efficiency. The total water input (WIN) measures all water entering the data centre boundary for operational purposes, while the potable water input (WIN-POT) focuses specifically on drinking-quality water resources. These indicators are essential for evaluating water usage effectiveness and for understanding the environmental impact of cooling technologies.

The directive further introduces indicators related to thermal management and energy reuse. The waste heat reused (EREUSE) quantifies the amount of heat recovered and utilised outside the data centre, representing an important aspect of circular energy use. Complementing this, the average waste heat temperature (TWH) provides insight into the usability of the recovered heat, as higher temperatures are generally more suitable for external applications such as district heating.

Renewable energy integration is addressed through a set of indicators capturing different sourcing mechanisms. The total renewable energy consumption (ERES-TOT) represents the sum of renewable

energy used by the data centre, including energy procured through guarantees of origin, power purchase agreements, and on-site generation. This breakdown enables a more detailed understanding of how renewable energy is incorporated into data centre operations.

In addition to infrastructure-level metrics, Annex II also includes indicators related to ICT capacity and data traffic. The server capacity (CSERV) is derived from standardised performance benchmarks and reflects the computational capability of the installed hardware, while the storage capacity (CSTOR) captures the total data storage potential. Data traffic indicators, such as incoming and outgoing data volumes, provide additional context for assessing operational intensity and efficiency.

To ensure consistency, the directive specifies detailed measurement methodologies and defines precise measurement points within the data centre infrastructure. For example, total energy consumption must be measured at the system boundary before energy is distributed within the facility, while IT energy consumption is measured at the level of power distribution units or uninterruptible power systems. The regulation also provides schematic diagrams illustrating these measurement points, supporting consistent implementation across different data centres.

Annex III – Sustainability Indicators and Calculation Framework

Annex III defines how the reported KPIs are transformed into a set of standardised sustainability indicators. These include Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), which expresses the ratio between total energy consumption and IT energy consumption, Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE), which relates water usage to IT energy consumption, Energy Reuse Factor (ERF), which measures the proportion of energy that is reused outside the data centre, and Renewable Energy Factor (REF), which quantifies the share of renewable energy in total consumption.

These indicators are calculated using predefined formulas, ensuring that all data centres apply the same methodology. By deriving these indicators from the KPIs defined in Annex II, the directive establishes a consistent and transparent link between raw measurements and high-level sustainability metrics. This enables benchmarking across facilities and supports the development of future rating schemes.

Annex IV – Data Aggregation and Public Disclosure

Annex IV specifies how the collected data and calculated indicators are aggregated and made publicly available. While individual data centre data remain confidential, aggregated statistics are published at both Member State and EU levels. These include total energy consumption, total water usage, and average values of key sustainability indicators.

The aggregation process uses weighted averages based on total energy consumption, ensuring that larger facilities have an appropriate influence on the overall results. This approach enables meaningful comparisons across regions and supports policy development and monitoring at the European level.

Classification of Indicators and Reporting Requirements

Although the directive does not explicitly distinguish between mandatory and voluntary indicators, all information and KPIs defined in Annexes I and II are required to be reported. However, the regulation introduces transitional provisions that allow temporary omissions or estimations during the initial reporting periods, particularly in cases where technical limitations prevent full data collection.

The table below summarises the classification of indicators defined in the directive and clarifies their reporting status.

Category	Indicator Type	Description	Mandatory Status	Notes
Annex I	General Information	Data centre identification, location, type, ownership, floor area, redundancy	Mandatory	Required for all reporting entities
Annex II – Energy	Energy Consumption (EDC, EIT)	Total and IT energy consumption	Mandatory	Based on EN 50600 methodology
	Installed IT Power (PDIT)	Installed or rated IT load	Mandatory	Weighted averages allowed
	Renewable Energy (ERES-TOT, GOO, PPA, OS)	Energy sourcing breakdown	Mandatory	Avoid double counting
	Grid Interaction	Demand response, battery capacity	Mandatory	Supports grid stability analysis
Annex II – Cooling & Environment	Temperature (TIN, TWH)	Cooling setpoints and waste heat temperature	Mandatory	Requires continuous monitoring
	Water Usage (WIN, WIN-POT)	Total and potable water use	Mandatory	Based on WUE methodology
	Waste Heat Reuse (EREUSE)	Heat reused outside data centre boundary	Mandatory	Strict boundary definition
	Refrigerants	Cooling fluids used	Mandatory	Linked to F-gas regulation
Annex II – ICT Capacity	Server Capacity (CSERV)	Compute capacity (SERT-based)	Mandatory (partial)	Full reporting for new equipment
	Storage Capacity (CSTOR)	Installed storage capacity	Mandatory (partial)	Estimation allowed initially
Annex II – Traffic	Data Traffic (TIN,	Network throughput	Mandatory	Multiple data

Category	Indicator Type	Description	Mandatory Status	Notes
	TOUT, BIN, BOUT)	and data volume	(flexible)	sources allowed
Annex III	Derived Indicators (PUE, WUE, ERF, REF)	Sustainability indicators	Mandatory (indirect)	Automatically computed
Transitional Provisions	Missing or Estimated KPIs	Temporary omissions allowed	Conditional	Only during initial reporting phases

12.2 Hyperscaler Sustainability Initiatives and User-Facing Resources

Hyperscaler	Initiative / Tool	Type	Description	Access
Amazon Web Services (AWS)	AWS Sustainability Hub	Platform / Best practices	Provides guidance, dashboards, and recommendations to optimise cloud workloads for carbon and cost efficiency.	https://aws.amazon.com/sustainability/ (Amazon Web Services, Inc.)
	AWS Customer Carbon Footprint Tool	Analytics tool	Enables customers to estimate emissions associated with their AWS usage based on cloud consumption data.	https://aws.amazon.com/aws-cost-management/aws-customer-carbon-footprint-tool/
	AWS Well-Architected Framework – Sustainability Pillar	Guidelines	Offers architectural best practices for building energy-efficient and sustainable cloud applications.	https://docs.aws.amazon.com/wellarchitected/latest/sustainability-pillar/
Microsoft Azure	Microsoft Sustainability Manager	Platform / Analytics	Provides tools for tracking emissions, resource use, and sustainability KPIs across cloud and enterprise operations.	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/sustainability/microsoft-sustainability-manager
	Azure Emissions Impact Dashboard	Monitoring tool	Enables customers to measure carbon emissions from Azure services and identify	https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/sustainability/emissions-impact-dashboard

Hyperscaler	Initiative / Tool	Type	Description	Access
			optimisation opportunities.	
	OpenTelemetry & Azure Monitor	Open standard / Monitoring	Supports standardised telemetry collection and observability across cloud workloads, enabling sustainability analytics.	https://opentelemetry.io/ (Wikipedia)
Google Cloud	Google Cloud Carbon Footprint	Analytics tool	Provides detailed reporting of carbon emissions associated with cloud usage, including region-specific insights.	https://cloud.google.com/carbon-footprint
	Carbon-Aware Computing (Carbon Sense / Carbon-Intelligent APIs)	API / Research	Enables optimisation of workloads based on real-time carbon intensity of energy supply.	https://cloud.google.com/sustainability
	Data Centers 24/7 Carbon-Free Energy Initiative	Strategy / Open knowledge	Public methodology and reporting approach for achieving hourly matching of carbon-free energy.	https://datacenters.google/operating-sustainably/
Cross-hyperscaler / Open initiatives	Cloud Carbon Footprint (open source)	Open-source tool	Provides estimation of cloud emissions across AWS, Azure, and Google Cloud using unified methodologies.	https://www.cloudcarbonfootprint.org/
	Green Software Foundation	Training / Standards	Offers open training, best practices, and certification for building energy-efficient software systems.	https://greensoftware.foundation/